

The genus *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898 (Gastropoda, Vitrinellidae) in the Tropical Indo-Pacific

El género *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898 (Gastropoda, Vitrinellidae) en el Indo-Pacífico tropical

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RESUMEN

Se estudian las especies de la familia Vitrinellidae, género *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898, del Indo-Pacífico tropical, recolectadas durante las expediciones Tropical Deep-Sea Benthos, dirigidas por IRD y MNHN, en Madagascar, Isla de Reunión, Nueva Caledonia, Vanuatu, Fidji, las Islas Salomón, las Islas Filipinas, Taiwán, Islas de la Sociedad y Papua Nueva Guinea. Para su correcta identificación, hemos estudiado todo el material tipo de las especies previamente conocidas, disponible en los distintos museos donde fueron depositadas, verificando las sinonimias existentes y describiendo las especies nuevas encontradas.

En total se han reconocido 45 especies actuales, tanto de aguas superficiales como profundas, resultando 24 de ellas nuevas para la ciencia. Cuando fue posible, cada una de las especies se ilustró mediante fotografías al microscopio electrónico de barrido (MEB), discutiendo su variabilidad específica, y aportando información sobre el hábitat, distribución geográfica y rango batimétrico. Se aportan datos radulares y operculares relativos a la especie *Pseudoliotia granulosa* y sobre las partes blandas de *P. dispersa* n. sp. y *P. oscostata* n. sp.

Se comentan otras especies relacionadas o próximas a este género.

Ejemplares tipo de las especies examinadas con propósito comparativo son ilustradas: *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850; *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859; *Cyclostrema anaglyptum* A. Adams, 1863; *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864; *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871; *Vitrinella caelata* Garrett, 1873; *Liotia gowllandi* Brazier, 1874; *Cyclostrema pulchellum* Dunker, 1860; *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899; *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900; *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900; *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903; *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Liotia tribulationis* Hedley, 1909; *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925; *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958; *Pseudoliotia liliputia* Laseron, 1958; *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958; *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958; *Pseudoliotia granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971.

Nuevas especies (24): *Pseudoliotia dispersa*, *Pseudoliotia vicina*, *Pseudoliotia oscostata*, *Pseudoliotia indicta*, *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai*, *Pseudoliotia teresae*, *Pseudoliotia intermixta*, *Pseudoliotia salva*, *Pseudoliotia sementis*, *Pseudoliotia faceta*, *Pseudoliotia plurifunis*, *Pseudoliotia fijiensis*, *Pseudoliotia profunda*, *Pseudoliotia pressa*, *Pseudoliotia plusnodosa*, *Pseudoliotia inanis*, *Pseudoliotia seposita*, *Pseudoliotia distincta*, *Pseudoliotia*

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rudispiralis, *Pseudoliotia minor*, *Pseudoliotia coronata*, *Pseudoliotia philippinensis*, *Pseudoliotia nodenim* and *Pseudoliotia nodosa*.

Nuevos sinónimos: *Discreliotia* Laseron, 1958 = *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898; *Liochrysta* Laseron, 1958 = *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898; *Cyclostrema bushi* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 = *Cyclostrema pulchellum* Dunker, 1860; *Pseudoliotia liliputia* Laseron, 1958 = *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1891.

Nuevas combinaciones: *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859; *Vitrinella caelata* Garret, 1873; *Liotia calliglypta* Melvill, 1891; *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899; *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900; *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900; *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Liotia tribulationis* Hedley, 1909; *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925; *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958; y *Circlotoma bellatula* Feng, 1996 son transferidas a *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898.

Lectotipos designados para: *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850 and *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925.

Neotipos designados para: *Delphinula reeviana* Hinds, 1843 and *Liotia calliglypta* Melvill, 1891.

ABSTRACT

The species of the family Vitrinellidae, genus *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898 in the tropical Indo-Pacific collected during the Tropical deep-sea Benthos expeditions, directed by IRD and MNHN are studied; they were collected in Madagascar, Reunion Island, New Caledonia, Vanuatu, Fiji, the Solomon Islands, the Philippine Islands, Taiwan, Society Islands and Papua New Guinea. For a correct identification, we have studied all the type material available in several museums of the previously known species where they were deposited.

In total we recognize 45 Recent species, both from shallow and deep water, resulting 24 new for science. When possible, each species was illustrated by photographs of scanning electron microscope (SEM), discussing their intraspecific variability, providing when this was possible information about the habitat, geographical distribution and bathymetric range. Radular and opercular data related to the species *Pseudoliotia granulosa* n. sp. and on soft parts of *P. dispersa* n. sp. and *P. oscostata* n. sp. were shown.

Type specimens of species examined for comparative purposes are illustrated: *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850; *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859; *Cyclostrema anaglyptum* A. Adams, 1863; *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864; *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871; *Vitrinella caelata* Garret, 1873; *Liotia gowlandi* Brazier, 1874; *Cyclostrema pulchellum* Dunker, 1860; *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899; *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900; *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900; *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903; *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Liotia tribulationis* Hedley, 1909; *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925; *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958; *Pseudoliotia liliputia* Laseron, 1958; *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958; *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958 and *Pseudoliotia granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971.

New species (24): *Pseudoliotia dispersa*, *Pseudoliotia vicina*, *Pseudoliotia oscostata*, *Pseudoliotia indicta*, *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai*, *Pseudoliotia teresae*, *Pseudoliotia intermixta*, *Pseudoliotia salva*, *Pseudoliotia sementis*, *Pseudoliotia faceta*, *Pseudoliotia plurifunis*, *Pseudoliotia fijiensis*, *Pseudoliotia profunda*, *Pseudoliotia pressa*, *Pseudoliotia plusnodosa*, *Pseudoliotia inanis*, *Pseudoliotia seposita*, *Pseudoliotia distincta*, *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis*, *Pseudoliotia minor*, *Pseudoliotia coronata*, *Pseudoliotia philippinensis*, *Pseudoliotia nodenim* and *Pseudoliotia nodosa*.

New synonyms: *Discreliotia* Laseron, 1958 = *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898; *Liochrysta* Laseron, 1958 = *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898; *Cyclostrema bushi* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 = *Cyclostrema pulchellum* Dunker, 1860; *Pseudoliotia liliputia* Laseron, 1958 = *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1891.

New combinations: *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859; *Vitrinella caelata* Garret, 1873; *Liotia*

calliglypta Melvill, 1891; *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899; *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900; *Liotia phillata* Hedley, 1900; *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Liotia tribulationis* Hedley, 1909; *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925; *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958; and *Circlotoma bellatula* Feng, 1996 are transferred to *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898.

Lectotypes designated for: *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850 and *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925.

Neotypes designated for: *Delphinula reeviana* Hinds, 1843 and *Liotia calliglypta* Melvill, 1891.

Other species related or close to this genus are commented.

INTRODUCTION

Pseudoliotia Tate, 1898 is a genus of small 'vitrinelliform' gastropods with a wide distribution in the Indo-Pacific. Their shells are morphologically very similar to the vetigastropod genera *Cyclostrema* Marryat, 1818 and *Liotia* Gray, 1847 but differ from these in having a multispiral protoconch denoting a planktotrophic larval development, a totally non-calcareous operculum and a taenioglossate radula. ABBOTT (1950) was already aware that "a great number of species have been described under *Cyclostrema*, particularly from the Indo-Pacific region, which obviously belong to the Vitrinellidae".

These species are distributed from the infralittoral to the bathyal stages, but there are hardly any references regarding their microhabitat. In Australia, *Pseudoliotia speciosa* (Angas, 1871) and *P. micans* (A. Adams, 1850) are the most common vitrinellids, and were found living in seagrass meadows and on hard objects (like wood, stones) in estuaries (PONDER & DE KEYZER, 1998). KANO, KASE & KUBO (2003) provided details about the habitat of *Pseudoliotia asteriscus* (Gould, 1859) [misspelled *astericus*].

Due to their small size, live specimens for biological studies are difficult to find. Therefore, little or nothing is known about the anatomy, radula and operculum of most of the described species; there is only a study of the anatomy of *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 by WHITE (1942), and the anatomical data of *Pseudoliotia*

speciosa and radular data of *P. micans* provided by PONDER & DE KEYZER (1998). Usually, the material used in the original descriptions of minute marine species consists only of shells, resulting in that nothing more is known about those species.

The greatest impediment at the beginning of this work was the need for the study and comparison of the type material, since original descriptions and figures did not allow us a sufficient understanding of the species delimitations. Most of this material was collected during the XIXth century, is now dispersed in collections of museums as NHMUK, MB, MV, USNM, AMS among others, and unfortunately is damaged or lost for some species.

In the present work we studied all the material of *Pseudoliotia* in MNHN, originating from campaigns conducted by this institution in the Indo-Pacific. For its correct identification, we searched for all the type material, assessing the existing synonyms and describing the new species found.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present work, the species of vitrinellids of the genus *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898 from different oceanographic campaigns operated by MNHN in the Indo-Pacific were studied. These are as follows:

MD32 (1982) on board R/V *Marion Dufresne* around Reunion Island.

LAGON (1984-1989) on board R/V *Vauban* explored New Caledonia, to map the biological communities of the coral reef lagoon.

MUSORSTOM 3 (1985) on board R/V *Coriolis* in the Philippines.

MONTROUZIER (1993) land based expedition in Touho and Koumac areas, New Caledonia.

BATHUS 1-4 (1993-94) on board R/V *Alis* around New Caledonia, the Norfolk and Loyalty Ridges.

MUSORSTOM 8 (1994) on board R/V *Alis*, explored the Vanuatu Archipelago.

MUSORSTOM 10 (1998) on board R/V *Alis* explored the Fijian Archipelago.

SUVA 2 (1998) and SUVA 4 (1999) expeditions, also on board R/V *Alis*, surveyed lagoons and harbours in Viti Levu

BORDAU 1 (1999) on board R/V *Alis*, explored de Fijian Archipelago.

SALOMON 1 (2001) on board R/V *Alis* surveyed the central part of the Solomon Islands, from Guadalcanal to Malaita and Makira.

TAIWAN 2002 on board Shrimp Trawler Chenging Fa, to conduct broad-scale deep-water sampling around Taiwan.

PANGLAO 2004 (Panglao Marine Biodiversity Project) land-based expedition in the Central Philippines: Panglao, Dauis, Cortes, Tagbilaran and Baclayon.

PANGLAO 2005 (Panglao Deep Sea Cruise) explored and researched the deep-sea fauna of the Bohol and Sulu Seas.

SANTO 2006 (Global Biodiversity Survey) land-based expedition in the waters of Espiritu Santo Island in Vanuatu.

TARASOC (2009) on board R/V *Alis*, explored the Society Islands and Tarava seamounts.

ATIMO VATAE (2012) land based expedition to Madagascar "Deep South" marine fauna & flora.

PAPUA NIUGINI (2012) land based expedition to Madang and Kavieng areas, Papua New Guinea.

Therefore, materials used in this study were obtained in both shallow and deep waters of Taiwan, Madagascar, Reunion Islands, New Caledonia, Vanuatu, Fiji, the Solomon and the Philippines, Society Islands and Papua New Guinea.

For most of the *MUSORSTOM/Tropical Deep-Sea Benthos* cruises, station numbers are preceded by a two-letter prefix which refers to the type of gear used: CC, chalut à crevettes (Shrimp Trawl); CH, chalut commercial (Otter Trawl); CP, chalut à perche (Beam Trawl); DR, drague à roche (Rock Dredge); DW, drague Warén (Warén Dredge). Since 1985, all stations in the main *MUSORSTOM* cruise series are numbered consecutively (now over 3000), but many satellite expeditions have used their own numbering system starting with 1.

On a steep slope, depth intervals for a single haul can span several hundred meters. As a consequence, when summarizing the bathymetric range of a species, we take the inner values of the deepest and shallowest stations, as there is no evidence that the species occurs beyond these values. For instance, if a species has been collected at 6 stations at depths of e.g. 611-636 m, 582-594 m, 693-811 m, 749-799 m, 283-405 m, and 350-800 m, the combined confirmed bathymetric range is 405-749 m, the depths between which the species definitely occurred, not 283-811 m.

All the studied species are illustrated using Scanning Electron Microscopes (SEM) Quanta 200 and AVO. Measurements of the teleoconch, including the maximum height (H) and maximum diameter (D) are based in the scale bar of the SEM photographs. The protoconch was measured by VERDUIN'S (1976) method in which a nucleus is considered at the beginning of the spire (Figure 1).

Abbreviations:

AMNH American Museum of Natural History, New York

AMS Australian Museum, Sidney

Figure 1. A, B. Method of measurement of the protoconch whorls.

Figura 1. A, B. Método de medición de las vueltas de la protoconcha.

ANSP Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia

MHNS Museo de Historia Natural, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris

MOM Musée Oceanographique, Monaco

MVA Museum Victoria Australia, Melbourne

NHMUK Natural History Museum United Kingdom, London

NMW National Museum of Wales, Cardiff

NSMT National Science Museum Natural History, Tokyo

NSW New South Wales Museum, Sidney

RBINS Royal Belgium Institute of Natural Sciences

SAM South Australian Museum, Adelaide

SMF Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt

USNM National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington

ZMB Museum für Naturkunde Zoologisches, Berlin

D maximum diameter of the shell, measured perpendicular to the axis of coiling

Stn. station

s shell

spm (s) alive collected specimen (s)

juv juvenile

fragm fragment

H total height of the shell

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily TRUNCATELLOIDEA Gray, 1840 Family VITRINELLIDAE Bush, 1897

PONDER & DE KEYZER (1998) placed *Pseudoliotia* in the family Vitrinellidae. CRISCIONE & PONDER (2013) distinguished Rissooidea and the Truncatelloidea as separate superfamilies, and placed the family Tornidae Sacco, 1896 (with Vitrinellidae treated as a junior synonym) in the latter. This was based on a phylogenetic analysis of 43 species representing 14 of the 23 families previously included in Rissooidea s.l. and the three families of Cingulopsoidea. They reached the conclusion that the Tornidae, represented in their study by two taxa (*Circulus subtatei* [currently *Ela-chorbis subtatei* (Suter, 1907)] and *Pseudoliotia micans* (A. Adams, 1850) would cluster together, with *Nozeba* (Iravadiidae) being sister to the Tornidae. BOUCHET ET AL. (2017) separated again Vitrinellidae from Tornidae based on a statement by TAKANO & KANO (2014) that *Vitrinella* was sister to *Iravadia* (currently in family Iravadiidae), rather than with *Teinostoma*. However the taxon sampling in the latter paper, primarily

concerned with another superfamily (Eulimoidea), does not include *Tornus* and is so limited that the family-level taxonomy of this group is better considered as still unresolved. The present work is essentially directed at the species level, therefore BOUCHET ET AL. (2017) are followed uncritically.

PONDER & DE KEYZER (1998: 763), based on several sources and several different genera, describe the vitrinellid animal as follows: “*The head has long, strap-like cephalic tentacles, bearing long stationary “setae” on the distal ends and with the eyes in bulges at their outer bases. The snout is long and bilobed distally and the anterior end of the foot is expanded into small lateral projections. Posteriorly, the foot is either indented or rounded, often with a metapodial tentacle dorsally, and there is no posterior pedal gland. The mantle edge bears a pair of pallial tentacles on the right side and a single one on the left. The ctenidium is well developed and sometimes has the anterior end free and capable of projecting from the mantle cavity. The osphradium is long and narrow*”.

Genus *Pseudoliotia* Tate, 1898

Pseudoliotia Tate, 1898: 71. [Type species by original designation: *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850. Recent, South Australia].

Liochrysa Laceron, 1958: 166. [Type species by original designation: *Microtheca acidula* Melvill & Standen, 1899] [error for *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899].

Discreliotia Laceron, 1958: 168. [Type species by original designation: *Discreliotia radians* Laceron, 1958]. **New synonym.**

Description: in TATE (1899: 215): “*Shell somewhat like Liotia; test thick and porcellanous; aperture oblique to the axis; its margin thickened; umbilicus reduced to a mere chink; operculum horny, multispiral*”.

The radula has the typical rissooidean form, the central teeth having a single pair of basal denticles (PONDER & DE KEYZER, 1998: 764, fig. 15.119 J, and herein Figure 3).

The operculum is circular with a central nucleus (Figure 3).

PONDER & DE KEYZER (1998) presented a drawing of a living *Pseudoliotia speciosa* (Angas, 1871) showing a narrow anteriorly bilobed edge of the foot, wide, club-shaped and pilose cephalic tentacles, lateral projections on the anterior edge of the foot, one metapodial tentacle and the two right pallial tentacles.

Remarks: TATE (1898a: 71) proposed *Pseudoliotia* as a new genus and designated *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams,

Figure 2. Living animals. A: *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp., Philippines, Bohol Island, Stn. S33, 9°43.8'N-123°52.7'E, 1-3 m; B-E: *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp., Vanuatu, Stn. VM19, 15°22.2'S-167°11.1'E, intertidal.

Figura 2. Animales vivos. A: *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp., Filipinas, Isla de Bohol, Stn. S33, 9°43,8'N-123°52,7'E, 1-3 m; B-E: *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp., Vanuatu, Stn. VM19, 15°22,2'S-167°11,1'E, intermareal.

1850 as type species. In another paper, TATE (1898b: 239) provided a brief account of the genus, describing the operculum as horny and multispiral. Finally, TATE (1899: 215) fully described the genus *Pseudoliotia* mentioning that the type species “recalls *Mölleria* which

is differentiated by a calcareous operculum. Judging from published figure and description, *Cyclostrema eburnea* Nevill, is congeneric”.

WHITE (1942), in his study on the anatomy of *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, showed that its

Figure 3. Radula and operculum of *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. from Vanuatu, Segond Channel, bridge on Matafou river, SANTO 2006: Stn. VM19, intertidal. A-D: different visions of the radulae; E, F: operculum; G: microsculpture of the operculum.

Figura 3. Rádula y opérculo de *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. de Vanuatu, Segond Channel, Puente del río Matafou, SANTO 2006: Stn. VM19, intermareal. A-D: diferentes vistas de la radula; E, F: opérculo; G: microescultura del opérculo.

Figure 4. A: *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850, lectotype, 3.0 mm (NHMUK 1968817-D-21072017). B: *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864, syntype, 3.0 mm (NHMUK 1870.10.26.139), Australia. C: *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859, lectotype, 1.77 mm (USNM 24055, original number: C.2050), Hong Kong. D: *Cyclostrema pulchella* Dunker, 1860, holotype, 3.0 mm (SMF-MC313703), Japan. E: *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, shells, 2.15 and 2.4 mm (NMW.1955.158 Coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55879), Vietnam. F: *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871, shell, 2.37 mm (NMW.1955.158.26790), Australia.

Figura 4. A: *Cyclostrema micans* (A. Adams, 1850), lectotipo, 3,0 mm (NHMUK 1968817-D-21072017). B: *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864, sintipo, 3,0 mm (NHMUK 1870.10.26.139), Australia. C: *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859, lectotipo, 1,77 mm (USNM 24055, número original: C.2050), Hong Kong. D: *Cyclostrema pulchella* Dunker, 1860, holotipo, 3,0 mm (SMF-MC313703), Japón. E: *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 conchas, 2,15 y 2,4 mm (NMW.1955.158 Coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55879), Vietnam. F: *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871, concha, 2,37 mm (NMW.1955.158.26790), Australia.

operculum is also wholly corneous and the radula taenioglossate.

ABBOTT (1950), in his revision of Western Atlantic *Cyclostrema* wrote: "An attempt was made by K.M. WHITE (1942) to define the genus *Cyclostrema* with an

anatomical study of "*Cyclostrema*" *bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer from India. The operculum is wholly chitinous and the radula taenioglossate. These features exclude this species from the family Liotiidae. This species is close to *Pseudo-*

Figure 5. A: *Vitrinella caelata* (Garrett, 1873), syntype, 2.0 mm (ANSP 20559). Fiji. B: *Liotia gowlandi* (Brazier, 1874), syntype, 2.4 mm (NHMUK 1875.5.28.2), Percy Island, N.E. Australia. C: *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, shells, 2.05 and 2.06 mm (NMW.1955.158, coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55883), Vietnam. D: *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958, holotype, 2.5 mm (AMS C.102619), Australia. E: *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958, holotype, 3.5 mm (AMS C.102623), Australia. F: *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958, holotype, 3.0 mm (AMS C.102620), Australia.

Figura 5. A: *Vitrinella caelata* (Garrett, 1873), sintipo, 2,0 mm (ANSP 20559). Fidji. B: *Liotia gowlandi* (Brazier, 1874), sintipo, 2,4 mm, (NHMUK 1875.5.28.2), Isla de Percy, NE de Australia. C: *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, conchas, 2,05 y 2,06 mm (MNW.1955.158, coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55883), Vietnam. D: *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958, holotipo, 2,5 mm (AMS C.102619). Australia. E: *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958, holotipo, 3,5 mm (AMS C.102623). Australia. F: *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958, holotipo, 3,0 mm (AMS C.102620). Australia.

liotia micans A. Adams, 1850 and *P. pseudocancellata* Bush, 1897".

LASERON (1958) wrote: "The characters of *Pseudoliotia* are the small, heavy shell with depressed spire and strong cancellate sculpture, the very oblique aperture with thickened margins but no

varix, and the open, deep umbilicus. The type locality of *C. micans* is South Australia. Several species occur in northern Australia, but TATE (1899) considered them all as variations of only one species." In the same publication he described three new species of *Pseudolio-*

Figure 6. A: *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp., holotype, 2.1 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34125), Vanuatu. B: *Pseudoliotia vicina* n. sp., holotype, 2.27 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34127), Vanuatu. C: *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp., holotype, 2.8 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34128), Papua New Guinea. D: *Delphinula reeviana* Hinds, 1843, neotype, 10.6 mm (NMW 1955.158 PR 26786), Singapore. E: *Cyclostrema anaglyptum* A. Adams, 1863, syntype, about 4.4 mm (MVS F31483), Japan. F: *Liotia calliglypta* Melvill, 1891, neotype, 5.0 mm (coated shell, AMS C.559538, older number C.7510b), Darnley Is. (09°35'00"S-143°46'00"E), Torres Strait.

Figura 6. A: *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp., holotipo, 2,1 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34125), Vanuatu. B: *Pseudoliotia vicina* n. sp., holotipo, 2,27 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34127), Vanuatu. C: *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp., holotipo, 2,8 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34128), Papua Nueva Guinea. D: *Delphinula reeviana* Hinds, 1843, neotipo, 10,6 mm (NMW 1955.158 PR 26786), Singapur. E: *Cyclostrema anaglyptum* A. Adams, 1863, sintipo, aprox. 4,4 mm (MVS F31483), Japón. F: *Liotia calliglypta* Melvill, 1891, neotipo, 5,0 mm (concha metalizada, AMS C.559538, núm. anterior C.7510b), Isla Darnley (09°35'00"S-143°46'00"E), Estrecho de Torre.

tia: *P. tropica*, *P. axialis* and *P. liliputia* and created, among others, the two new genera *Liochrysta* and *Discreliotia*. *Liochrysta* was subsequently placed in synonymy with *Pseudoliotia*. In relation to *Discreliotia*, if we assessed the mor-

phological characters of *D. radians* (Fig. 5E), type species of the genus, and concluded that it is morphologically close to *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958 (Fig. 5D), and we cannot find reasons for a generic separation. For this reason, *Dis-*

Figure 7. A: *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899, holotype, 5.0 mm (coated shell, NHMUK 1899.2.23.15.), Australia. B: *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900, holotype, 4 mm (NHMUK 1900.11.10.39), Philippines. C: *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903, syntype, 6.3 mm (NHMUK 1903.12.15.64), Persian Gulf. D: *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp., shell, 7.1 mm (MNHN), Philippines. E: *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai* n. sp., holotype, 8.87 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34130), New Caledonia. F: *Pseudoliotia teresae* n. sp., holotype, 8.32 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34131), Reunion.

Figura 7. A: *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899, holotipo, 5,0 mm (NHMUK 1899.2.23.15.), Australia. B: *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900, holotipo, 4 mm (NHMUK 1900.11.10.39), Filipinas. C: *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903, sintipo, 6,3 mm (NHMUK 1903.12.15.64), Golfo Pérsico. D: *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp., concha, 7,1 mm (MNHN), Filipinas. E: *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai* n. sp., holotipo, 8,87 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34130), Nueva Caledonia. F: *Pseudoliotia teresae* n. sp., holotipo, 8,32 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34131), Reunión.

creliotia is herein regarded as a junior synonym of *Pseudoliotia*.

HIGO, CALLOMON & GOTO (1999) recorded 6 species of *Pseudoliotia* as occurring in Japanese waters: *P. pulchella* (Dunker, 1860) (G992), *P. granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971 (G993), *P. reeveana* (Reeve, 1843) (G994), *P. asteriscus*

(Gould, 1859) (G995), *P. anaglypta* (G996) and *P. godeti* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907) (G997), giving type locality, distribution, habitat and original genus of each species. OKUTANI (2000) provides a figure and a brief description of four of these: *P. pulchella*, *P. asteriscus*, *P. reeveana* and *P. granulosa*.

Figure 8. A: *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp., holotype, 4.4 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34133), Papua New Guinea. B: *Pseudoliotia salva* n. sp., holotype, 4.4 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34134), Taiwan. C: *Pseudoliotia sementis* n. sp., holotype, 2.6 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34101), Papua New Guinea. D: *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp., shell, 2.6 mm (MNHN), Papua New Guinea. E: *Pseudoliotia granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971, holotype, 10.8 mm (NSMT – MoR 17783). F: *Pseudoliotia plurifunus* n. sp., holotype, 4.6 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34104), Vanuatu.

Figura 8. A: *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp., holotipo, 4,4 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34133), Papua Nueva Guinea. B: *Pseudoliotia salva* n. sp., holotipo, 4,4 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34134), Taiwan. C: *Pseudoliotia sementis* n. sp., holotipo, 2,6 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34101), Papua Nueva Guinea. D: *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp., concha, 2,6 mm (MNHN), Papua Nueva Guinea. E: *Pseudoliotia granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971, holotipo, 10,8 mm (NSMT – MoR 17783). F: *Pseudoliotia plurifunus* n. sp., holotipo, 4,6 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34104), Vanuatu.

SASAKI (2008) mentioned that “The shell of *Pseudoliotia* is sculptured by rough spiral ribs, granules on the ribs, and lamellate axial ribs connecting the granules. *Pseudoliotia pulchella* (Fig. 4D-E) can be collected from the undersides of buried stones in embayments, and the living shell is completely covered with a dark, rusty substance.”

The habitat of *Pseudoliotia pulchella* is therefore similar to that of *Tornus subcarinatus* (Montagu, 1803), an European species which lives on the underside of boulders and stones deeply embedded in sand, in places exposed to strong waves and currents, together with other molluscan species (e.g. *Alvania lactea* (Michaud, 1832), *Bornia*

Table I. Described species of Indo-Pacific belonging to *Pseudoliotia*, according to WoRMS and OBIS Indo-Pacific Molluscan Databases. Specific names after GNI-Global Names Index (Index of scientific names) beta.

Tabla I. Especies del Indopacífico descritas en el género *Pseudoliotia*, de acuerdo a las bases de datos WoRMS y OBIS. Nombres específicos extraídos de GNI-Global Names Index (Índice de nombres científicos) beta.

	WoRMS	OBIS
<i>Pseudoliotia acidalia</i> (Melvill & Standen, 1899)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia anaglypta</i> (A. Adams, 1863)		+
<i>Pseudoliotia asteriscus</i> (Gould, 1859)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia axialis</i> Laseron, 1958	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia bushi</i> (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907)		+
<i>Pseudoliotia caelata</i> (Garrett, 1873)		+
<i>Pseudoliotia calliglypta</i> (Melvill, 1891)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia godeti</i> (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907)		+
<i>Pseudoliotia gowllandi</i> (Brazier, 1874)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia granulosa</i> Kuroda & Habe, 1971		+
<i>Pseudoliotia hattenbergeri</i> Rolán & Rubio, 2002	+	
<i>Pseudoliotia henjamensis</i> (Melvill & Standen, 1903)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia linguifera</i> (Thiele, 1925)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia micans</i> (A. Adams, 1850)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia philtata</i> (Hedley, 1900)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia pulchella</i> (Dunker, 1860)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia radians</i> (Laseron, 1958)		+
<i>Pseudoliotia reeviana</i> (Hinds, 1843)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia speciosa</i> (Angas, 1871)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia tribulationis</i> (Hedley, 1909)	+	+
<i>Pseudoliotia tropica</i> Laseron, 1958	+	+

sebetia (O.G. Costa, 1830), *Pseudopythina macandrewi* (P. Fischer, 1867) as referred in ROLÁN & RUBIO (2002). The only West African species of *Pseudoliotia* (*P. hattenbergeri*) was described in the same paper.

In order to know “all” the described species of Indo-Pacific belonging to *Pseudoliotia*, we have consulted appropriate databases (WoRMS, OBIS Indo-Pacific Molluscan Database) and compared the data retrieved with those of GNI-Global Names Index (Index of sci-

entific names) beta, with the results shown in Table I.

Of the 21 species referred in Table I, 10 are from Australia, 3 from Japan, 2 from Annam, 2 from Indonesia, 1 from Hong Kong, 1 from Fiji, 1 from the Persian Gulf and 1 is an outlier from Congo, West Africa.

In this study, we could recognize 45 species which are illustrated and figured in the following pages, and are reproduced on synoptic plates (Figures 4-11) for easier comparison.

Micans Group

The species which form the Micans group are characterized by the presence in the last whorl of the teleoconch of spiral cords forming strong nodules at the inter-

sections with the axial ribs. The first sub-sutural cord marks a strong angle on the shell profile and forms a shoulder which disappears in the last quarter whorl.

The group is formed by the following species:

Pseudoliotia micans (A. Adams, 1850)
Pseudoliotia asteriscus (Gould, 1859)
Pseudoliotia pulchella (Dunker, 1860)
Pseudoliotia speciosa (Angas, 1871)
Pseudoliotia caelata (Garrett, 1873)
Pseudoliotia gowllandi (Brazier, 1874)

Pseudoliotia godeti (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907)

Pseudoliotia axialis Laseron, 1958
Pseudoliotia radians (Laseron, 1958)
Pseudoliotia tropica Laseron, 1958
Pseudoliotia dispersa n. sp.
Pseudoliotia vicina n. sp.
Pseudoliotia oscostata n. sp.

Pseudoliotia micans (A. Adams, 1850) (Figures 4A, 4B, 12A-L)

Cyclostrema micans A. Adams, 1850: 44, plate 48. [Type locality: Port Lincoln, South Australia].

Liotia angasi Crosse, 1864: 343, pl. 13, fig. 4. [Type locality: St Vincent's Gulf, South Australia].

Pseudoliotia micans (A. Adams, 1850): TATE (1898a: 71).

"*Cyclostrema*" *micans* (A. Adams, 1850): DEKKER, H. & ORLIN, Z. (2000: 21).

Type material: Lectotype (here designated) of *Cyclostrema micans* A. Adams, 1850 (NHMUK 1968817/1) and 12 paralectotypes (NHMUK 1968817/2-13) (see Remarks), Hugh Cuming collection (pers. inf. Andreia Salvador). *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864, 3 syntypes in MNHN [MNHN-IM-2000-31021]; 2 syntypes of *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864 in NHMUK 1870.10.26.139 (images by Kevin Webb, NHMUK Photographic Unit).

Material examined: Only the type material.

Description, based on the lectotype of Cyclostrema micans A. Adams, 1850 (NHMUK 1968817/1): Shell small (<3.50 mm), solid, formed by a little more than 4.5 whorls, turbiniform, wider than high, narrowly umbilicate.

The protoconch has 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls and is totally smooth. The teleoconch has 3 whorls. Last whorl with 6 spiral cords, with strong nodules at the intersections with axial ribs. The first subsutural cord angles strongly the shell and forms on the first whorls a shoulder, which disappears in the last quarter whorl; the 3 peripheral cords and the basal one have much thicker nodules than the periumbilical one. The spaces between the cords are concave.

Umbilicus funnel-shaped, narrow and deep, delimited by a cord with small nodules, inside with numerous axial folds. Aperture rounded, strongly prosocline; outer lip thickened, externally indented by the termination of the cords, thinning out to a narrow rim at the edge.

Habitat: This species lives subtidally under rocks and stones. It was also found in seagrass meadows and other substrates, and under rocks and debris

in sheltered bays and estuaries in the lower littoral and shallow sub-littoral zones (BEECHEY, 2014)

Distribution: South Australia: Port Lincoln (A. ADAMS, 1850), St Vincent's Gulf (CROSSE, 1864). Occurs also in south-eastern Australia (NSW, TAS and VIC) and elsewhere in the Indo-West Pacific (LASERON, 1954, 1958); Tasmania (MAY, 1921); Red Sea (DEKKER & ORLIN, 2000); Maharashtra, W India, Andaman and Nicobar Islands (SUBBA RAO, 2003).

BEECHEY (2014) considered it endemic to Australia: Cape Moreton, Queensland, southwards and around southern Australia to central South Australia, including Tasmania.

Remarks: TATE (1899: 223), in his revision of the Australian Cyclostrematidae and Liotiidae, having studied the types of *C. micans* and *C. angasi* in the British Museum, declared them conspecific, notwithstanding they had been treated as distinct, generically and specifically, by TRYON (1888).

Having examined 4 photographs of the syntypes of *Cyclostrema micans* from the Hugh Cuming Collection (NHMUK 1968817/), we could observe that they include mixed shells of *P. pulchella* and

Figure 9. A: *Pseudoliotia fijiensis* n. sp., holotype, 7.00 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34105), Fiji. B: *Liotia tribulationis* Hedley, 1909, shell, 1.77 mm (MNHN), Vanuatu. C: *Pseudoliotia profundus* n. sp., holotype, 1.64 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34107), Solomon Islands (1036-1138 m). D: *Pseudoliotia pressa* n. sp., holotype, 2.06 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34108), Madagascar. E: *Pseudoliotia plusnodosa* n. sp., holotype, 2.35 mm (MNHN IM-2000-3409), Tahiti, Society Islands. F: *Pseudoliotia distincta* n. sp., holotype, 2.1 mm (MNHN IM-2000-3411), Tahiti (347-460 m).

Figura 9. A: *Pseudoliotia fijiensis* n. sp., holotipo, 7,00 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34105), Fidji. B: *Liotia tribulationis* Hedley, 1909, concha, 1,77 mm (MNHN), Vanuatu. C: *Pseudoliotia profundus* n. sp., holotipo, 1,64 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34107), Islas Salomón (1036-1138 m). D: *Pseudoliotia pressa* n. sp., holotipo, 2,06 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34108), Madagascar. E: *Pseudoliotia plusnodosa* n. sp., holotipo, 2,35 mm (MNHN IM-2000-3409), Tahití, Islas de la Sociedad. F: *Pseudoliotia distincta* n. sp., holotipo, 2,1 mm (MNHN IM-2000-3411), Tahití (347-460 m).

P. micans. Only the shell labelled as 1968817-D-21072017 agrees with the description of *C. micans* and is here selected as lectotype, while the other three (1968817-A-21072017; 1968817-B-21072017; 1968817-C-21072017) are shells of *P. pulchella*.

The shells are covered by a dark brown periostracum when alive (Fig. 12H); this thick brown periostracum wears away exposing a white shell with grey markings, which seems to quickly erode to dull white (see BEECHY, 2014).

Figure 10. A: *Pseudoliotia seposita* n. sp., holotype, 2.16 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34112), Tahiti. B: *Pseudoliotia inanis* n. sp., holotype and paratype, 2.05 and 1.8 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34113/34114), New Caledonia. C: *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900, holotype, 5.0 mm (AMS/C8101), Australia. D: *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925, lectotype, 2.47 mm (ZMB/moll – 10491), Indonesia. E: *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp., holotype and paratype, 3.03 and 3.26 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34115/34116), Papua New Guinea.

Figura 10. A: *Pseudoliotia seposita* n. sp. holotipo, 2,16 mm, (MNHN IM-2000-34112). Tahiti. B: *Pseudoliotia inanis* n. sp. holotipo y paratipo, 2,05 and 1,8 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34113/34114). Nueva Caledonia. C: *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900, holotipo, 5,0 mm (AMS/C8101), Australia. D: *Vitrinella linguifera* Thiele, 1925, lectotipo, 2,47 mm (ZMB/moll – 10491), Indonesia. E: *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp., holotipo y paratipo, 3,03 y 3,26 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34115/34116), Papua Nueva Guinea.

Pseudoliotia asteriscus (Gould, 1859) n. comb. (Figures 4C, 12M-O)

Liotia asteriscus Gould, 1859: 142 [Type locality: Hong Kong].

Type material: Syntype of *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859 (now lectotype) USNM C2050, figured by YEN (1944, pl. 50, figs. 30-31). Lectotype (with original number: C2050) designated by JOHNSON (1964: 43) and renumbered USNM 24055. Type locality: Hong Kong, North Pacific Ocean. Collector William Stimpson. Examined by photograph. Paralectotype of *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859 (filed as *Brookula asteriscus*). Registration number in ANSP: 38463. Locality: Hong Kong, China. Collector William Stimpson. Not examined.

Material examined: Only the type material.

Figure 11. A: *Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp., holotype, 3.35 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34117), Philippines. B: *Pseudoliotia coronata* n. sp., holotype, 2.8 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34119), Vanuatu. C: *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp., shell, 2.85 mm (MNHN). Vanuatu. D: *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp., holotype, 1.72 mm. (MNHN IM-2000-34122), Solomon Is. E: *Pseudoliotia philippinensis* n. sp., holotype and paratype, 1.55 and 2.2 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34123/34124), Philippines. F: *Circlotoma bellatula* Feng, 1996, shell, 1.45 mm (MNHN), Papua New Guinea.

Figura 11. A: *Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp., holotipo, 3,35 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34117), Filipinas. B: *Pseudoliotia coronata* n. sp., holotipo, 2,8 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34119), Vanuatu. C: *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp., concha, 2,85 mm (MNHN), Fidji. D: *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp., holotipo, 1,72 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34122), Islas Salomón. E: *Pseudoliotia philippinensis* n. sp., holotipo y paratipo, 1,55 y 2,2 mm (MNHN IM-2000-34123/34124), Filipinas. F: *Circlotoma bellatula* Feng, 1996, concha, 1,45 mm (MNHN), Papua Nueva Guinea.

Description, based on the lectotype (USNM 24055): Shell very small (<2.00 mm), solid, formed by a little more than 4 whorls, turbiniform with a relatively high spire, somewhat wider than high (H/D: 0.68), moderately umbilicate.

The protoconch, very dirty and eroded on the examined specimen, has $1\frac{3}{4}$ whorls and measures about 350 μ m.

The teleoconch has $2\frac{1}{4}$ whorls, apically angled and basally convex. The first whorl is angled by a thick nodulose carina. The last whorl has 5 thick carinae with nodules (1 subsutural, 2 peripheral, 1 at the base and 1 periumbilical). The nodules of the peripheral carinae are very thick and prominent, being 18 on the last whorl. The axial ribs

Figure 12. A-L: *Pseudoliotia micans* (A. Adams, 1859). A: Original figures. B-C: lectotype, NHMUK 1968817-D-21072017 (images taken by Kevin Webb, NHMUK, Photographic Unit). D-G: syntypes of *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864, 3.11, 3.05 mm in diameter, NHMUK 1870.10.26.139, St. Vincent's Gulf, South Australia; H: shell with periostracum, 2.5 mm; I-J: shells, 2.8 mm, Simpsons Bay, Port Hacking, NSW (C.326758) reproduced from <seashellsofsw.org.au/Tornidae/> with permission of Des Beechey). K-L: syntypes of *Liotia angasi*, MNHN-IM-2000-31021, 3.0 mm. M-O: Lectotype of *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859, 1.77 mm in diameter x 1.2 mm high, USNM 24055 (Original Number: C.2050). Collector: William Stimpson (photographed by Yolanda Villacampa, Department of Invertebrate Zoology from Smithsonian Institution).

Figura 12. A-L: *Pseudoliotia micans* (A. Adams, 1859). A: Figura original. B-C: lectotipo, NHMUK 1968817-D-21072017 (imágenes tomadas por Kevin Webb, NHMUK, Photographic Unit). D-G: *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864, sintipos, 3,11, 3,05 mm de diámetro, NHMUK 1870.10.26.139, St. Vincents Gulf, Sur de Australia; H: concha con periostraco, 2,5 mm; I-J: conchas, 2,8 mm, Bahía de Simpsons, Port Hacking, NSW (C.326758) in <seashellsofsw.org.au/Tornidae/>. K-L: sintipos de *Liotia angasi*, 3,0 mm, MNHN-IM-2000-31021. M-O: Lectotipo de *Liotia asteriscus* Gould, 1859, USNM 24055 (Número original: C.2050), diámetro 1,77 mm x 1,2 mm alto. Collector: William Stimpson. (fotografiado por Yolanda Villacampa, Department of Invertebrate Zoology de la Smithsonian Institution).

are thick and connect the nodules between carinae, forming a re-entering angle within the interspace.

Umbilicus wide and deep, delimited by a cord of small nodules, from which inside there are axial ribs and some spiral cordlets. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area and columella very thick, not reflected; outer lip thickened, externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: 1.77 mm in diameter, 1.2 in height (H/D: 0.68).

Habitat: Intertidal, on sandy bottom (HIGO ET AL., 1999); on sandy gravel

bottom in intertidal zone (OKUTANI, 2000).

Distribution: Hong Kong (GOULD, 1859); Seto inland sea and China (HIGO ET AL., 1999); from Okinawa to continental southeast Asia (OKUTANI, 2000).

Remarks: The species did not appear doubtful to previous authors: GOULD (1859) commented that although the shell was very small, it was evidently an adult and was well characterized. OKUTANI (2000) wrote that it is similar to *P. pulchella*, but much smaller, and with stronger axial ribs.

Pseudoliotia pulchella (Dunker, 1860) (Figures 4D-E, 13A-J)

Cyclostrema pulchellum Dunker, 1860: 225. [Type locality: "im Hafen von Decima" (Dejima, harbour of Nagasaki City, western Kyūshū, Japan)].

Cyclostrema bushi Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907: 207-208, pls. 5-7, figs. 11-13. [Type locality not mentioned in the original description but the syntypes are labelled: Ben-Son beach, Vietnam like the preceding species in that paper, *Cyclostrema godeti*]. The name of the species has to be emended to *bushae* following ICZN art. 31.1.2 because Dautzenberg & Fischer stated that the species is dedicated to Miss K. Bush.

Pseudoliotia pulchella (Dunker, 1860): HABE (1964: 33, pl. 10, fig. 32); (ROBBA ET AL., 2004: 54-55).

Type material: Holotype of *Cyclostrema pulchella* Dunker, 1860. Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt, registration number: SMF-313703. Holotype figured by JANSSEN (1993) and examined by photographs sent by Dr. Ronald Janssen. Three syntypes of *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, registration number: MNHN-IM-2000-31062. Examined by photographs.

Other material examined: (11 spms): Baie d'Along (currently Ha-Long, Vietnam), collected by Bavay, identified as *Cyclostrema bushi* Dautzenberg & Fischer, in National Museum Wales: NMW.1955.158, Melvill-Tomlin coll. n° PR55879.

Description, based on the holotype of Cyclostrema pulchellum Dunker, 1860: Shell small (<3.00 mm), rather solid, formed by more than 4 whorls, turbini-form with a rather low spire, wider than high (H/D: 0.52), carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 1 ¾ whorls and is totally smooth. The teleoconch has 2 ¼ whorls. The first whorl is angled by a nodulose carina. The last whorl has in addition 5 thick nodose carinae (1 sub-sutural, 3 peripheral, and 1 periumbilical). The nodules of the peripheral carinae are very thick and prominent, being 22 on the last whorl. The axial ribs are thick and connect the nodules between carinae, forming a re-entering angle

within the interspace; this angle is ca. 150° between the subsutural carina and the peripheral, and 135° between the two peripheral carinae (see Figure 13B).

Umbilicus wide and deep, delimited by a cord bearing small nodules, inside with rather thick axial ribs. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area and columella thick, not reflected; outer lip thickened, externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: 2.90 mm in diameter, 1.50 in height (H/D: 0.52).

Description, based on the syntypes of Cyclostrema bushae Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907: Shell small (<3.00 mm), formed by a little more than 3 ½ whorls, rather solid, orbicular, depressed, wider

Figure 13. *Pseudoliotia pulchella* (Dunker, 1860). A-C: holotype of *Cyclostrema pulchellum* Dunker, 1860, 3.0 mm, (SMF - Mollusca Collection SMF-313703; Senckenberg DB). Locality: Dejima, harbour of Nagasaki City, western Kyūshū, Japan. Photo S. Hof, courtesy of R. Janssen, Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut Frankfurt/M. D-G: shells (identified as *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907), 2.15, 2.4, 2.4, 2.58 mm in diameter, NMW.1955.158, Coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55879, Halong Bay, Taikin (Tonkin), Vietnam. Original collection: Bavay. H-I: protoconch and detail. J: microsculpture.

Figura 13. *Pseudoliotia pulchella* (Dunker, 1860). A-C: holotipo de *Cyclostrema pulchellum* Dunker, 1860, 3,0 mm, (SMF - Colección de Molluscos SMF-313703; Senckenberg DB). Localidad: Dejima, bahía de Nagasaki City, al oeste de Kyūshū, Japón. Foto S. Hof, cortesia de R. Janssen, Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut Frankfurt/M. D-G: conchas (identificadas como *Cyclostrema bushae* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907), 2,15, 2,4, 2,4, 2,58 mm de diámetro, MNW.1955.158, Coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55879, Halong Bay, Taikin (Tonkin), Vietnam. Colección original: Bavay. H-I: protoconcha y detalle. J: microscultura.

than high (H/D: 0.50), with spire little elevated, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has slightly more than one whorl, measures about 400 μm and is completely smooth. The teleoconch has 2 $\frac{1}{4}$ whorls, angled adapically and basally. The first whorl is angled by a nodose carina. The last whorl have with 5 thick nodular carinae (1 subsutural, 2 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical).

The nodules on the peripheral carina are very thick and prominent, being 22-24 on the last whorl. The axial ribs are thick and connect the nodules between carinae, forming a re-entering angle within the interspace, which is concave; this angle is ca. 150° between the subsutural carina and the peripheral, and 135° between the two peripheral carinae.

Umbilicus wide and deep, delimited by a cord of small nodules, inside with the thick axial ribs continued. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area and columella thick, not reflected; outer lip with a thickened edge.

Dimensions: One of the shells examined measures 2.50 mm in diameter, 1.24 mm in height (H/D: 0.50).

Habitat: Infralittoral, on fine sandy bottoms, intertidally and down to 20 m depth (KURODA, HABE & OYAMA, 1971); in tide pools among rocks (FUKUDA ET AL., 2000); intertidal to 20 m, in sand (HIGO ET AL., 1999); under rocks on sandy gravel bottom in the intertidal zone in sheltered area (OKUTANI, 2000); shallow water, on muddy bottoms (ROBBA ET AL., 2004); on the undersides of buried stones in embayments, and the living shell is completely covered with a dark, rusty substance (SASAKI, 2008).

Distribution: From Japan to Gulf of Thailand. Known from northeastern Honshū (Iwate prefecture) and southwards, northern Honshū to southern Kyūsū, Japan Sea (Oga peninsula); from Korea (HIGO ET AL., 1999); from Sanriku and Oga Peninsula in Japan Sea, to Kyushu (OKUTANI, 2000); from the Gulf of Thailand (ROBBA ET AL., 2004); from Japan (SASAKI, 2008).

Remarks: KURODA & HABE (1952: 50) held *P. pulchella* as a synonym of *P. micans* but later HABE (1964: 34) wrote: "This was erroneously known as *P. micans* A. Adams from Australia". *Pseudoliotia micans* is considerably thicker and less depressed, with one more spiral cord on the last whorl.

Pseudoliotia pulchella is very similar to *P. speciosa* in its general aspect, having a similar number of nodules on the peripheral carina on the last whorl, but differing in having a somewhat lower spire, a greater distance between the subsutural cord and the peripheral one and by lacking spiral cords inside the umbilicus and having curved axial folds.

After comparing the holotype of *Cyclostrema pulchellum* (SMF-313703) with the 3 syntypes of *Cyclostrema bushi* from MNHN (IM-2000-31062), and with additional material in NMW, we noted that both are similar in shape and ornamentation and conclude, in agreement with ROBBA ET AL. (2004: 55), that *Cyclostrema bushi* is a junior synonym of *Cyclostrema pulchellum*. The name *C. bushi*, which was explicitly dedicated to a woman should have been emended to *C. bushae* following ICZN Art. 31.1.2.

Pseudoliotia speciosa (Angas, 1871) (Figures 4F, 14A-G)

Liotia speciosa Angas, 1871: 19, pl. 1, fig. 26. [Type locality: Double Bay, Port Jackson, Sydney, NSW].

Pseudoliotia speciosa (Angas, 1871): TATE (1899: 223).

Pseudoliotia liliputia Laseron, 1958: 168, figs. 16-18. [Type locality: Darwin beaches, Queensland, Australia]. **New synonym.**

Pseudoliotia speciosa (Angas, 1871): IREDALE & MCMICHAEL (1962: 35).

Type material: *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871, 4 syntypes, registration number NHMUK 1877.5.12.107 and 1871.7.5.32. Locality: Port Jackson. G.F. Angas collection. Examined by photographs. Holotype

Figure 14. *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871. A-D: 4 syntypes, NHMUK 1877.5.12.107 - 1871.7.5.32, Port Jackson. G.F. Angas collection. E-G: shell, NMW.1955.158.26790, Port Jackson, Sydney, NSW. *Figura 14.* *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871. A-D: 4 *sin tipos*, NHMUK 1877.5.12.107 - 1871.7.5.32, Port Jackson. *colección G.F. Angas.* E-G: *concha*, NMW.1955.158.26790, Port Jackson, Sydney, NSW.

of *Pseudoliotia liliputia* Laseron, 1958. AMS, registration number: C.102618. Locality: Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia (12°28'S-130°50'E), 1942. Examined by photographs.

Other material examined: 1 s, from a lot of 15 s (NMW.1955.158.26790) from type locality. Examined by photographs.

Description, based on the syntypes of Liotia speciosa Angas, 1871: Shell very small (<2.50 mm), rather solid, formed by more than 4 ¼ whorls, turbiniform with a low spire, wider than high (H/D: 0.58), widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2 whorls and is totally smooth. The teleoconch has 2 ¼ whorls. The first whorl is angled by a nodulose carina. The last whorl has 5 thick nodulose carinae (1 subsutural, 2 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical). The nodules of the peripheral carinae are very thick and prominent, being 22 on the last whorl. The axial ribs are thick and connect the nodules between

carinae, forming a re-entering angle within the interspace; this angle is ca. 135° between the subsutural carina and the peripheral, and also between the two peripheral carinae.

Umbilicus wide and deep, delimited by a cord bearing smaller nodules, inside there are 2 thick spiral cords crossed by thick axial ribs. Aperture circular, very prosocline; parietal area and columella thick, not reflected; outer lip thickened externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions of the figured shell: 2.37 mm in diameter x 1.37 mm in height. (H/D: 0.58)

Habitat: In seagrass meadows and on substrates such as the underside of rocks and debris in sheltered bays and estuaries, in the lower littoral and shallow sub-littoral zones. Common. "Under stones at a very low tide (Brazil)" in ANGAS (1871).

Distribution: Australia: Known from Darwin (Northern Territory), Gulf of Carpentaria, and throughout Queensland southwards to Ulladulla (New South Wales). Double Bay, Port Jackson, Sydney, NSW (*Pseudoliotia speciosa* Angas, 1871); Darwin, Queensland (*P. liliputia* Laseron, 1958); Lower E coast and New South Wales (IREDALE & MCMICHEL, 1962).

Remarks: TATE (1899: 223), after examining authenticated specimens of *Liotia speciosa* from the Australian Museum, considered *L. speciosa* as certainly congeneric with *C. micans*.

LASERON (1958: 168) remarked some similarity, in form and sculpture, of *P.*

liliputia with *P. gowllandi*, but the latter differs not only in size but in the number and disposition of the spiral keels, the two peripheral keels giving it a distinctive profile in lateral view. Curiously he did not make any comment on its similarity with *P. speciosa*. Currently, in the Atlas of Living Australia, *P. liliputia* is treated as a synonym of *P. speciosa*. After the examination of the types of both species we agree that they are conspecific.

Pseudoliotia speciosa is also very similar to *P. pulchella* in its general appearance, even having the same number of nodules in the peripheral carina on the last whorl, but differs by having a higher spire, in having equidistant carinae (peripheral carina more distant from the subsutural one in *P. pulchella*), forming angles of ca. 135° on the profile; finally, in having 2-3 spiral cords and straight axial folds inside the umbilicus (strong axial ribs in *P. pulchella*).

Pseudoliotia caelata (Garrett, 1873) n. comb. (Figures 5A, 15 A-E)

Vitrinella caelata Garrett, 1873: 214, pl. 2, fig. 16. [Type locality: Viti Islands (now Fiji) (Coll. Garrett)].

Type material: Syntype of *Vitrinella caelata* Garrett, 1873. In ANSP registration number: 20599. Locality: Viti Islands (now Fiji). Examined by photograph.

Material examined: Only the type material.

Description, based on the syntype of Vitrinella caelata: Shell small (<3.00 mm), solid, formed by 4 whorls, turbiniform with a relatively elevated spire, a little wider than high, carinate and narrowly umbilicate.

The protoconch may have about 1 whorl but it is very eroded on the type specimen. The teleoconch has 2 ¼ whorls, adapically carinate and basally very convex. The first whorl is angled by a carina with small nodules. The last whorl is bicarinate (one subsutural carina and another one peripheral) which angle the shell and present medium-sized, axially elongate nodules at the intersections with the axial ribs, which are about 30-33 on the last whorl. The axial ribs are thin and connect the nodules between subsutural and the

peripheral carinae, forming a re-entering angle of ca. 160° within the interspace. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by fine spiral cordlets.

Umbilicus narrow and deep, delimited by the axial ribs which form an angle before penetrating inside, where there are also spiral cordlets. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area and columella thick, not reflected; outer lip thickened by a narrow rim, with cords and nodules being attenuated.

Dimensions: The syntype is 2.0 mm in diameter, 1.0 in height (H/D: 0.50).

Habitat: Unknown, type material beached.

Distribution: Only known from Fiji (GARRETT, 1873).

Remarks: GARRETT (1873) wrote that besides being pretty, it was a rare species,

Figure 15. A-E: *Pseudoliotia caelata* (Garrett, 1873), syntype (ANSP 20559) and protoconch, Viti Islands. F-H: *Pseudoliotia gowllandi* (Brazier, 1874). F: original figures. G-H: syntypes, 2.4 and 2.4 mm in diameter; registration number NHMUK 1875.5.28.2. Locality: Percy Island, N.E. Australia. Presented by J. Brazier Esq. (specimens glued to a card).

Figura 15. A-E: *Pseudoliotia caelata* (Garrett, 1873), sintipos (ANSP 20559) y protoconcha, Islas Viti. F-H: *Pseudoliotia gowllandi* (Brazier, 1874). F: figuras originales. G-H: sintipos, 2,4 y 2,4 mm de diámetro; número de registro NHMUK 1875.5.28.2. Localidad: Isla de Percy, N.E. Australia. Presentado por J. Brazier Esq. (ejemplares pegados a una tarjeta).

of which only 4 specimens had been found in the sand of a beach at Kiva Island.

The species is well characterized and the differences with other congeneric species are its high spire, the low number of carinae, the more numerous and narrow axial ribs, the smaller size of the nodules at the intersections, and the narrow and deep umbilicus.

GARRETT (1873) also described *Vitrinella liricincta* and *Vitrinella sculptilis*, the

latter included in the genus *Circulus* by PONDER (1994), considering that it had the same characteristic features as *Circulus mortoni* Ponder, 1994. Currently *V. sculptilis* is considered synonym of *Circulus marchei* (Jousseaume, 1872) from Poulo Pinang (Pulau Pinang), Malaysian Peninsula (described in JOUSSEAUME, 1872: 392). After examining the holotype of *Vitrinella liricincta*, we agree that it also belongs to the genus *Circulus*.

Pseudoliotia gowllandi (Brazier, 1874) (Figures 5B, 15F-H)

Liotia gowllandi Brazier, 1874: 672, pl. 83, figs. 1, 2. [Type locality: Percy Island, north-east coast of Australia]. According to DUNCAN (1937), this part of *Proceedings* was effectively published in 1874. *Pseudoliotia gowllandi* (Brazier, 1874): LASERON (1958): 178, figs. 7-9.

Type material: Syntypes (2) of *Liotia gowllandi* Brazier, 1874 (Figure 15G-H). In NHMUK 1875.5.28.2. Locality: Percy Island, NE Australia. Examined by photograph. Other syntype of *Liotia gowllandi* Brazier, 1874 in Australian Museum, registration number: C.11503. Locality: Percy Islands, Middle (No. 2) Island (21°39'S-150°14.30'E), Queensland, Australia. Not examined.

Material examined: Only the type material.

Description, based on the syntypes in NHMUK: Shell small (< 3.00 mm), solid, formed by 4 ¼ whorls, white, turbiniform with a low spire, wider than high, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch appears rather eroded on the material examined and it is not easy to see its termination and to measure its diameter. It may have somewhat more than one whorl and seems completely smooth at first sight, but has a first phase smooth and a second with tubercles aligned spirally in about 4 rows and irregular oblique lines near the suture. The teleoconch has 2 ¾ whorls. The first whorl is angled by a carina with small nodules. The last whorl is tricarinate (1 subsutural, 1 peripheral and 1 basal); these carinae angle the shell and present large nodules at the intersections with the axial ribs, which are 25-28 on the last whorl. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by fine spiral cordlets, more conspicuous in the spaces between the carinae.

Umbilicus broad and deep, delimited by an angle in the axial ribs which are continued inside; spiral cords are not observed in the umbilicus. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area and columella thick, not reflected; outer lip thickened by a narrow rim, with cords and nodules being attenuated.

Dimensions: The syntype photographed is 2.4 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Found under stones (coll. Brazier) (LASERON, 1958).

Distribution: Australia: Northern Territory and NE coast, Queensland (LASERON, 1958). Papua New Guinea: Port Moresby and Milne Bay (Collector:

Hedley, C. (1890); AM - Malacology C.8588, C8604).

Remarks: BRAZIER (1874), when describing *Liotia gowllandi*, remarked its similarity with *Liotia speciosa* from Port Jackson. TATE (1899: 223) considered *L. gowllandi* as a variety of the South Australian *P. micans* which also ranges into New South Wales, and with which he had synonymized the Peronian *P. speciosa*.

Later, *P. speciosa* was restored as valid by Hedley for the second Peronian species, but the name *P. micans* was generally used for specimens from Queensland e.g. HEDLEY (1909).

LASERON (1958: 167) noted the considerable confusion regarding the identity of this species, and also the difference between the type in NHMUK and the published figures of BRAZIER (1874), which show the axial ribs rather more numerous, and do not show the lateral profile of *P. gowllandi*. Laseron stated as differential features of the species "apart from the form and size, the vitreous and shining texture, the absence of fine spiral threads on or between the axial ribs, and the swelling of the axial ribs where they cross the spiral keels. Of the latter two are present on the upper surface of the whorls and three are visible on the base. We have verified that the comment from LASERON (1958) regarding "the absence of fine spiral threads on or between the axial ribs" in *P. gowllandi* is not correct. We have seen that all the teleoconch of this species appears covered by very fine spiral threads on or between the axial ribs (Fig. 15A).

The species is characterized by the number and distribution of the spiral carinae, the number of nodules and the size and depth of the umbilicus as well

as the lack of spiral cordlets inside it. indeed quite different from the photog-
Anyway, the original figure seems raphed syntypes.

Pseudoliotia godeti (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907) n. comb. (Figures 5C, 16A-L)

Cyclostrema godeti Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907: 206-207, pl. VII. figs. 8, 9, 10. [Type locality: Ben-Son Beach, Annam, Vietnam].

Type material: 5 syntypes, MNHN-IM-2000-31163 (examined by photography).

Other material examined: (75 s): *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907. National Museum Wales, MNW.1955.158 Coll. Melvill-Tomlin, registration number PR55883. Locality: Do-Son, Tonkin: 74 s, *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907. National Museum Wales, NMW.1955.158 Coll. Melvill-Tomlin, registration number PR55884.

Description, based on the syntypes in MNHN and material in NMW.PR.55884: Shell small (<4.5 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls, turbiniform with a relatively high spire, wider than high (H/D: 0.67), carinate.

The protoconch has a little less than 2 whorls, measures about 280 μ m, being completely smooth. The teleoconch has 3 whorls, adapically and basally angled. The first whorl is angled by a nodose carina. Last whorl with 5 thick nodose carinae (1 subsutural, 2 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical). The axial ribs are thick and connect the nodules between carinae, forming a re-entering angle within the interspace; this angle is ca. 135° between the subsutural carina and the peripheral carinae. The nodules on the carinae, with the exception of the periumbilical one, are very thick and prominent, counting 20-22 in the last whorl. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by fine spiral cordlets, more apparent in the spaces between the carinae. At intervals of 8-10 cordlets, there are evenly spaced, thicker compound cordlets (Fig. 16L).

Umbilicus relatively wide and deep, delimited by a cord with small nodules, inside with thick axial ribs and spiral

cordlets. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area and columella thick; outer lip thickened, externally indented by the termination of the cords, internally bordered by a narrow rim.

Dimensions: One of the shells examined is 2.16 mm in diameter, 1.44 in height (H/D: 0.66).

Habitat: Unknown, type material beached.

Distribution: Only known from type locality.

Remarks: DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1907) wrote that the new species was characterized by its prominent ornamentation; because the tubercles formed at the intersections of the axial ribs with the peripheral cord give the contour of the shell a regularly wavy appearance.

Pseudoliotia micans is similar in the general shape and the thickness of the shell, but the spiral cords are stronger, separate and more prominent, the ribs are less numerous and the lower one is close to the umbilicus.

Pseudoliotia godeti may be differentiated from *Pseudoliotia bushae* (= *P. pulchella*) because the latter has a wider protoconch with fewer whorls, and a coarser microsculpture.

Pseudoliotia axialis Laseron, 1958 (Figures 5D, 17A-B)

Pseudoliotia axialis Laseron, 1958: 168, figs. 13-15. [Type locality: Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia].

Type material: Holotype of *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958 in AMS, registration number C.102619. Locality: Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia (12°28'S-130°50'E). Examined by photographs.

Material examined: Only the type material.

Description, based on the holotype: Shell small (<3.0 mm), solid, formed by 4.1 whorls, turbiniform, somewhat depressed, narrowly umbilicate.

The protoconch has a little more than 2 whorls, completely smooth. The teleoconch has 2 whorls, rounded, with a narrow concave area adjacent to the sutures, delimited by a thick spiral carina. Sculpture formed by spiral cords, axial ribs and spiral threads. The axial ribs are strong, oblique and rounded, and they are separated by deep channels; they start next to the suture, crossing the concave space between the suture and forming thick nodules over the carina, then extend towards the base, thickening in the peripheral area, to terminate abruptly on the edge of the umbilicus. All spaces between the axial ribs are crossed by fine spiral threads of similar size and regularly distributed.

Umbilicus narrow and deep, the axial ribs prolonged within it by narrow riblets which rapidly fades out. Aperture rounded, very prosocline, with a continuous peristome; outer lip thick, internally bordered by a prominent rim.

The holotype size 2.5 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Unknown.

Distribution: Australia: Darwin in Northern Territory; Moreton Bay, Port Curtis, Keppel Bay, Hervey Bay, Starcke River, Torres Strait and Great Sandy Strait in Queensland.

Remarks: Examining the holotype we have seen the existence of regularly distributed spiral threads of similar size, which are occupying the interspaces between the axial ribs, but without crossing them. The umbilicus is very small and deep, not delimited by any spiral cord, and inside only shows the extension of the axial ribs.

LASERON (1958) wrote: "This is the deepest of all the species, and is easily recognized by the strong, smooth axial ribs, and the presence of only one spiral keel".

In our opinion, this species is characterized by the rounded subsutural spiral keel, the thick and winding axial ribs, with spiral threads in the interspaces, the rounded and deep umbilicus with the axial ribs extending into its interior, and the very oblique aperture with a narrow secondary apertural edge within.

Pseudoliotia radians (Laseron, 1958) n. comb. (Figures 5E, 17C-D)

Discreliotia radians Laseron, 1958: 169, figs. 19-21. [Type locality: off Point Charles, Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia, in 15-20 fathoms [27-36 m].

Type material: Holotype in AMS, Registration number: C.102623. Paratypes of *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958. Australian Museum, Registration number: C.163404, from the type locality. Not examined. Holotype of *Discreliotia serrata* Laseron, 1958. Australian Museum, Registration number: C.102622. same type locality as *D. radians*. Not examined.

Material examined: Only of the type material.

Description, based on the holotype: Shell small (<4.0 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls, turbiniform, somewhat depressed, very narrowly umbilicate.

The protoconch has a little more than 2 whorls, completely smooth. The teleoconch has 3 whorls, descending in sharp steps, the earlier whorls flattened above with vertical sides. Sculpture formed by spiral carinae, spiral threads and axial ribs.

Upper surface flattened next to the sutures, thence with a sharp spiral carina, below which the surface descends in a

concave curve to a narrow platform above a sharp peripheral carina; faint spiral threads fill this space. The axial ribs are strong, oblique and rounded, as wide as their interspaces; they are extending from the edge of the peripheral carina to the edge of the umbilicus; there are 10-11 wide axial ribs which disappear in the last quarter whorl, to become replaced by an additional sharp, spiral carina, as prominent as the peripheral carina.

Umbilicus nearly closed, partially occluded by a small callous parietal

Figure 16. A-E: *Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, syntypes, MNHN-IM-2000-31163. Ben-Son beach, Vietnam. F-I: shells, 2.05 mm, 2.06, 2.13, 2.34 mm, all MNW.1955.158, Coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55883. Do-Son beach, Vietnam. J: protoconch. K-L: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 16. A-E: Cyclostrema godeti* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, sintipos, MNHN-IM-2000-31163. Playa de Ben-Son, Vietnam. F-I: conchas, 2,05 mm, 2,06, 2,13, 2,34 mm, todas en MNW.1955.158, Coll. Melvill-Tomlin - PR55883. Playa de Do-Son, Vietnam. J: protoconcha. K-L: microescultura y detalle.

extension. Aperture rounded, very prosocline, with a continuous peristome; outer lip thick, bordered internally by a distinct rim.

The holotype measures 3.5 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Infralittoral, collected from dredgings at 27-36 m depth.

Figure 17. A-B: *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958. holotype, 2.5 mm, AMS C.102619. Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia (12°28'S-130°50'E). C-D: *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958, holotype, 3.5 mm, AMS C.102623. E-F: *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958, holotype, 3.0 mm, 32 km off Point Charles Darwin, 12°10'S-130°22'E, AMS C.102620.

Figura 17. A-B: *Pseudoliotia axialis* Laseron, 1958. holotipo, 2,5 mm, AMS C.102619. Darwin, Northern Territory, Australia (12°28'S-130°50'E). C-D: *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958, holotipo, 3,5 mm, AMS C.102623. E-F: *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958, holotipo, 3,0 mm, 32 km frente a Point Charles Darwin, 12°10'S-130°22'E, AMS C.102620.

Distribution: Australia: Northern Territory, 32 km off Point Charles, Darwin (LASERON, 1958).

Remarks: LASERON (1958) already indicated that *Discreliotia radians* and *D.*

serrata were very similar species in its form and aperture, nearly identical. Currently, in the Atlas of Living Australia, *D. serrata* is treated as a synonym of *D. radians*.

Pseudoliotia tropica Laseron, 1958 (Figures 5F, 17E-F)

Pseudoliotia tropica Laseron, 1958: 168, figs. 10-12. [Type locality: 32 km off Point Charles, Darwin].

Type material: Holotype in AMS, registration number: C.102620. Locality: Australia, Northern Territory, 32 km off Point Charles, Darwin, (12°10'S-130°22'E). Examined by photograph.

Material examined: (1 s): Only the type material.

Description, based on the holotype: Shell small (<3.5 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls separated by a deep suture, turbiniform, very depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2 whorls, completely smooth. The teleoconch has 3

whorls of rapid growth, on which there are two carinae, one adapical and other peripheral more prominent like a keel. The adapical carina is elevate, nodulose and delimiting a subsutural concave space; the peripheral carina is very prominent and angles the shell. Sculpture formed by spiral

cords, spiral threads and axial ribs. Main sculpture of sharp, oblique axial ribs, rising and thickening slightly where they cross with the upper spiral carina, below which they bend towards the peripheral keel, and from there evenly continue onto the base. The axial ribs are crossed throughout, both above and on the base, by numerous, closely packed, spiral threads, which form small nodules at the intersections with the ribs; a stronger subsutural cord is seen on the second half of the last whorl.

Umbilicus round and deep, delimited by a nodulose cord, inside with 2 cords bearing smaller nodules crossed by fine axial riblets. Aperture very prosocline, with a continuous peristome; outer lip thick, bordered internally by a distinct rim.

The holotype size 3.0 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Common in 15-20 fms at Pt. Charles, Darwin; Darwin beaches (LASERON, 1958).

Distribution: Australia: Point Charles, Darwin, Northern Territory (LASERON, 1958).

Remarks: According to LASERON (1958) the species is also common in the Torres Strait area, where it has been labelled as *gowllandi*. Compared to that species, it is consistently larger, more depressed, has a different lateral profile and fewer spiral keels. The fine spiral threads also distinguish it from that and other species, and the lack of basal and periumbilical carinae also distinguish this species from other similar ones in the Indo-Pacific area.

Pseudoliotia dispersa n. sp. (Figures 3A-G, 6A, 18A-F, 19A-G, 20A-F)

Type material: Holotype MNHN IM-2000-34125 and 9 paratypes MNHN IM-2000-34126.

Material examined: (1 spm, 35 s): Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: 10 s, Segond Channel, vicinity of Luganville, Stn. VM53, 15°31'S-167°11.9'E, intertidal, soft and hard bottom [type material]; 1 spm, Segond Channel, bridge on Matafou river, Stn. VM19, 15°22.2'S-167°11.1'E, intertidal, soft bottom. Philippines, PANGLAO 2004: 4 s, Panglao Island, Bingag-Tabalong, Stn. M10, 9°37.8'N-123°48.4'E, 0-3 m, rocky intertidal with seagrass; 2 s, Bohol Island, Maribohoc Bay, Stn. T11, 9°40.9'N-123°50.0'E, 78-95 m, sponges and muddy sand; 1 s, Panglao Island, Bingag/Tabalong, Stn. L51-60, 9°37.7'N-123°47.9/48.1'E, 62 m, muddy sand bottom with sponges. Papua New Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI: 17 s, Yomba Island, Stn. PD73, 05°14.7'S-145°47.3'E, 20-25 m; 1 s, Hargun Island, Stn. P519, 05°01.6'S-143°08.1'E, 5 m.

Type locality: Vanuatu, Segond Channel, vicinity of Luganville, Stn. VM53, 15°31'S-167°11.9'E, intertidal, soft and hard bottoms [SANTO 2006: Stn. VM53].

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the Latin verb *dispergere* which means "to disperse", alluding to its presence in several countries.

Description: Shell small (<2.5 mm), solid, formed by 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, turbinate, depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring about 310 μ m in diameter, with 2 whorls and two distinct phases, the first smooth and the second with thick tubercles, spirally aligned, in the adapical part, and with fine spiral and oblique cordlets in the abapical part (Fig. 20 D). The teleoconch has about 2 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, and is ornamented with thick carinae, spiral cordlets and axial ribs. On the last whorl four thick carinae can be seen, one sub-

sutural, two peripheral and one basal, and about 20 strong axial ribs. At the intersection of the axial folds with the carinae, thick nodules are formed. The first carina, subsutural, is less prominent, and so are its nodules; the second and third peripheral ones angle the shell and their nodules are very large; the fourth one, basal, has nodules also prominent, although smaller. The spaces between cords are concave, the ribs form between the peripheral carinae a re-entering angle of 135°. The axial ribs, when reaching the base, are angled towards the umbilicus; prior to reaching the edge of the umbilicus, the inter-

Figure 18. *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.1 mm in diameter, Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: Stn. VM53, Segond Channel, vicinity of Luganville, MNHN; B-C: paratypes, 2.1, 2.1 mm, from the type locality, MNHN; D: protoconch of the holotype; E-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 18. Pseudoliotia dispersa n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,1 mm de diámetro, Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: Stn. VM53, Segond Channel, en la vecindad de Luganville, MNHN; B-C: paratipos, 2,1, 2,1 mm, de la localidad tipo, MNHN; D: protoconcha del holotipo; E-F: microescultura y detalle.

spaces between ribs form small depressions, less pronounced where approaching the aperture. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by very fine spiral threads. Under high magnification, there appears to be, at intervals of

every 8-10 threads, a cluster of 2-3 thicker threads forming equidistant cordlets (Fig. 20F).

Umbilicus broad and deep, bordered by a distinct angle, not by a cord; in its interior the axial ribs are much thinner,

Figure 19. *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. A-C: shell, 1.66 mm, Philippines, Panglao Island, Bingag/Tabalong, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. L51-60, 62 m, MNHN; D: protoconch; E-G: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 19. Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. A-C: concha, 1,66 mm, Filipinas, Isla de Panglao, Bingag/Tabalong, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. L51-60, 62 m, MNHN; D: protoconcha; E-G: microescultura y detalle.

crossed by 9-10 fine spiral cordlets. Aperture very prosocline, rounded, with a continuous peristome; outer lip thick, internally bordered by a narrow rim.

Operculum multispiral with a central nucleus (Fig. 3E-G), formed by a wide nucleus in central position and four whorls. On its anterior face there is

Figure 20. *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. A-C: shells, 1.86, 1.8, 2.0 mm, Papua New Guinea, Yomba Island, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD73, 20-25 m, MNHN; D: protoconch of the shell fig. 17A; E-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 20. *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. A-C: conchas, 1,86, 1,8, 2,0 mm, Papua Nueva Guinea, Isla de Yomba, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD73, 20-25 m, MNHN; D: protoconcha de la concha fig. 17A; E-F: microescultura y detalle.

a microsculpture formed by spirally aligned microgranules which cover the four spiral whorls, except the nucleus.

The edge of the operculum is formed by a narrow fringe of minute, tightly set radial threads.

Radula taenioglossate (Fig. 3A-D), formula 2-1-R-1-2. Central tooth very wide; cutting edge with a main long and sharp central cusp and 3-4 smaller cusps at each side; lateral edges expanded and thickened, free from the rest of base for most of their length; base with a pair of denticles, ventral enlargement with a well developed U-like shape. Lateral tooth elongate, similar to central one, but its base lacks denticles; cutting edge rather long, with a main central cusp and 5 smaller cusps at each side. Marginal teeth long, curved; inner marginal tooth with 17-18 small cusps on the upper third of its outer edge; outer marginal tooth similar in shape and size to the inner marginal teeth, but lacking cusps.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.1 mm in diameter and 1.02 in height (H/D: 0.48).

Habitat: Intertidal, on soft and hard bottoms in Vanuatu. Infralittoral to circalittoral, collected on rocky intertidal bottom with seagrass at 3 m depth, and dredged in muddy sand bottom with sponges at 78-95 m depth, in the Philippines. Infralittoral at 20-25 m depth, in Papua New Guinea.

Distribution: Known from Vanuatu, Philippines and Papua New Guinea.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. is a polymorphic species which is widely distributed, having been collected in Vanuatu, the Philippines and Papua New Guinea. Individuals of each of these populations possess certain char-

acteristics which could be considered as interspecific differentiation.

In Vanuatu (Fig. 18), the type locality, individuals are characterized by having a smaller protoconch, a small number of depressions around the umbilicus because these disappear halfway through the last whorl; they also have a higher number of spiral cordlets inside the umbilicus.

Specimens from the Philippines (Figs. 19), Panglao and Bohol Islands, are characterized by the size and number of whorls of the protoconch, the number of axial ribs, the number of cordlets inside the umbilicus and a higher number of depressions around the umbilicus. Also, they are characterized because the peripheral carina is placed in the middle of the periphery.

Specimens from Yomba and Haguon Islands, Papua New Guinea (Fig. 20) also have a peripheral carina which angles the shell like a keel and it is situated in the middle of the periphery; they are characterized by the number of axial ribs, between 24-26 on the last whorl, by the small depressions which are formed around the umbilicus and by the number and thickness of the spiral cords and the axial ribs inside the umbilicus.

The radula of *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp. is very similar to that of *Anticlimax maranii* Rubio & Rolán, 2014 but differs in having the central cusp of the rachidean and lateral teeth longer and sharper, as well as in having a larger number of cusps to each side.

Pseudoliotia vicina n. sp. (Figures 6B, 21A-F)

Type material: Holotype MNHN IM-2000-34127.

Material examined: (2 s): Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: 1 s, Segond Channel, vicinity of Maritime College, Stn. LD30, 15°31.4'S - 167°10.0'E, 7-8 m, grey mineral sand. Solomon Island, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Stn. CP1781, 8°31'S-160°38'E, 1036-1138 m.

Type locality: Vanuatu, Segond Channel, vicinity of Maritime College, 15°31.4'S - 167°10.0'E, 7-8 m, grey mineral sand [SANTO 2006: Stn. LD30].

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin word *vicinus* which means "neighbouring" alluding to that the species was collected in two nearby archipelagos, Vanuatu and Solomon.

Description: Shell very small (<2.5 mm), solid, formed by 4 whorls, orbicular, turbiniform, depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring about 300 μ m in diameter, with almost 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls and it is rather eroded in the

holotype. The teleoconch has about $2\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, and is ornamented with thick carinae, spiral cords and axial ribs. On the last whorl, there are three thick carinae, one subsutural and two peripheral. Thick nodules are formed at the intersection of the axial ribs with the carinae. The first one, subsutural, is less prominent, and so are its nodules; the second and third, peripheral, angle the shell and their nodules are very large, being up to 19-20. The spaces between cords are concave, and between the peripheral carinae, the ribs form a re-entrant angle of 135° . Base very convex. There is no basal carina nor periumbilical cord. The axial ribs, when reaching the base, are angled towards the umbilicus; prior to reaching the edge of the umbilicus, the interspaces between ribs form small depressions, less pronounced where approaching the aperture. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by very fine spiral cordlets, more closely set adapically and further apart abapically.

Umbilicus wide and deep, bordered by a distinct angle, not bounded by any cord; inside with one prominent spiral

cord, thin axial riblets, and spiral cordlets in the interspaces. Aperture very prosocline, rounded, with a continuous peristome; outer lip thick.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.27 mm in diameter and 1.18 mm in height (H/D: 0.52).

Habitat: Infralittoral, collected on a bottom of grey mineral sand at 7-8 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Vanuatu, its type locality, and Solomon Islands.

Remarks: The species is characterized by the smaller size of the protoconch; the spiral cordlets thicker and more separated in the abapical part than in the adapical; the number of depressions in the interspaces of ribs around the umbilicus and the smaller number of spiral cordlets inside the umbilicus.

The most similar species, also present in the same geographic area is *Pseudoliotia dispersa* n. sp., but being differentiated by having only one spiral cord inside the umbilicus and by the abapical spiral cordlets being thicker and more separated.

Pseudoliotia oscostata n. sp. (Figures 2B-E, 6C, 22A-E, 23A-E, 24A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34128).

Material examined: (6 s): Papua New Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI: 1 s, Mitibog lake, Kranket Island, Stn. PM15, $05^\circ11.8'S-145^\circ49.3'E$, 0 m, small embayment with muddy mangrove and nearby coral; 1 s, S Sek Island, Stn. PD23, $05^\circ06'S-145^\circ49.2'E$, 3-7 m; 1 s, Mostrem Bay, N Midibur, Stn. PD86, $05^\circ4.3'S-145^\circ46.4'E$, 8 m; 1 s, E Nui Island, Madang Harbour, Stn. PD14, $05^\circ12'S-145^\circ48'E$, 10-15 m. 1 s, Alexishafen, Stn. PD31, $05^\circ05.3'S, 145^\circ48.1'E$, 1-6 m (holotype). Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: 1 s, N Urelapa Island, Stn. VM26, $15^\circ36.7'S-167^\circ01.8'E$, intertidal.

Type locality: Papua New Guinea, Alexishafen, $05^\circ05.3'S-145^\circ48.1'E$, 1-6 m [PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD31].

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the Latin words *os* "mouth" and *costatus* "with ribs" alluding to the sculpture of the peristome.

Description: Shell small (<3.0 mm), solid, formed by about 4 whorls, turbinate, depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring about $340\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, with $1\frac{3}{4}$ whorls; it is very eroded on the examined specimens. The teleoconch has about 3 whorls, and is ornamented with thick

carinae, spiral cordlets and axial ribs. On the last whorl four thick carinae can be seen, one subsutural, two peripheral and one basal, and there are 31 strong axial ribs. Thick nodules are formed at the intersection of the axial folds with the carinae. The first carina, subsutural, is less prominent and so are its nodules; the second and third, peripheral ones, angle the shell and their nodules are

Figure 21. *Pseudoliotia vicina* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.27 mm in diameter, Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: Stn. LD30, vicinity of Maritime College, 7-8 m, MNHN. D: protoconch; E-F: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 21.* *Pseudoliotia vicina* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 2,27 mm de diámetro, Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: Stn. LD30, en la vecindad del Maritime College, 7-8 m, MNHN. D: *protoconcha*; E-F: *microescultura y detalle*.

very large; and the fourth, basal, has the nodules also prominent, although somewhat smaller. The spaces between cords are concave, the ribs forming there a

entering angle of 150° between the peripheral carinae and of 135° between the peripheral carina and the basal one. Base convex, with a basal carina and a

Figure 22. *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp. A-C: holotype: 2.17 mm, Papua New Guinea, Alexishafen, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD31, 0 m, MNHN; D: protoconch; E: microsculpture.

Figura 22. *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp. A-C: holotipo: 2,17 mm, Papua Nueva Guinea, Alexishafen, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD31, 0 m, MNHN; D: protoconcha; E: microescultura.

periumbilical cord. The axial ribs arriving at the edge of the umbilicus are angled inwards, forming small nodules which become attenuated where approaching the aperture. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by very fine spiral threads. Sometimes are observed thin spiral cordlets equally spaced every 10-12 threads.

Umbilicus broad and deep, delimited by a cord bearing a string of small nodules, inside with axial ribs crossed by two definite spiral cords and up to 3-4 minor spiral cordlets, forming nodules at the intersections. Aperture very prosocline, rounded, with a continuous peristome; outer lip thickened, the inner edge covered with small radiating riblets.

Figure 23. *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp. A-C: shell, 1.6 mm, Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: N Urelapa Island, SANTO 2006: Stn. VM26, intertidal, MNHN; D: microsculpture; E: specimen with soft parts, Vanuatu, Segond Channel, bridge on Matafou river, Stn. VM19, intertidal, MNHN.

Figura 23. *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp. A-C: concha, 1,6 mm, Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: N Isla Urelapa, SANTO 2006: Stn. VM26, intermareal, MNHN; D: microescultura; E: ejemplar con partes blandas, Vanuatu, Segond Channel, Puente del rio Matafou, Stn. VM19, intermareal, MNHN.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.17 mm in diameter and 1.47 mm in height (H/D: 0.52).

External anatomy: The soft parts are here described based on the photographs of a living individual (Figs. 2B-E, 23E) from Vanuatu. The head has a long and narrow snout, bilobed distally and a little depressed. Long cephalic tentacles finely ciliated in their distal half are observed with an eye on a slight

basal bulge; the right cephalic tentacle is bifid, possibly teratology. There are two pallial tentacles on the right side. The anterior end of the foot is expanded into lateral projections; posteriorly the foot is rounded, no metapodial tentacle was observed. Opercular lobe simple; there are no tentacles associated with the opercular lobe.

Habitat: Infralittoral, at 0-10 m; collected in a small embayment with

Figure 24. *Pseudoliotia oscostata* n. sp. A-B: shell, 2.8 mm, Papua New Guinea, Kranket Island, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PM15, 0 m, MNHN. C: shell, 2.5 mm, E Nui Island, Madang Harbour, Stn. PD14, 10-15 m, MNHN; D: protoconch of the holotype; E-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 24. Pseudoliotia oscostata n. sp. A-B: concha, 2,8 mm, Papua Nueva Guinea, Isla de Kranket, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PM15, 0 m, MNHN. C: concha, 2,5 mm, E de la Isla de Nui, Puerto de Madang, Stn. PD14, 10-15 m, MNHN; D: protoconcha del holotipo; E-F: microescultura y detalle.

muddy mangrove and nearby coral, at 0 m and dredged between 3-15 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Papua-New Guinea and Vanuatu.

Remarks: There are some characters of this species that differ from other similar species of the same group: the radial ribs which appear on the peristome, very well

marked and constant; its size slightly larger compared to others; its large number of axial ribs (higher than in any other species of the group); the lack of small depressions around the edge of the umbilicus and the microsculpture of small and regular threads with some isolated cordlets.

The radial ribs on the peristome is the specific character which best differentiates *P. oscostata* from *P. calliglypta* as well from the other known congeneric species. Otherwise *P. calliglypta* (Fig. 6F) has a more elevated spire, the last whorl more rounded with the spiral angulation less prominent.

Reeviana Group

The species which form the Reeviana group are characterized by the presence in the teleoconch of a quadrangular-rectangular reticule as the result of the intersection of the axial ribs with the spiral cords.

The group is formed by the following species:

- Pseudoliotia reeviana* (Hinds, 1843)
- Pseudoliotia anaglypta* (A. Adams, 1863)
- Pseudoliotia calliglypta* (Melvill, 1891)

- Pseudoliotia acidalia* (Melvill & Standen, 1899)
- Pseudoliotia cristata* (Sowerby, 1900)
- Pseudoliotia henjamensis* (Melvill & Standen, 1903)
- Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp.
- Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai* n. sp.
- Pseudoliotia teresae* n. sp.
- Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp.
- Pseudoliotia salva* n. sp.
- Pseudoliotia sementis* n. sp.
- Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp.

Pseudoliotia reeviana (Hinds, 1843) (Figures 6D, 25A-G)

Delphinula reeviana Hinds, 1843: L.A. REEVE (1843: vol 1, pl. 4, figs. 17a-b). [Type locality: Straits of Malacca, 70 fms].

Delphinula reeviana Hinds, 1845: 52, pl. 16, fig. 17.

Cyclostrema reeviana, Hinds: A. ADAMS (1850: 42); G.B. SOWERBY II (1866: 250, pl. 255 fig. 9-10).

Cyclostrema reeveana (Hinds, 1843): ADAMS & ADAMS (1858: 406).

Delphinula reeviana Hinds in Reeve, 1843: SHERBORN (1930: 5449).

Liotina reeveana (A. Adams, 1850): CHUANG (1973).

Cyclostrema reeveana (Hinds) A. Adams, 1850: TREW (1984: 79).

Liotia reeveana (A. Adams, 1850): CHOU ET AL. (1994).

Pseudoliotia reeviana (Reeve, 1843 in 1843-65): HIGO ET AL. (1999: 106) [G994].

Pseudoliotia reeviana (Reeve, 1843): OKUTANI (2000: 175, pl. 87, fig. 8).

Pseudoliotia reeviana (Hinds, 1843): POPPE (2008: 508, pl. 199, fig. 5).

Cyclostrema reeveana A. Adams, 1850: TAN & WOO (2010: 26).

Type material: Supposedly in Cuming collection, NHMUK (type material not found, *per. com.* Andreia Salvador). A neotype (Figs. 25B-D) is designated (NMW.1955.158.26789) from Singapore, from the lot of 15 spms Col. Melvill-Tomlin, (NMW.1955.158.26594), registration number PR 55385 (ex collection Archer).

Other material examined: 1 spm, National Museum of Wales, Col. Melvill-Tomlin, NMW 1955.158, registration number PR 55384. Locality: Borneo.

Type locality: The original type locality was Straits of Malacca, 70 fms; the neotype (here designated) is from Singapore.

Description, based on the neotype (Figs. 25B-D): Shell of medium size (<11.00 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls, orbicular with a depressed spire, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2.1 whorls, measures about 410 μ m in diameter and is surrounded by a wide and deep channel; it is developed in two phases, the first one

is smooth, and the second has small tubercles irregularly distributed, which are concentrated in greater number close to the suture. The teleoconch has 3 whorls and its periphery is bluntly carinate. The ornamentation is formed by prominent spiral cords and strong axial ribs, forming a regular reticulate with pointed tubercles on the intersection points. In apertural view, 6 spiral cords can be seen; the first three are located close to the suture and, in the periphery, are more prominent and form carinae; the remaining three are in the base and are less prominent. Adaptically on last ½ whorl and up to the edge of the outer lip, new cords are developed, being finer and intercalated between the carinae. All the teleoconch is covered by spirally aligned microgranules.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, funnel-shaped, allowing to see the previous whorls; it is delimited by a spiral cord and inside are one spiral cord close to its outer edge, 3-4 cordlets in its innermost part and also many axial riblets. Aperture oval, prosocline; columella arched, not thickened and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip not thickened, slightly drawn outwards, externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: The neotype size is 10.6 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Infralittoral, at the depth of 17 fms (REEVE, 1843). In the original description, reported from 70 fms.

Distribution: Straits of Malacca, Indonesia (HINDS, 1843; REEVE, 1843).

Okinawa (Sashiki-cho, Shinzato); Philippines (HIGO *ET AL.*, 1999). Okinawa (Japan) and southward to Tropical West Pacific (OKUTANI, 2000).

Remarks: The type material of *Delphinula reeviana* Hinds, 1843 from the Cumings Collection at NHMUK is considered lost (Andreia Salvador, pers. comm.). We have located in Melvill-Tomlin collection housed at National Museum of Wales 15 specimens labelled as "*Cyclostrema reeveana* Hinds", from "Singapore (Strait of Malacca) ex Coll. Archer" (NMW.1955.158, lot PR55385).

Once examined and verified that these specimens match the original description and figures of the species and come from the same geographical area, we designate as neotype a 10.6 mm specimen from the lot PR55385 at NMW, with register number NMW.1955.158.26789. (Figs. 25B-D). REEVE (1843) attributed authorship to "Hinds, Proc. Zool. Soc. 1843", but Hinds' paper was not published and the (re)description of this species appeared only in HINDS (1845, p. 52), where it is stated that the names of the species is "a compliment to Mr. Lovell Reeve...". Therefore, according to ICZN article 50.1.1, authorship of *Delphinula reeviana* is Hinds, 1843, in spite of previous opinions by KEEN (1966: 266) about Reeve authorship for species attributed to Hinds by Reeve in *Conchologia Iconica* and published prior to Hinds' publication, or by PETIT (2007: 78), who propose authorship for Hinds' species first published by Reeve as "Hinds in Reeve".

Pseudoliotia anaglypta (A. Adams, 1863) (Figures 6E, 26A-D)

Cyclostrema anaglyptum, A. Adams, 1863: 73. [Type locality: Yobuko, Japan].

Cyclostrema anaglypta A. Adams, 1863: G.B. SOWERBY (1866: 252, pl. 255, figs. 28-29).

Pseudoliotia anaglypta (A. Adams, 1863): HIGO *ET AL.* (1999: 106) [G996].

Type material: Syntype of *Cyclostrema anaglyptum* A. Adams, 1863, Museum Victoria, registration number MV F31483. Locality: Japan. Examined by photograph. The shell is broken.

Material examined: None.

Description, based on the syntype (MV F31483) *Museum Victoria*: Shell small (< 4.5 mm), solid and glossy, formed by 4.5 whorls, globose, turbiniform, white, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has more than one whorl and is protruding above the teleoconch. The teleoconch has 3 ½ whorls and is ornamented with thick spiral cords (carinae) which angle the shell; the

Figure 25. *Pseudoliotia reeviana* (Hinds, 1843). A: figuration in Sowerby (1866); B-D: neotype, 10.6 mm, NMW 1955.158.26789, Singapore; E-G: shell, 10.6 mm, NMW (PR 55384), Borneo.
 Figura 25. *Pseudoliotia reeviana* (Hinds, 1843). A: figura en Sowerby (1866); B-D: neotipo, 10,6 mm, NMW 1955.158.26789, Singapur; E-G: concha, 10,6 mm, NMW (PR 55384), Borneo.

thick axial ribs form rounded nodules at the point of intersection. Its entire surface is slightly rough. In the last quarter of whorl there are 10-12 nodose cords, which are distributed between the suture and the umbilical margin. All the spaces between the carinae are concave.

Umbilicus wide and deep, bounded by a cord with thick rounded nodules; with axial folds inside. Aperture circu-

lar, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a callous layer; columella thick, arched and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: The syntype (MV F31483) is 4.10 mm in diameter.

Original description in ADAMS (1863): "*C. testa depresso-turbinata, alba, nitida, profunde et late umbilicata, spira*

elatuscula; anfractibus rotundatis, carinulis concentricis aciitis crenulatis, interstitiis lineis radiantibus late clathratis ornatis, basi carinulis confertis denticulatis instructa; umbilico magno, intus radiatim lirato; apertura orbiculari, margine crenato”.

SOWERBY (1866: 252) repeats the description and remarks of ADAMS (1863). TRYON (1888: 88) described it as: “*Turbinated, with broad, flattened umbilicus, last whorl with three spiral, beaded ribs, convex, white, solid, lip externally crenulated. Diam. 4 mm.*”

Distribution: Only known from type locality. Yobuko, Japan (A. ADAMS, 1863); Yobuko, Saga prefecture, northern Kyūshū, Japan (HIGO ET AL., 1999).

Remarks: A. ADAMS (1863) comments: “*A very beautiful, richly embossed*

shell, with the style of sculpture very much resembling that of C. reeveana, but the form is more turbinate than in that pretty species”.

The only type material available (syntype) is a fragmented shell deposited in the Victoria Museum (F31483). Both the original description (free figuration), such as description and subsequent figuration by SOWERBY (1866: 52) and TRYON (1888: 88) do not allow a correct identification of the species. In addition, TRYON (1888: 88) indicates: “*last whorl with three spiral, beaded ribs*”, claim that does not match the number of spiral cords showing the syntype. Accordingly, we consider this species a “*taxon inquirendum*” like it is currently in WoRMS.

Pseudoliotia calliglypta (Melvill, 1891) n. comb. (Figure 6F, 26E-K)

Liotia calliglypta Melvill, 1891: 410-411, pl. 2, fig. 10. [Type locality: Thursday Island, Queensland, Australia].

Type material: Holotype of *Liotia calliglypta* Melvill, 1891. Locality: Thursday Island. Status: Stated as lost in the original description. The type was not found in NHMUK (pers. inf. from Andreia Salvador). Neotype here designated (Fig. 26D-F) 1 spm, AM (C.559538, formerly C.7510b) from Torres Strait, Darnley Island, Queensland, Australia, 09°35'S-143°46'E, 46-55 m, in mud and sand.

Material examined (by photography): 1 spm (C.207847) from Cape York Peninsula, Albany Passage, Queensland, Australia, 10°45'S-142°37'E, 7-26 m, mud and sand; 2 spms from Torres Strait, Darnley Island, Queensland, Australia, 09°35'S-143°46'E, 46-55 m, sandy mud (neotype).

Description, based on the neotype: Shell small (≤ 5 mm), solid and glossy, formed by 4.75 whorls, globose, turbiniform, white, bicarinate and narrowly umbilicate.

The protoconch has almost 1 ¼ whorls, measures 340 μ m in diameter, is protruding from the teleoconch and is apparently smooth. The teleoconch has 3 ½ whorls and is ornamented with 3 thick spiral cords (carinae) which angle the shell, thick axial ribs and spiral cordlets. In apertural view, 3 thick carinae can be seen; 1 subsutural, 1 in the middle of the periphery and 1 circumscribes the umbilicus. The thick axial ribs form sharp nodules at the intersections with the carinae. In the last whorl of the teleoconch, 29-30 sinuous axial riblets and 36-37 spiral cordlets can

be observed. Between the suture and the subsutural cord there are 8 cordlets; between the subsutural cord and the peripheral one there are 8 cordlets and between the peripheral cord and the umbilicus there are 20-21 cordlets. All the spaces between axial ribs are concave. At the base, the axial ribs are angled towards the umbilicus, forming large rounded nodules at the points of inflexion; the axial ribs penetrate inside the umbilicus where a fine spiral cordlet can be seen. There are 20-22 axial riblets inside the umbilicus.

Umbilicus narrow and deep bounded by thick rounded nodules; inside there are 19-20 axial ribs. Aperture circular, prosocline; parietal area covered by a fine callous layer; columella thick, arched and slightly reflected to-

Figure 26. *Pseudoliotia anaglypta* (A. Adams, 1863); A: figuration in Sowerby, 1866, as *Cyclostrema anaglypta*; B-C: syntype, MVS F31483, Yobuko, Japan. D-J. *Pseudoliotia calliglypta* (Melville, 1891); D-F: neotype (coated), 5.0 mm, AM (Cape York Peninsula, Albany Passage, Queensland, Australia) and protoconch. G-J: shell, 5.5 mm, Torres Strait, Darnley Island, Queensland, Australia, 09°35'S-143°46'E, 46-55 m.

Figura 26. *Pseudoliotia anaglypta* (A. Adams, 1863); A: figura en Sowerby, 1866, como *Cyclostrema anaglypta*; B-C: sintipo, MVS F31483, Yobuko, Japón. E-J. *Pseudoliotia calliglypta* (Melville, 1891); D-F: neotipo (metalizado), 5,0 mm, AM (Península de Cabo York, Albany Passage, Queensland, Australia) y protoconcha. G-J: concha, 5,5 mm, Estrecho de Torres, Isla de Darnley, Queensland, Australia, 09°35'S-143°46'E, 46-55 m.

wards the umbilicus; outer lip smooth internally, externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: The neotype, AMS (C.559538) is 5.0 mm in diameter. The shell in AMS (C.7510a) is 5.5 mm diameter.

Habitat: Infralittoral to circalittoral, on sandy mud, sand and mud at 7-55 m.

Distribution: Known from Thursday Island, Cape York Peninsula and Torres Strait, Queensland, NE coast of Australia.

Remarks: After the original description of *Liotia calliglypta*, MELVILL (1891) listed the main morphological characters of the specie: "shell extremely oblique, four-whorled, with many oblique ribs crossed by one very strange

median line in the last whorl, the interstices between the longitudinal ribs being densely lirate; mouth circular, umbilicus half-covered", then commented that after having drawn the figure of this shell, it was unfortunately lost, without knowing if it could be found in the future.

At present the type was not found in NHMUK (pers. inf. from Andreia Salvador).

The shell selected as neotype (Fig. 26D-F) conforms to the original description of the species. The species has some similarity with *P. acidalia*, *P. cristata*, *P. intermixta*, *P. salva* y *P. sementis*, but differs from all them by its carinate profile and the larger number of axial ribs and spiral cordlets.

Pseudoliotia acidalia (Melvill & Standen, 1899) n. comb. (Figures 7A, 27A-C)

Microtheca acidalia Melvill & Standen, 1899: 177-178; pl. 10, figs. 10, 10a. [Type locality: Torres Strait].

Microtheca acidalia (Melvill & Standen, 1899): IREDALE (1918: 28).

Liochrysa acidula (Melvil & Standen, 1899): LASERON (1958: 166, figs. 1-3).

Type material: Specimen labelled as holotype of *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899, in NHMUK 1899.2.23.15. Locality: Torres Straits. Collected and presented by Prof. A.C. Haddon. Examined by photograph; Melvill & Standen (1899: 178) mentioned having two perfect specimens, resulting in that this may be a syntype as well. In the Manchester Museum, there is another shell labelled as syntype, registration number: EE.3665 [Haddon] (MCGHIE, 2008). Not examined.

Material examined: (2 s): Only the type material.

Description, based on the NHMUK syntype: Shell small (< 6.5 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls, globose, turbiniform, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has almost 1.1 whorls, is completely smooth and protrudes above the teleoconch. This teleoconch has 3.9 whorls and is ornamented with prominent nodulose spiral cords (like carinae), spiral cordlets and axial ribs. The nodules are very thick and pointed; the axial ribs are broad and rather diffuse, not forming a reticule; the spaces between cords are completely covered by thin spiral cordlets. On the last whorl, in apertural view, 5 thick nodulose cords can be seen; 1 subsutural, 3 in the periphery and 1 very thick at the base, which circumscribes the umbilicus.

Umbilicus wide and deep, bounded by a very thick nodulose carina; in its interior two thick spiral cords, numerous fine spiral threads and lines of growth can be seen. Aperture circular, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella very thick, arched and slightly reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip with smooth edge, unaffected by the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The NHMUK syntype is 5 mm in diameter, 3.5 mm in height. LASERON (1958) wrote that his figured specimen was 6.2 mm in diameter.

Habitat: In shell-sand (MELVILL & STANDEN, 1899); dredged at 27-36 m, Pt. Charles, Darwin (LASERON, 1958).

Distribution: Australia: Torres Strait Islands, Queensland (MELVILL &

Figure 27. *Pseudoliotia acidalia* (Melvill & Standen, 1899); A: original figuration in MELVILL & STANDEN, 1899; B-C: holotype, 5 mm in diameter, NHMUK 1899.2.23.15. Locality: Torres Straits Islands, Queensland, Australia. D-G: *Pseudoliotia cristata* (Sowerby, 1900); D: original figuration; E-G: holotype, 4 mm, in NHMUK 1900.11.10.39., Cebu Island, Philippines.

Figura 27. Pseudoliotia acidalia (Melvill & Standen, 1899); A: representación original en MELVILL & STANDEN, 1899; B-C: holotipo, 5 mm de diámetro, NHMUK 1899.2.23.15. Localidad: Islas del Estrecho de Torres, Queensland, Australia. D-G: *Pseudoliotia cristata* (Sowerby, 1900); D: representación original; E-G: holotipo, 4 mm, en NHMUK 1900.11.10.39., Isla de Cebú, Filipinas.

STANDEN, 1899); Pt. Charles, Darwin, Northern Territory (LASERON, 1958).

Remarks: A. ADAMS (1863: 264) described the genus *Microthyca* with *Isanda crenellifera* A. Adams, 1862 as the type species by monotypy. SOWERBY (1866: 254) and later authors misspelled this genus as *Microtheca*. IREDALE (1918) pointed out that “*Microthyca* stands instead of *Microtheca*. Two pages earlier A. Adams (op. cit.) proposed *Microthyca*, and this was altered to *Microtheca*, and has since commonly been so spelt; in the latter state it is invalid,

so that reversion must be made to the first spelling, otherwise a new name would be necessary” because it would then be preoccupied by the genus *Microtheca* Dejean, 1835 [Coleoptera]. *Microtheca* was considered by PILSBRY (1888) as a subgenus of *Teinostoma*; MELVILL & STANDEN (1899) also used the spelling *Microtheca* and placed it closer to *Cyclostrema* and therefore separated generically.

LASERON (1958) indicated that a remarkable feature of this species is the large basal cord encircling the umbilic-

cus. The specimen illustrated has a maximum diameter of 6.2 mm and a minimum diameter of 5 mm.

The species is characterized by:

1. the number of nodulose spiral cords in the last whorl.

2. the lack of the axial ribs.

3. the presence of very fine spirals cordlets covering all the teleoconch.

4. the thick periumbilical cord.

5. the presence of a thick spiral cord inside the umbilicus.

Pseudoliotia cristata (Sowerby, 1900) n. comb. (Figures 7B, 27D-G, 28A-G)

Cyclostrema cristata Sowerby, 1900: 128, pl. 11, figs. 9 [Type locality: Cebu Island, Philippines].

Type material: Holotype of *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900, registration number NHMUK 1900.11.10.39. Locality: Cebu, Philippines. Collection Sowerby and Fulton. Examined by photograph.

Other material examined: (1 s): *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900, in National Museum Wales, Collection Melvill-Tomlin NMW.1955.158., registration number PR 55880. Locality: Cebu, Philippines. Collection date: 01/10/1900.

Description, based on the holotype (NHMUK 1900.11.10.39) and the shell from National Museum Wales, Coll. Melvill-Tomlin NMW.1955.158, registration number PR 55880: Shell small (<5 mm), solid and glossy, globose, formed by 5 whorls, turbiniform, white, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has almost $1\frac{1}{4}$ whorls, measures 340 μm in diameter and is protruding above the teleoconch; it is completely smooth, has two distinct phases and ends in a non-sinuuous labial edge. The teleoconch has $3\frac{1}{2}$ whorls and is ornamented with thick spiral cords (carinae) which angle the shell; thick axial ribs forming rounded nodules at the intersections, and spiral cordlets intercalated between the main spiral cords. Its entire surface is slightly rough. In apertural view, 7 thick cords can be seen; 1 subsutural, 3 in the periphery and 3 at the base, of which the innermost circumscribes the umbilicus. In the first 3 whorls of the teleoconch the nodules become gradually thicker and more pointed, being much thicker and rounded in the last half whorl. Between the subsutural cord and the peripheral one there are 5 cordlets starting from the first whorl, almost disappearing in the last $1\frac{3}{4}$ whorl. In the last quarter of whorl there are 4 new cords, also nodulose, which are intercalated between the existing ones. All the spaces between the carinae are concave. At the base, the ax-

ial ribs are angled towards the umbilicus forming large rounded nodules at the point of inflexion; there are 23-24 axial ribs. Of the two basal cords, the innermost sits closer to the periumbilical one than to the outer basal cord. The three cords have rounded nodules which become thicker and prominent where approaching the outer lip.

Umbilicus wide and deep, allowing to see the previous whorls, bounded by thick rounded nodules; in its interior there are 15-16 thick axial folds. Aperture circular, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella very thick, arched and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip with smooth edge, unaffected by the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype (NHMUK 1900.11.10.39) is 4 mm in diameter and 3 mm in height (H/D: 0.75). The shell in NMW (PR 55880) is 4.77 mm diameter, 3.27 mm height (H/D: 0.69).

Habitat: Unknown.

Distribution: Known from Cebu Island, Philippines, its type locality (SOWERBY, 1900).

Remarks: SOWERBY (1900) indicated that the morphological characters that define the species are: shell of a somewhat globose form, crisply cancellated with prominent spiral keel ridges, which are almost spinously tuberculated at the points where they are crossed by the numerous radiating lirae.

Figure 28. *Pseudoliotia cristata* (G.B. Sowerby III, 1900). A-D: shell, 4.0 mm NMW.1955.158, Collection Melvill-Tomlin, registration number PR 55880. Locality: Cebu, Philippines; E: protoconch; F-G: microsculpture.

Figura 28. *Pseudoliotia cristata* (G.B. Sowerby III, 1900). A-D: concha, 4,0 mm NMW.1955.158, colección de Melvill-Tomlin, número de registro PR 55880. Localidad: Cebu, Filipinas; E: protoconcha; F-G: microescultura.

The species with which *Pseudoliotia cristata* has greater affinity are *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp. and *P. salva* n. sp.

Pseudoliotia intermixta n. sp. differs from *P. cristata* being the shell a little more depressed, the protoconch shorter

and having a separation between the periumbilical cord and those peripheral.

Pseudoliotia salva n. sp. is different because the nodules of the basal cords are all rounded rather than elongated and because the inner basal cord is located nearest the periumbilical.

Another species that has a certain affinity is *P. acidalia*, which differs by

lacking the fine spiral cordlets that cover the entire surface of the teleoconch and the thick periumbilical cord.

Pseudoliotia cristata is also similar in its form with *P. calliglypta*, from which it can be distinguished because the latter species has a larger height, a higher number of axial ribs and also of spiral cordlets.

Pseudoliotia henjamensis (Melvill & Standen, 1903) (Figures 7C, 29A-E)

Cyclostrema henjamense Melvill & Standen, 1903: 291, pl. XX, fig. 3. [Type locality: Persian Gulf, Henjam Island].

Cyclostrema henjamense Melvill & Standen, 1903: BOSCH ET AL. (1995: 38, fig. 76).

Pseudoliotia henjamense (Melvill & Standen, 1903): DEKKER & ORLIN (2000: 21).

Type material: *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903, 1 syntype, registration number NHMUK 1979254, F.W. Townsend collection. Locality: Persian Gulf, Henjam Island, 10 fms. Dredged by F.W. Townsend, 1901-1903. Examined by photographs. *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903, a figured syntype registration number NHMUK 1903.12.15.64, purchased from Sowerby and Fulton. Locality: Persian Gulf, Henjam Island, 10 fms. Dredged by F.W. Townsend, 1901-1903. Examined by photographs.

Other material examined: None.

Description, based on the examination of the syntypes in NHMUK: Shell small (<6.50 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls, orbicular, depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2 whorls, in the same plane as the first two whorls of the teleoconch. The teleoconch has 3 whorls with a carinate periphery. The ornamentation is formed by prominent spiral cords (carinae) and strong axial ribs, forming a regular reticulate with pointed tubercles at the intersections. The spaces between the carinae are slightly concave. In apertural view 7 spiral cords can be seen; the first three are more prominent and form carinae: one close to the suture and two in the periphery; the remaining four are on the base and are less prominent. Adapically on last ½ whorl and up to the edge of the outer lip, new finer cords are intercalated between the carinae; the number of cords varies from one specimen to another. All the reticulate is covered by fine axial riblets.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, funnel-shaped, allowing to see the pre-

vious whorls, delimited by a spiral cord; inside there are 7 spiral cords and many axial riblets. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; columella arched, thickened and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thickened, slightly drawn outwards, externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: Figured syntype: 6 mm in diameter x 3 mm in height (H/D: 0.5).

Habitat: In the Persian Gulf, Henjam Island, collected at 10 fathoms, amongst coarse sand and broken shells.

Distribution: Henjam Island, Persian Gulf (Melvill & Standen, 1903) and Gulf of Elat-Aqaba, Red Sea (EDELMAN-FURSTENBERG & FAERSHTEIN, 2010).

Remarks: MELVILL & STANDEN (1903) wrote that *C. henjamensis* appears on the borderland between *Cyclostrema* and *Liotia*, and that the mouth-characters were Cyclostremoid. In this species, the seven keels on the last whorl are closely longitudinally intersected by oblique riblets, these being gemmulate at the points of junction.

After the examination of the syntypes deposited in the NHMUK we

Figure 29. *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903. A: original figuration in Melvill & Standen, 1903; B-C: syntype, 7.4 mm, registration number NHMUK 1979254, F.W. Townsend collection. Locality: Persian Gulf, Henjam Island, 10 fms. Dredged by F.W. Townsend, 1901-1903. D-E: figured syntype, 6.3 mm, registration number NHMUK 1903.12.15.64, purchased of Sowerby and Fulton. Locality: Persian Gulf, Henjam Island, 10 fms. Dredged by F.W. Townsend, 1901-1903. F-K: *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp., F-H: shell, 7.38 mm in diameter. Philippines; I-J: protoconch and details; K: microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 29. *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903. A: representación original en Melvill & Standen, 1903; B-C: sintipo, 7,4 mm, número de registro NHMUK 1979254, F.W. colección Townsend. Localidad: Golfo Pérsico, Henjam Island, 10 fms. Dragado por F.W. Townsend, 1901-1903. D-E: sintipo representado, 6,3 mm, número de registro NHMUK 1903.12.15.64, comprado a Sowerby and Fulton. Localidad: Golfo Pérsico, Henjam Island, 10 fms. Dragado por F.W. Townsend, 1901-1903. F-K: *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp., F-H: concha, 7,38 mm de diámetro. Filipinas; I-J: protoconcha y detalles; K: microescultura de la teleoconcha.

have observed that *Pseudoliotia henjamense* is very similar to *P. reeviana*, but differs from this by having the aperture much more prosocline, and the less prominent tubercles at the intersection of the spiral cords with the axial ribs. We have not seen the protoconch in

detail, but apparently it lacks a suture channel. MELVILL & STANDEN (1903) do not make any comment on the matter.

The species also closely resembles *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai* n. sp., but differs from this in having fewer spiral cords.

Pseudoliotia indicta n. sp. (Figures 7D, 29F-K, 30A-E)

Pseudoliotia reeviana (Reeve, 1843): POPPE (2008: pp. 508, figs. 5 A-C).

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34129) (Fig. 30A-C).

Material examined: (2 s): Papua New Guinea: 1 s, Yomba Island, Stn. PD 74, 05°14.7'S - 145°47.4'E, 1-3 m, beach, MNHN (holotype). Philippines: 1 s, Cebu Island, Liloan, 25 m.

Type locality: Papua New Guinea, Yomba Island, Stn. PD 74, 05°14.7'S - 145°47.4'E, 1-3 m, beach.

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the Latin verb *indicare*, which means "to announce publicly", "to proclaim" which is the object of this work.

Description: Shell of moderate size (<8.00 mm), solid, formed by 5 whorls, orbicular, depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, measuring about 420 μ m in diameter, surrounded by a wide and deep channel; it develops in two phases, the first one is smooth and the second has small tubercles irregularly distributed. The teleoconch has 3 whorls and a carinate periphery. The ornamentation is formed by prominent spiral cords and strong axial ribs, intersect forming a regular reticulate with pointed tubercles at the intersections. The spaces between the carinae are concave. In apertural view, 7 spiral cords can be seen; those located close to the suture and on the periphery are more prominent and form carinae; the remaining ones are on the base and less prominent. Adapically, in the last $\frac{1}{4}$ of whorl and up to the edge of the outer lip, up to 7 new cords are developed, much finer, intercalated between the carinae. There are no microgranules on the surface of the teleoconch.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, funnel-shaped, allowing see the previous whorls; it is bounded by a spiral cord; inside, there are one spiral cord close to the bounding cord, one smaller spiral cord along the innermost part,

and many axial ribs (Fig. 30C). Aperture oval, prosocline; parietal area covered by a thin callous layer; columella arched, reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip not thickened, slightly drawn outwards, externally indented by termination of the cords, internally also slightly reflecting the external sculpture.

Dimensions: The holotype is 7.1 mm in maximum diameter and 3.8 mm in height (H/D: 0.53).

Habitat: Infralittoral at 1-3 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Yomba Island, Papua New Guinea, and in the Philippines Archipelago.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp. is characterized by the protoconch bounded by a wide channel; by having 7 carinae in the teleoconch, by lacking spirally aligned microgranules on its surface and by having spiral cords within the umbilicus, one along its inner margin and another on its outer margin.

Samples from Papua New Guinea and Philippines are very similar and at the same time, they are those most resembling the original figuration of *Delphinula reeviana* Hinds in Reeve, 1843. In both populations, the sutural channel starts in the protoconch, and the rough surface of its second phase, the number and location of the carinae of the teleoconch as well as the number of spiral cords, and the form and crenulate

Figure 30. *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp.; A-C: holotype, 7.1 mm, Yomba Island, Papua New Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD74, 1-3 m, MNHN. D: protoconch of the holotype; E: detail of the protoconch.

Figura 30. *Pseudoliotia indicta* n. sp.; A-C: holotipo, 7,1 mm, Isla de Yomba, Papua Nueva Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD74, 1-3 m, MNHN. D: protoconcha del holotipo; E: detalle de la protoconcha.

part of the aperture, are morphological characters present in the samples from both locations. Nevertheless the specimens from both locations differs from *P. reeviana* by the greatest number of carinae, for having fewer cordlets inside the umbilicus and lacking of microgranules spirally aligned.

Pseudoliotia indicta has a resemblance to *P. henjamensis*, but differs by presenting the spiral cords at different position, with wider spaces between the peripheral cords; the spaces between cords are much more concave and the nodes that are formed at the intersection points with the axial ribs are much more

prominent and pointed. The aperture is more prosocline, and can be counted in the last 1/4 of whorl between 10-14 spiral cords distributed between the suture and the umbilicus. The protoconch in *P. henjamense* is usually almost on the same level as the first whorl of the teleoconch, while in *P. indicta* the protoconch is protruding. In addition,

the geographic distance between their areas of collecting is huge, which has more importance if we consider that *P. indicta* has a protoconch with only 1 3/4 whorls, what suggests a limited dispersion area. It has not been possible to verify in the syntypes of *P. henjamensis*, the existence of the subsutural groove, or the ornamentation of the protoconch.

Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai n. sp. (Figures 7E, 31A-G)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34130).

Material examined: (36 s): New Caledonia, LAGON: 1 s, Secteur Ouen - Baie du Prony, between Mont doré and Ouen Island, Stn. DW111, 22°24.30'S-166°47.70'E, 25 m, sable grossier; 1 s, Secteur Ouen - Baie du Prony, Stn. 234bis, 22°32.40'S-166°51.00'E, 60 m, sable grossier; 1 s, Lagon Nord, Stn. DW506, 19°20.60'S-163°32.40'E, 56 m; 3 s, Secteur de Koumac, Baie Chesselou, Stn. DW905, 20°59.30'S-164°36.90'E, 56-57 m; 1 s, Secteur de Koumac, Baie Chesselou, Stn. DW911, 20°56.80'S-164°34.80'E, 13-19 m; 1 s, Secteur de Poum, Abords Baie de Neouè, Stn. DW969, 20°24.00'S-164°03.20'E, 23 m; 1 s, Secteur de Poum, Abords Passe de la Gazelle, Stn. DW973, 20°23.70'S-163°59.70'E, 27 m; 1 s, Secteur de Poum, Abords Ile de Neba, Stn. DW1011, 20°08.20'S-163°59.10'E, 14 m; 1 s, Secteur des Belep, Stn. DW1099, 19°47.00'S-163°45.50'E, 38 m [holotype]. MONTROUZIER: 8 s, Secteur de Touho, Chenal at NE of Banc de Touho, Stn. 1260, 20°44'S-165°14'E, 49-59 m, shelly sand; 1 s, Secteur de Koumac, Chenal de la Passe de Kaoumac, Stn. 1314, 20°39.8'S-164°15.3'E, 30-63 m, shelly sand-mud; 1 s, Secteur de Koumac, Passe Deverd, Stn. 1322, 20°45.2'S-164°15.2'E, 53-71 m, sand-muddy. Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: 2 s, SE Aésé Island, Stn. AT23, 15°27'S-167°16'E, 176-210 m. MUSORSTOM 8: 1 s, Vanuatu, Stn. DW1105, 15°03'S-167°07'E, 154-179 m; 1 s, Vanuatu, Stn. DW1070, 15°37'S-167°16'E, 184-190 m. Fiji, SUVA 2: 4 s, Viti Levu, Lagon Ouest, Stn. DW62, 17°47.9'S-177°12.9'E, 32 m; 5 s, Viti Levu, Lagon Ouest, Stn. DW44, 17°51.7'S-177°13.0'E, 33 m. SUVA 4: 1 s, Viti Levu, Bega Lagon, Stn. DW26, 18°24.1'S-178°04.8'E, 42-43 m. Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Solomon, Stn. DW1767, 8°19'S-160°40'E, 98-200 m.

Type locality: New Caledonia, Secteur des Belep, 19°47.00'S-163°45.50'E, 38 m [LAGON: Stn. DW1099].

Etymology: The species is named after Gabriel Rueda, the grandson of the first author.

Description: Shell of moderate size (< 9 mm), vitreous, formed by a little more than 5 whorls separated by a deep suture; dirty white, very depressed, strongly carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 1 3/4 whorls measuring about 410 µm in diameter; it is developed in two phases, the first one, embryonic, is smooth and has 3/4 whorls and the second, larval stage, is finely wrinkled and has one whorl; the protoconch whorls are separated by a channelled suture that narrows at the start of the first whorl of the teleoconch. The teleoconch has between 3 1/4 - 3 1/2 whorls and is ornamented with carinae and spiral cords, axial ribs and spirally aligned microtubercles which cover its entire surface. In the apertural view can

be seen 3 carinae distributed between the suture and the periphery and 6-7 prominent spiral cords on the periphery and the base. In the last 1/2 whorl, additional spiral cords are intercalated and can become fully developed where they reach the aperture; between the suture and the first carina, 2-3 cords can be seen at the beginning of the last whorl; they become 6 close to the aperture. The axial costulation is thick and forms a quadrangular-rectangular reticule; the spiral cords are more prominent and pointed tubercles are formed at the intersections.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, inside with marked growth lines and fine cordlets in the part approaching the aperture (Fig. 31D). Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by

Figure 31. *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 8.87 mm, MNHN, New Caledonia, Secteur des Belep, LAGON: Stn. 1099, 38 m; D: shell, 9.0 mm, Stn. 1011; E: protoconch; F-G: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 31. Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 8,87 mm, MNHN, Nueva Caledonia, Secteur des Belep, LAGON: Stn. 1099, 38 m; D: *concha*, 9,0 mm, Stn. 1011; E: *protoconcha*; F-G: *microescultura y detalle*.

a thick callous layer; columella arched, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus but not occluding it; outer lip

without denticles on its inner side, externally indented by termination of the many spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 8.87 mm in maximum diameter and 4.37 mm in height (H/D: 0.49).

Habitat: Predominantly infralittoral and circalittoral, found in New Caledonia and Fiji at depths ranging between 14 and 60 m, in bottoms of coarse sand, sand grit, muddy shell grit and muddy sand; in Vanuatu and Solomon Islands, it has been found deeper, in 98-184 m.

Distribution: Nueva Caledonia, Fiji, Vanuatu and Solomon Islands.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia gabrielruedai* n. sp. differs from *Pseudoliotia reeviana* in lacking the sutural channel that starts in the protoconch; in having a smooth protoconch instead of ornamented with microtubercles, and in having a greater number of spiral cords in the teleoconch and a more numerous cordlets inside of its umbilicus. Under a high magnification, the very minute tubercles can be seen covering all of its surface.

Pseudoliotia teresae n. sp. (Figures 7F, 32A-G)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34131) and 12 paratypes in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34132).

Material examined: (13 s): Reunion Island: 13 s, au large de Sainte Suzanne, MD32: Stn. DC126, 20°52'S-55°38'E, 110 m.

Type locality: Reunion Island, au large de Sainte Suzanne, 20°52'S-55°38'E, 110 m [MD32: Stn. DC126].

Etymology: The species is named after Maria Teresa Pérez Jiménez, incipient malacologist and good friend of the first author.

Description: Shell small (>5.0 mm), formed by about 4 ½ whorls separated by a marked suture, very depressed with a flat spire, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 1 ¾ whorls, measuring about 430 µm in diameter, apparently smooth; it develops in two phases, the first one, embryonic, just of ½ whorl and other, larval, has almost 1 ½ whorls. The teleoconch has about 3 whorls and is ornamented with carinae and spiral cords, fine irregular axial ribs and microtubercles spirally aligned that cover its entire surface. In apertural view, 3 thick nodose carinae can be seen, one subsutural and two peripheral, and four thick spiral cords at the base. The axial ribs have an irregular shape and unequal size, joining nodules situated on the carinae, and thinning out in the spaces between carinae. Between the subsutural carina and the suture there is a finer spiral cord, and additional spiral cordlets are intercalated where this spiral cord approaches the aperture.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, allowing to see the previous whorls,

delimited by a spiral cord; inside there are one spiral cordlet terminating at the base of the columella, three finer ones in the innermost part, and many axial riblets. Aperture oval, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella arched, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip externally indented by termination of the carinae and spiral cords which give it an "scalloped" appearance.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 8.32 mm in diameter and 3.86 mm in height. H/S: 0.46.

Habitat: Dredged at 110 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Reunion, its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia teresae* n. sp. is characterized by its nodose carinae, spaces between cords and carinae markedly concave and the thin and irregular axial costulation and a spiral microsculpture formed by irregular lines. These characters are enough to distinguish it clearly from *Pseudoliotia reeviana*, *P. indicta* n. sp. and *P. gabrielruedai* n. sp., species which share major similarities.

Figure 32. *Pseudoliotia teresae* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 8.32 mm, MNHN; Reunion Island, Campaigne MD32, Stn. DC126, 110 m; D-E: protoconch and detail; F-G: microsculpture and detail.
Figura 32. *Pseudoliotia teresae* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 8,32 mm, MNHN; Isla de Reunión, Campaña MD32, Stn. DC126, 110 m; D-E: *protoconcha* y *detalle*; F-G: *microescultura* y *detalle*.

Pseudoliotia intermixta n. sp. (Figures 8A, 33A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34133).

Material examined: (1 s): Papua New Guinea, Sek Island, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD26, 05°05.9'S - 145°49.1'E, 18-22 m (MNHN): holotype.

Type locality: Papua New Guinea, Sek Island, 05°05.9'S - 145°49.1'E, 18-22 m [PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD26].

Etymology: The species is named after the Latin word *intermixtus* which means "intermingled", alluding to the mixture of the characters of the species.

Description: Shell small (< 4.4 mm), solid and glossy, formed by 4 ½ whorls, globose, turbiniform, white, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has almost 1 ¼ whorls, measures about 300 µm in diameter and is protruding above the teleoconch; it is completely smooth, has two distinct phases and ends in a sinuous labial edge. The teleoconch has of 3 ¼ whorls and is ornamented with thick spiral cords (carinae) that angle the shell; thick axial ribs which intersect with spiral cords forming sharp tubercles at the intersections, and fine spiral grooves which cover all the shell, cords and ribs included. In apertural view, 6 spiral cords (carinae) can be seen: one close to the suture, 3 on the periphery and 2 more in the base, one of which, the thickest one, circumscribes the umbilicus.

Umbilicus wide and deep, allowing to see the previous whorls; delimited by a thick carina which forms a marked angle; inside there are thick axial riblets. Aperture rounded, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella very thick, arched and reflected towards the umbilicus but without occluding it; outer lip with smooth edge, not modified by the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 4.40 mm diameter, 3.05 mm in height (H/D: 0.69).

Habitat: Infralittoral, dredged at 18-22 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from its type locality.

Remarks: The species with which *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp. has more affinity for its general form and ornamentation are *Pseudoliotia acidalia*, *P. calliglypta*, *P. anaglypta* and *P. cristata*.

Pseudoliotia intermixta n. sp. differs from *P. acidalia* by having thick axial ribs that intersect with spiral cords forming a regular reticule; by having less thick periumbilical and more uniform cords, presenting axial ribs inside the umbilicus and have a surface of the teleoconch covered by spiral grooves and not by cordlets.

From *Pseudoliotia cristata*, it is distinguished by having an uniform periumbilical cord instead of thick folds bordering the umbilicus.

From *P. calliglypta*, it is distinguished by having fewer axial ribs and fewer spiral cordlets.

From *P. anaglypta*, the separation is difficult because this species has not a complete shell as type and the description is confuse: anyway, this species has a larger number of spiral cords, which are very nodulose; the drawing of the original description shows a shell with the aperture more vertical and not oblique, and more spiral nodular cords on the base.

Pseudoliotia salva n. sp. (Figures 8B, 34A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34134).

Material examined: (1 s): Taiwan, TAIWAN 2002: 1 s, SW Coast, Stn. CP162, 22°09.6'N-120°37.9'E, 190-200 m (holotype).

Type locality: Taiwan, SW Coast, 22°09.6'N-120°37.9'E, 190-200 m [TAIWAN: Stn. CP162].

Etymology: The species name is after the Latin word *salvus* which means "in good condition" so that we could compare and differentiate this species from others similar in the group.

Figure 33. *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 4.4 mm, MNHN, Papua New Guinea, Sek Island, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD26, 18-22 m; D: protoconch of the holotype; E-F: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 33. Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 4,4 mm, MNHN, Papua Nueva Guinea, Isla de Sek, PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD26, 18-22 m; D: *protoconcha del holotipo*; E-F: *microescultura y detalle*.

Description: Shell small (< 4.2 mm), very solid, glossy, formed by a little more than 4 whorls, globose, turbiniform, white, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has almost $1 \frac{1}{4}$ whorls, measures 380 μm in diameter and is protruding above the teleoconch; it is completely smooth, has two distinct

phases and ends in a non-sinuuous labial edge. The teleoconch has a little more than 3 whorls and is ornamented with thick spiral cords (like carinae) which angle the shell, thick axial ribs which form pointed nodules at the intersections with the spiral cords, and spiral cordlets. In apertural view, 7 thick cords can be seen; 1 subsutural, 3 in the periphery and 3 at the base, of which the innermost circumscribes the umbilicus. In the first whorl of the teleoconch the subsutural cord does not have clear nodules, therefore having a more rounded profile; the nodules become gradually thicker and more pointed as they approach the outer lip. Between the subsutural cord and peripheral one the axial ribs are very concave, the subsutural cord being higher than the others. Intercalated with these main cords, there are 3 spiral cordlets at the beginning of the teleoconch and 5 cordlets on the first whorl, which just disappear in the last $1\frac{3}{4}$ whorl. In the last quarter of whorl, 4 new cords, also nodose, are intercalated between the main cords. At the base, the axial ribs are angled towards inside the umbilicus, forming elongated nodules at the points of inflexion; there are 23 axial ribs. Of the three basal cords, the median one is intercalated on the last half whorl, equidistantly between the periumbilical and the outermost one. These three cords have elongated nodules which become thick and prominent where approaching to the outer lip.

Umbilicus wide and deep, allowing to see the previous whorls; it is bounded by a thick cord bearing elongated nodules; in its interior the axial ribs are

prolonged as 15-16 thick axial folds. Aperture circular, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella very thick, arched and slightly reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip with a smooth edge, not modified by the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype is 4.20 mm in diameter, 3.05 mm in height (H/D: 0.73).

Habitat: Dredged at 190-200 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Taiwan, its type locality.

Remarks: The species with which *Pseudoliotia salva* n. sp. has more similarity in shape and general ornamentation are *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp., *Pseudoliotia calliglypta* n. sp. and *Pseudoliotia cristata* n. sp. It also has some affinity with *Pseudoliotia acidalia* n. sp. and *Pseudoliotia anaglypta* n. sp.

Pseudoliotia salva n. sp. differs from *P. intermixta* n. sp. in having the first whorl of the teleoconch rounded and not angled; in lacking microsculpture from the first $1\frac{3}{4}$ whorl; in having one more basal cord and elongated nodules bordering the umbilicus.

It differs from *P. acidalia* in having thick axial ribs which intersect with the spiral cords forming a regular reticule; in having the periumbilical cord less thick and more uniform, and in having axial ribs inside the umbilicus.

From *P. calliglypta*, it is distinguished by having fewer axial ribs and fewer spiral cordlets, and being more depressed.

Pseudoliotia cristata is different because the basal cords are equidistant and its nodules are elongated rather than rounded.

Pseudoliotia sementis n. sp. (Figures 8C, 35A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34101).

Material examined: (1 s): PAPUA NIUGINI: 1 s, Papua New Guinea, Madang, E Airport, Stn. PD02, 05°12.5'S-145°47.8'E, 3-8 m.

Type locality: Papua New Guinea, Madang, E Airport, 05°12.5'S-145°47.8'E, 3-8 m [PAPUA NIUGINI: Stn. PD02].

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin noun *sementis*, *is* which means "sowing, planting" alluding to its external morphology like a seed.

Figure 34. *Pseudoliotia salva* n. sp. A-D: holotype, 4.2 mm; Taiwan, TAIWAN 2002, CP162, 190-200 m. E-F: protoconch and detail.

Figura 34. *Pseudoliotia salva* n. sp. A-D: holotipo, 4,2 mm; Taiwan, TAIWAN 2002, CP162, 190-200 m. E-F: protoconcha y detalle.

Description: Shell very small (<2.7 mm), solid and glossy, formed by more than 4 ½ whorls, globose, turbiniform almost as high as broad with a dome-shaped spire, white, carinate and deeply umbilicate.

The protoconch has nearly 2 ¼ whorls, measuring 460 µm in diameter, is protruding above the teleoconch and is apparently smooth. The teleoconch has a spire with a little more than 2 ½

whorls and is ornamented with thick spiral cords which angle the shell, thick axial ribs which cross the spiral cords forming sharp nodules at the intersections, and fine growth lines; the spaces between the cords are rather concave. In apertural view, 8 spiral cords can be seen on the last whorl, regularly distributed between the suture and the edge of the umbilicus, as well as four finer cords inside the umbilicus. The first four cords are crossed by the thick axial ribs to form a quadrangular reticule with thick tubercles at the intersections; the following abapical four cords are smooth without tubercles or axial ribs in the interspaces, only with marked growth lines like fine cordlets.

Umbilicus moderately wide but deep, inside with 4 spiral cordlets. Aperture rounded, strongly prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; very thick columella, arched and slightly reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip externally scalloped by the termination of the spiral cords.

Pseudoliotia faceta n. sp. (Figures 2A, 8D, 36A-G)

Pseudoliotia sp.: LOZOUET & PLAZIAT (2008: 35, pl. 24, figs. 13-14 and p. 61, pl. 25, figs. 1-3).

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34102) and 15 paratypes (MNHN IM-2000-34103) in MNHN.

Material examined: (16 s): Philippines, PANGLAO 2004: 16 spms, Bohol Island, Abatan River estuary, Stn. S33, 9°43.8'N-123°52.7'E, 1-3 m, mud sand.

Type locality: Philippines, Bohol Island, Abatan River estuary, 9°43.8'N-123°52.7'E, 1-3 m, mud sand [PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S33].

Etymology: The species name is after the Latin word *facetus*, *a*, *um* which means "elegant, delicate, exquisite" alluding to its typical characters.

Description: Shell minute (< 1.5 mm), solid, formed by 3 ½ whorls, orbicular, turbiniform-depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2 ¼ whorls, measures 500 µm in diameter and is developed in 2 differentiated phases, both completely smooth; it ends in a labial sinuous margin. The teleoconch has 1 ¼ whorls and is fully carinate. Ornamentation formed by spiral carinae, axial ribs and marked growth lines. In apertural view, there are 6 carinae (1 subsutural, 3

peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical); in the last 1/4 whorl, 2 additional spiral cordlets can be seen, one between the suture and the subsutural carina, and another inside the umbilicus. The carinae are in general, almost smooth; only the subsutural and the peripheral ones presented nodules, albeit not very prominent, at the intersections with the axial ribs on the last whorl. The spaces between the carinae are very concave, being occupied by the axial ribs, which adapically are quite prominent and quite

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.68 mm in diameter, 2.57 mm height (H/D: 0.96).

Habitat: Infralittoral, dredged at 3-8 m.

Distribution: Only known from its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia sementis* n. sp. is characterized by the large number of spiral cords, by the quadrangular reticule that is formed between the adapical cords, by the crossing of the cords with the thick axial ribs forming sharp nodules on the intersection points, by having the basal cords smooth, without axial ribs in the interspaces, being observed only marked growth lines.

The species with which it has a greater similarity are *Pseudoliotia cristata* (Sowerby, 1900), *P. intermixta* n. sp. and *P. salva* n. sp., from all of which it differs by its more rounded adapical part; by the much larger protoconch; by having one or two more spiral cords on the last whorl and for lacking a periumbilical carina.

Figure 35. *Pseudoliotia sementis* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.68 mm; Madang, Papua New Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI, Stn. PD02, 3-8 m, MNHN. D: protoconch; E-F: detail.

Figura 35. *Pseudoliotia sementis* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 2,68 mm; Madang, Papua Nueva Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI, Stn. PD02, 3-8 m, MNHN. D: protoconcha; E-F: detalle.

separate from each other, and abapically are rather fine and numerous; on last whorl 18-19 nodules can be seen on the peripheral carina.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a periumbilical cord, with a convex inner wall and many axial riblets and a thick spiral cord inside. Aperture circular, prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick

callous layer; columella arched, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thickened, with sharp edge, externally indented by termination of the cords; internally crenulate in immature specimens which have not completely developed the lip; a notch is then formed in its upper corner.

Operculum circular, multispiral, chitinous with a central nucleus.

Animal: The soft parts (Figs. 2A, 36F) are here described based on the photographs of a living individual of *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp. from PANGLAO, PL255: Head with long and rounded snout bilobed distally. Long cephalic tentacles with motile cilia and stiff compound cilia on the distal ends and with the eyes in bulges at their outer bases. The mantle edge bears a pair of pallial tentacles on the right side. Ctenidium finger-shaped, protruding from pallial cavity along mantle edge. Anterior end of the foot expanded into small lateral projections; posterior end of the foot indented. Metapodial tentacle absent.

Colour: The animal is translucent. Head, snout, foot and outer pallial tentacle have opaque white flecks. Cephalic tentacles have opaque black flecks on the stem and opaque white flecks on the distal ends. Black eyes. The buccal mass is pale red.

Dimensions: The holotype is 1.45 mm in diameter and 1.0 in height (H/D: 0.69).

Habitat: Infralittoral, collected by suction in mud sand bottom at 1-3 m depth.

The subtidal domain adjacent to estuarine mangroves, in the sandy mud banks of the mid estuary, is locally dominated by micro-gastropods such as Vitrinellidae (*Pseudoliotia* sp.) (LOZOUET & PLAZIAT, 2008).

Distribution: Only known from Bohol Island, Philippines, Abatan River estuary, its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp. has some similarity with *Pseudoliotia intermixta* n. sp. and *P. salva* n. sp. from which it differs because these species have more marked prosocline axial ribs with more prominent nodules, have two cords inside the umbilicus and their protoconchs are very short.

Granulosa Group

The species which form the Granulosa group are characterized by the presence in the teleoconch of finer sculptures and spinose granules, result of the intersection of the axial ribs (convergence of 2-3 axial ribs) with the spiral cords.

The group is formed by the following species:

Pseudoliotia granulosa Kuroda & Habe, 1971

Pseudoliotia plurifunus n. sp.

Pseudoliotia fijiensis n. sp.

Pseudoliotia granulosa Kuroda & Habe, 1971 (Figures 8E, 36H-J)

Pseudoliotia granulosa Kuroda & Habe, 1971: 107, figs. 5-6. [Type locality: Sagami Bay, Central Honshū, Japan].

Type material: Holotype in National Science Museum Natural History, Tokyo (NSMT-MoR 17783) examined by photograph.

Other material examined: None.

Description, based on of the holotype: Shell of medium size (<12 mm), solid, formed by 5 ¼ whorls, orbicular, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is smooth, with about 2 whorls. The teleoconch has 3 ¼ whorls, ornamented with spiral cords and axial ribs. In apertural view, 14-16 cords of different sizes distributed between the suture and the umbilicus can be counted; 28-30 cords can be seen close to the aperture.

The spaces between cords are narrow, concave and occupied by lamellar axial ribs. These axial ribs cross the spiral cords forming small pointed spines. The peripheral cords are thicker, and their spines are more prominent; they are formed by the convergence of 2 or 3 axial ribs.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, allowing to see the previous whorls, delimited by a spiral cord and inside with three spiral cords, one external and two internal, as

Figure 36. *Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.45 mm in diameter, MNHN, Bohol Island, Abatan River stuary, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S33, 9°43.8'N-123°52.7'E, 1-3 m; B-E: paratypes, 1.5, 1.45, 1.35, 1.45 mm, same locality, MNHN; F: living animal. G: protoconch. H-J: *Pseudoliotia granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971, holotype, Sagami Bay, Japan NSMT – MoR 17783. *Figura 36. Pseudoliotia faceta* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,45 mm de diámetro, MNHN, Isla de Bohol, estuario del río Abatan, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S33, 9°43,8'N-123°52,7'E, 1-3 m; B-E: paratipos, 1,5, 1,45, 1,35, 1,45 mm, la misma localidad, MNHN; F: animal viviente. G: protoconcha. H-J: *Pseudoliotia granulosa* Kuroda & Habe, 1971, holotipo, Bahía de Sagami, Japón NSMT – MoR 17783.

well as fine axial riblets. Aperture oval, very prosocline. Parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella thick, arched and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip externally indented by ter-

mination of the cords, “scalloped” on its peripheral area.

Habitat: Sandy gravel bottom in shallow waters down to 100 m deep (OKUTANI, 2000).

Distribution: Japan: Sagami Bay, Suruga Bay (HIGO ET AL., 1999); from Sagami Bay to Kii Peninsula (OKUTANI, 2000).

Remarks: OKUTANI (2000) wrote that *P. granulosa* is similar to *Pseudoliotia reeviana* in general shape but with finer sculpture and spinose granules, and that it may be a geographical form of the preceding species.

In spite of this opinion we found many differences: *P. granulosa* is larger,

more flat, with more numerous spiral cords (28-30 against 13-15), the cords are covered by very smaller tubercles, the umbilicus is larger, the protoconch different, etc.

Pseudoliotia granulosa may be differentiated from *P. plurifunus* n. sp. and *P. fijiensis* n. sp. by the larger number of the spiral cords, by the axial ribs in form of lamellae and by the different form of the spines.

Pseudoliotia plurifunus n. sp. (Figures 8F, 37A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34104).

Material examined: (13 s, 1 juv): **New Caledonia**, LAGON: 1 s, Grand Récif Sud, Stn. 355, 82 m; 1 s, Grand Récif Sud, Stn. 357, 77 m. BATHUS 1: 1 s, Côte Est, Stn. DW689, 260-265 m; 1 s, Côte Est, Stn. DW691, 227-250 m. MUSORSTOM 4: 1 s, Stn. DW151, 200 m. TERRASSES: 1 s, Terrasses Sud-Est, Stn. DW3093, 190-200 m. **Vanuatu**, MUSORSTOM 8: 2 s, Stn. DW1105, 15°03'S-167°07'E, 154-179 m; 1 s, Stn. DW1070, 15°37'S-167°16'E, 184-190 m; 1 s, 1 juv, Stn. DW1101, 15°04'S-167°08'E, 205-210 m (Type material). **Fiji**, MUSORSTOM 10: 2 s, Bligh Water, Stn. CP1323, 143-173 m; 1 s, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1334, 251-257 m.

Type locality: Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8, Stn. DW1101, 15°04'S-167°08'E, 205-210 m.

Etymology: The species name is derived from the Latin words *plus*, *pluris* which means "more" and *funis*, which means "cord" making reference to the numerous spiral cords of the shell.

Description: Shell small (< 4.6 mm), formed by 4 ¼ whorls separated by a deep suture, orbicular, depressed and deeply umbilicate.

The protoconch has two whorls, measuring about 470 µm in maximum diameter and it is developed in two phases, the first one completely smooth and the second one with small microtubercles distributed over the entire surface. The teleoconch has more than 2 ¼ whorls, and it is ornamented with spiral cords, fine axial striae and, under high magnification, a great quantity of microtubercles spirally aligned can be seen covering the entire surface. The spiral cords are thick, of similar size, narrower than their interspaces and distributed over all the teleoconch; they form pointed nodules at the intersections with the axial ribs. In apertural view, 9 spiral cords distributed between the suture and the umbilicus can be observed; the spaces between them are concave and of similar size, except between the second and third cords where the space is much larger. On the last whorl, new cords are intercalated in

the subsutural area and with the periumbilical one, their number is increased up to 16 cords near the aperture. The axial ribs are fine and although generally they cross individually the cord, in the peripheral cords of the last whorl they are joined in pairs to form the tubercles; taking as reference the first peripheral cord, 60 axial riblets can be counted.

Umbilicus broad and deep, delimited by a spiral cord, inside with many axial ribs and thin spiral cordlets. Aperture rounded, prosocline; parietal area covered by a thin callous layer; columella arched, not thickened nor reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip externally scalloped by the termination of the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 4.6 mm in diameter and 2.4 mm in height (H/D: 0.52).

Habitat: Dredged in 77-260 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from New Caledonia, Vanuatu and Fiji.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia plurifunus* n. sp. is very similar to *P. granulosa* and *P. fijiensis* n. sp. but *P. granulosa* differs by the higher number of spiral cords on the

Figure 37. *Pseudoliotia plurifunus* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 4.6 mm in diameter, MNHN, Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8, Stn. DW1101, 205-210 m. D: protoconch; E-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 37. Pseudoliotia plurifunus n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 4,6 mm de diámetro, MNHN, Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8, Stn. DW1101, 205-210 m. D: *protoconcha*; E-F: *microescultura y detalle*.

teleoconch, by the regular distribution of the axial ribs in the interspaces and the different shape of the spines. *Pseudoliotia fijiensis* n. sp. differs by having a

less depressed spire, more numerous spiral cords covering the walls inside the umbilicus, and the outer lip thickened.

Pseudoliotia fijiensis n. sp. (Figures 9A, 38A-G)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34105) and 4 paratypes (MNHN IM-2000-34106) in MNHN.

Material examined: (9 s): Fiji, BORDAU 1: 5 s, Ride de Lau Vanua Balavu, Stn. DW1435, 17°11'S - 178°45'W, 170-183 m (type material). MUSORSTOM 10: 2 s, Bligh Water, Stn. CP1323, 17°16'S - 177°46'E, 143-173 m; 2 s, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1334, 16°51'S-178°14'E, 251-257 m.

Type locality: Fiji, BORDAU 1: Stn. DW1435, 170-183 m.

Etymology: The species is named after the islands where the species was collected.

Description: Shell medium-sized (< 7 mm), formed by about 4 ½ whorls separated by a deep suture, orbicular, very depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has almost 1 ½ whorls measuring about 460 µm in maximum diameter and it is developed in two phases, the first one completely smooth and the second with very thin, barely perceptible microtubercles distributed across its surface. The teleoconch has about 3 whorls and is ornamented with spiral cords, fine axial striae and microtubercles spirally aligned which cover the entire surface. Spiral cords are of similar size, narrower than their interspaces and distributed over all the teleoconch; at the intersections with the axial ribs, elevated tubercles are formed. In apertural view, there are 10 spiral cords which are distributed between the suture and the umbilicus, the spaces between them are concave and the cords are of similar size; close to the aperture, there are 22-23 cords. The axial ribs are fine and very numerous; on the peripheral cords of the last whorl they join by three to form tubercles; taking as reference the first peripheral cord, there are more than 100 axial riblets on the last whorl.

Umbilicus broad and deep, allowing to see the previous whorls; inside with many axial riblets and 6 fine spiral cordlets. Aperture oval, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callous layer; columella arched, thickened and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thickened, slightly drawn outwards, externally not modified by spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 7.00 mm in diameter and 2.75 mm in height (H/D: 0.39).

Habitat: Dredged in 170-251 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Fiji, its type locality.

Remarks: The main differential character of *Pseudoliotia fijiensis* n. sp. is its ornamentation; the axial ribs, very numerous, come together each three to form pointed tubercles at their intersection with the spiral cords. From *Pseudoliotia plurifunus* n. sp., it is distinguished also by having a much more depressed spire and the outer lip thickened, reflected outwards and not modified by the termination of the spiral cords.

From *P. granulosa*, it differs by its thickened lip, not having the outer lip crenulate, also because the spiral cords fully cover the inside of the umbilicus and the spines have a different shape.

Tribulationis Group

The species which make up the "Tribulationis Group" are characterized by having microtubercles in the second phase of the protoconch; pointed nodules in the subsutural and peripheral carinae, and thick rounded nodules in the basal and the periumbilical ones. By having or not, between the suture and subsutural cord, a canal crossed by axial ribs in form of lamellae.

The group is formed by the following species:

Pseudoliotia tribulationis (Hedley, 1909)

Pseudoliotia profundus n. sp.

Pseudoliotia pressa n. sp.

Pseudoliotia plusnodosa n. sp.

Pseudoliotia distincta n. sp.

Pseudoliotia seposita n. sp.

Pseudoliotia inanis n. sp.

Figure 38. *Pseudoliotia fijiensis* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 7.00 mm in diameter, Fiji, NO Alis, BORDAU I: Stn. DW1435, 170-183 m. D: protoconch; E-G: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 38. *Pseudoliotia fijiensis* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 7,00 mm de diámetro, Fidji, NO Alis, BORDAU I: Stn. DW1435, 170-183 m. D: protoconcha; E-G: microescultura y detalle.

Pseudoliotia tribulationis (Hedley, 1909) n. comb. (Figures 9B, 39A-H, 40A-G, 41A-G, 42A-G)

Liotia tribulationis Hedley, 1909: 436, pl. 39, figs. 40-42. [Type locality: Hope Islands, Queensland].
Pseudoliotia tribulationis (Hedley, 1909).

Type material: Holotype in Australian Museum, registration number (C.27209).

Material examined: (94 s): Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: 1 s, W Tutuba Island, Stn. DS96, 15°34'S-167°16'E, 114 m, silty sand slope; 4 s, Segond Channel, Coolidge wreck, Stn. FS54, 15°31.4'S-167°14.1'E, 20-31 m; 1 s, Stn. DS99 15°32'S-167°17'E, 100-105 m, cave sand holes with sand pockets; 1 s, Segond Channel, E Sarakata river mouth, Stn. LS17, 15°31.1'S-167°10.5'E, 7 m, mud and sand. Philippines, PANGLAO 2004: 1 s, Bohol Island, Manga, Stn. S21, 9°41.7'N-123°50.9'E, 4-12 m, reef slope with slit; 14 s, Bohol Island, Manga, Stn. S21, 4-12 m, reef slope with slit; 4 s, Panglao Island, Biking, Stn. S1, 9°35.3'N-123°50.5'E, 5 m, reef slope with overhangs; PANGLAO 2004: 1 s, Philippines, Panglao Island, Bingag/Tabalong, Stn. M10, 9°37.8'N -123°48.4'E, 0-3 m, rocky intertidal with seagrass; 16 s, Philippines, Bohol Island, Maribohoc Bay, Stn. T11, 9°40.9'N-123°50.0'E, 78-95 m, sponges and muddy sand. Papua New Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI: 1 s, N Siar Island, Stn. PB08, 05°11'S-145°48.4'E, 4-5 m; 5 s, Bilbil Island, Stn. PS28, 05°17.9'S-145°46.7'E, 14 m; 3 s, Bilbil Island, Stn. PB10, 05°17.9'S-145°46.7'E, 10 m, inner reef; 1 s, Rempi Area, Stn. PB20, 05°02.1'S-145°48.2'E, 32 m, outer slope; 1 s, Hargun Island, Stn. PB22, 05°01.4'S-145°48'E, 20 m, outer slope; 1 s, S Urembo Island, Stn. PB36, 05°15.9'S-145°47.1'E, 17 m, outer slope; 2 s, W Kranket Island, Stn. PD10, 05°11.7'S - 145°48.8'E, 16-28 m; 3 s, Sek Island, Stn. PD26, 05°05.9'S-145°49.1'E, 18-22 m; 1 s, W Sek Island, Stn. PD27, 05°05'S-145°48.7'E, 30-35 m; 1 s, S Yabob Island, Stn. PD66, 05°15.5'S-145°47.3'E, 2-6 m; 1 s, S Kranket Island, Stn. PS09, 05°12.3'S-145°48.8'E, 8-10 m; 1 s, S Megas Island, Stn. PS12, 05°05.3'S-145°48.6'E, 6 m; 1 s, S Sek Island, Stn. PS13, 05°05.9'S-145°49.3'E, 8 m, inner slope; 5 s, E Bonad Island, Stn. PS30, 05°08.2'S-145°49.4'E, 37 m; 3 s, S Urembo Island; Stn. PS41, 05°15.9'S-145°47.1'E, 10 m, outer slope; 1 s, S Urembo Island, Stn. PS42, 05°15.9'S-145°47.1'E, 18-27 m, outer slope; 1 s, S Urembo Island, Stn. PS44, 05°15.9'S-145°47.1'E, 11 m, outer slope; 7 s, W Yabob Island, Stn. PS45, 05°15.4'S-145°47.0'E, 6 m (type material). Red Sea: 12 s, Jordan, Aqaba, sediments from 10-15 m (MHNS).

Type locality: Hope Islands, Queensland, 5-10 fathoms. Examined by photograph.

Description, based on the holotype in AM (C.27209): Shell small (≤ 3.0 mm), solid, formed by 4 whorls, turbinate-depressed with a subsutural channel, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch protrudes from the rest of the shell, measuring between 480-520 μm , having more than $2 \frac{1}{4}$ whorls, and it is developed in two distinct phases, the first almost totally smooth and the second totally covered by microtubercles which are more concentrated close to the suture. The teleoconch has $1 \frac{3}{4}$ whorls; ornamented by nodulose carinae and cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. The spiral carinae are crossed by axial ribs forming more or less sharp nodules on the intersection points; there are as many nodules as axial ribs. In apertural view, on the last whorl, 6 carinae can be observed, of which 1 is subsutural, 3 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical; there is also a

spiral nodulose cord, which is situated between the suture and the subsutural carina and 4 spiral cords which are intercalated between the carinae, next to the outer lip. Between the suture and subsutural cord, a channel is developed which is crossed by lamellar axial ribs, forming very small nodules where abutting on the cord; in the last whorl 50 lamellae can be counted. All the carinae are nodulose; the nodules of the subsutural and peripheral carinae are small and pointed; those in the basal and periumbilical carinae are rounder and thicker. The space between the carinae is concave and is more pronounced between the peripheral ones. Axial ribs are sinuous, occupy the spaces between the carinae forming quadrangular cells; they are most evident near the carinae and at the intersections and are barely perceptible in the interspaces between the carinae; in the peripheral carina on

Figure 39. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A: holotype, original illustration. B-C: holotype, 2.85 mm, AMS (C.27209); D-F: shell, 1.77 mm in diameter, Vanuatu, Segond Channel, Coolidge wrech, SANTO 2006: Stn. FS54, 20-31 m; G: protoconch; H: microsculpture.

Figura 39. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A: holotipo, ilustración original. B-C: holotipo, 2,85 mm, AMS (C.27209); D-F: concha, 1,77 mm de diámetro, Vanuatu, Segond Channel, Coolidge wrech, SANTO 2006: Stn. FS54, 20-31 m; G: protoconcha; H: microscultura.

Figure 40. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A-C: shell, 1.72 mm in diameter, MNHN, Philippines, Bohol Island, Manga, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S21, 4-12 m, D: protoconch; E-G: sculpture and detail.

Figura 40. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A-C: concha, 1,72 mm de diámetro, MNHN, Filipinas, Isla de Bohol, Manga, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S21, 4-12 m, D: protoconcha; E-G: escultura y detalle.

Figure 41. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A: shell, 1.9 mm in diameter, MHNS; Jordan, Aqaba, in sediments at 20 m; B: shell, 2.06 mm, Hurghada, 30 m, MHNS. E: protoconch; F-G: sculpture and detail.

Figura 41. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A: concha, 1,9 mm de diámetro, MHNS; Jordania, Aqaba, en sedimentos a 20 m; B: concha, 2,06 mm, Hurghada, 30 m, MHNS. E: protoconcha; F-G: escultura y detalle.

the last whorl, 35-37 nodules can be counted. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by spirally aligned microtubercles.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a nodulose carina. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears 18 thick axial folds; no spiral cords inside. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a callus; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, forming a small internal angle with the parietal area, externally indented by the termination of the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 2.85 mm in diameter. The specimens photographed measured between 1.81 mm and 1.73 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Mainly infralittoral, also found deeper in circalittoral bottoms. In Australia, Hope Islands and off the Palm Islands, Queensland, dredged in 5-15 fathoms (HEDLEY, 1909). In Vanuatu, dredged at 7 m on mud and sand (Stn. LS17); at 20-31 m (Stn. FS54); at 100-105 m in caves and holes with sand pockets (Stn. DS99) and at 114 m on silty sand slope (Stn. DS96).

In Philippines, Bohol Island, obtained by suction at 4-12 m deep on reef slope with slit and trawled at 78-95 m, on sponges and muddy sand bottom; in Panglao Island collected at 0-3 m, in rocky intertidal with seagrass.

In Papua New Guinea infralittoral species collected at 2-37 m, both inner reef and outer slope and by vacuum cleaning, at 14 m.

Distribution: Hope Islands and off the Palm Islands, Queensland, Australia (HEDLEY, 1909) and Vanuatu; Panglao and Bohol Islands, Philippines; Aqaba, Jordan, Red Sea and Papua New Guinea.

Remarks: HEDLEY (1909) mentioned that *Liotia tribulationis* is the species nearest related to *L. venusta* Hedley, 1901 (pag.17, pl. 3), but this is much smaller, though proportionately higher and narrower, and more ornately sculptured. It is more remotely similar to *L. acidalia* Melvill & Standen, and *L. phillata* Hedley.

Pseudoliotia tribulationis is a species with a high degree of variability, which we have seen when comparing samples from different locations. Individuals from each of the study areas (Vanuatu, Philippines, Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands and Red Sea) have a few different morphological characters, which initially inclined us to consider them as different species. After assessing carefully their characters we came to the conclusion that all they were of the same very polymorphic species, with a wide distribution.

Among the studied specimens of Philippines, there are two different "morphs":

A) coincides with the basic morphotype (Fig. 40) and is mainly characterized by the greater number of lamellae on the subsutural channel and the more numerous nodules on the peripheral carina, compared to its congeners. It also differs by having a smaller protoconch, with a slightly lower number of whorls.

B) is a somewhat more rough morphotype and is characterized by having fewer nodules on the subsutural and peripheral carinae; by having thick and more rounded nodules on the basal and periumbilical carinae, touching each other, and by having fewer lamellae in the subsutural channel than those from other areas.

The shells from Aqaba, Jordan, Red Sea (Fig. 41) are characterized by a similar development of spiral and axial ornamentation, without dominance of one over the other; also both the carinae and the spiral cords, as well as the axial ribs and folds are strong and well developed, being present inside the umbilicus, with thick axial folds and 2 thick spiral cords.

The shells from Papua New Guinea, present the same morphs to those from Philippines:

A) (Stn. PS45) some are characterized by the numerous lamellae on the subsutural channel; by the presence of fine spiral cords inside the umbilicus; by having the basal carina with fewer nodules, by having fewer, thinner folds inside the umbilicus.

Figure 42. *Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A-C: shell: 2.27, 1.6, 1.9 mm, MNHN, Papua New Guinea, W Yabob Island, Stn. PS45, 6 m. D-E: protoconch and detail; F-G: sculpture and detail. *Figura 42. Pseudoliotia tribulationis* (Hedley, 1909). A-C: concha: 2,27, 1,6, 1,9 mm, MNHN, Papua Nueva Guinea, W Isla de Yabob, Stn. PS45, 6 m. D-E: protoconcha y detalle; F-G: escultura y detalle.

B) (Stn. PS45/PS28) like those from the Philippines (Fig. 40), this morphotype is characterized with respect to the

morphotype A by having a fewer lamellae in the subsutural channel and fewer nodules on the peripheral carina,

however it presents a greater number of folds inside the umbilicus.

Between the shells from the Philippines and those from Papua New Guinea, there are slight variations in the number of lamellae which occupy the

subsutural channel (higher in the shells of Papua New Guinea), as well as in the number of cords which are intercalated where approaching the outer lip and the number of cordlets in the interior of the umbilicus (higher in the shells of Papua).

Pseudoliotia profundi n. sp. (Figures 9C, 43A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34107).

Material examined: (1 s): Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Stn. CP1781, 8°31.2'S-160°37.7'E, 1036-1138 m.

Type locality: Solomon Islands, 8°31.2'S-160°37.7'E, 1036-1138 m. [SALOMON 1: Stn. CP1781].

Etymology: The specific name derives of the Latin word *profundus* which means "deep", alluding to the collecting at great depth.

Description: Shell minute to very small (≤ 2.0 mm), solid, formed by 4 whorls, turbate-depressed, with a subsutural channel, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, has $2\frac{1}{4}$ whorls and a diameter of about $430\ \mu\text{m}$; it presents two differentiated phases and the surface is totally covered by irregularly distributed microtubercles and strong growth lines. The teleoconch has $1\frac{3}{4}$ whorls; ornamented by nodulose carinae and cords, axial folds and ribs, and very numerous microtubercles. The spiral carinae are crossed by axial ribs forming more or less sharp nodules at the intersections. In apertural view, in the last whorl, 6 carinae can be observed, of which 1 is subsutural, 3 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical; there are also a spiral nodulose cord between the suture and the subsutural carina, and fine spiral cords located between the carinae, close to the outer lip. The suture is separated from the subsutural cord by a channel which is crossed by lamellar axial ribs; these lamellae reach the cord, on which they form very small nodules; in the last whorl 50 lamellae can be counted. All the carinae are nodulose; the nodules of the subsutural and peripheral carinae are thick and sharp, those of the basal and periumbilical ones are thicker and rounded; on the peripheral carina, 40 nodules can be counted on the last whorl, and 25 on the basal carina. The space between the carinae is concave and

is deeper between the peripheral ones. Axial ribs are sinuous, occupying the spaces between the carinae forming rectangular cells; they are more evident near the carinae and at the intersection points; and they are almost not perceptible in the middle part of the interspaces between carinae. The basal and the periumbilical carinae are very close, united by heavy axial ribs which connect the nodules of both. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by spirally aligned microtubercles.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a nodulose carina. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears 23 very thick axial folds which extend over the periumbilical carina; no spiral cords inside. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callus; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, externally indented by the termination of the cords, forming a strong internal angle with the parietal area.

Dimensions: The holotype size is 1.64 mm in diameter x 0.85 in height (H/D: 0.52).

Habitat: Bathyal species dredged at 1036-1138 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Solomon Islands, its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia profundi* n. sp. is characterized by the small size of its protoconch, compared to congeneric species; by having the protoconch covered by

Figure 43. *Pseudoliotia profundus* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 1.64 mm in diameter, MNHN, Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: Stn. CP1781, 1036-1138 m; D: protoconch; E-F: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 43. Pseudoliotia profundus* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 1,64 mm de diámetro, MNHN, Islas Salomón, SALOMON 1: Stn. CP1781, 1036-1138 m; D: *protoconcha*; E-F: *microescultura y detalle*.

microtubercles and distinct growth lines; by its very marked ornamentation, by having the basal and periumbilical carinae with wide and rounded nodules

united by thick axial ribs, by having as many axial folds inside the umbilicus as periumbilical nodules, and by lacking spiral cordlets inside.

Pseudoliotia pressa n. sp. (Figures 9D, 44A-G, 45A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34108).

Material examined: (2 s): Madagascar, ATIMO VATAE: 1 s, Cape Sainte Marie, South of Madagascar, Stn. BS14, 25°36.0'S-45°08.7'E, 16 m, sandy bottom (holotype); 1 s, Cape Sainte Marie, South of Madagascar, Stn. BS16, 25°34.9'S-45°07.6'E, 15 m, on conglomerate of rocks and sand.

Type locality: South of Madagascar, Cape Sainte Marie, 25°36.0'S-45°08.7'E, 16 m [ATIMO VATAE: Stn. BS14].

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the Latin verb *premo* which means "compress, constringe, oppress" alluding to the numerous axial riblets on the shell.

Description: Shell minute to very small (≤ 2.0 mm), solid, formed by 4.1 whorls, turbinately-depressed, with a sub-sutural channel, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring about 450 μm , with more than $2\frac{1}{4}$ whorls; it is developed in two distinct phases, the first one totally smooth and the second covered by microtubercles which are more concentrated closer to the suture. The teleoconch has 2 whorls, ornamented by nodular carinae and cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. The spiral carinae are crossed by axial ribs forming more or less sharp nodules at the intersections. In apertural view, on the last whorl, 6 carinae can be seen, of which 1 is subsutural, 3 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical; there are also a spiral nodulose cord, which is situated between the suture and the subsutural carina and 6 spiral cords which are placed between the carinae, close to the outer lip. The suture and the subsutural cord are separated by a channel which is crossed by lamellar axial ribs forming very small nodules where abutting on the cord; in the last whorl 65-69 lamellae can be counted. All the carinae are nodular; the nodules of the subsutural and peripheral carinae are small and pointed; those on the basal and periumbilical carinae are rounder and thicker. The space between the carinae is concave and is deeper between the peripheral ones. The axial ribs are sinuous, occupy the spaces between the carinae forming rectangular cells; they are most evident near the carinae and at the intersections and are barely perceptible in the middle part of the inter-

spaces between the carinae; in the peripheral carina on the last whorl, 48-50 nodules can be counted. The entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by spirally aligned microtubercles.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a nodulose carina. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears 35 axial folds, corresponding to the nodules on the periumbilical cord; no spiral cords inside. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a callus; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; externally indented by the termination of the spiral cords and carinae, forming a small internal angle with the parietal area; the inner edge also deflected by the termination of the peripheral carinae.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.06 mm in diameter and 1.03 mm in height (H/D: 0.5).

Habitat: Infralittoral species obtained by brushing at -16 m in sandy concretion.

Distribution: Only known from South Madagascar, Cape Sainte Marie, its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia pressa* n. sp. is characterized by having more numerous lamellae in the subsutural channel, more numerous axial folds inside the umbilicus and more numerous spiral cords on the outer lip than the remaining species of the group.

From *Pseudoliotia tribulationis*, it also differs by the greater number of axial ribs, the greater number of nodules on the peripheral carina and the rectangular shape of the cells between this peripheral carinae.

We have considered the shell from Stn. BS16 as belonging to this taxon

Figure 44. *Pseudoliotia pressa* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.06 mm in diameter, MNHN, South of Madagascar, Cape Sainte Marie, ATIMO VATAE: Stn. BS14, 16 m; D: protoconch; E-G: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 44. Pseudoliotia pressa* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 2,06 mm de diámetro, MNHN, Sur de Madagascar, Cabo Santa María, ATIMO VATAE: Stn. BS14, 16 m; D: *protoconcha*; E-G: *microescultura y detalle*.

because, even with some notable differences, we should not propose a specific separation having only one shell of

each, also taking into account the geographical proximity of the two stations and similar depth. This shell (*Pseudolio-*

Figure 45. *Pseudoliotia cf. pressa*. A-C: shell, 1.7 mm in diameter, MNHN, South of Madagascar, Cape Sainte Marie, ATIMO VATAE: Stn. BS16, 15 m; D: protoconch; E-F: sculpture and detail. *Figura 45. Pseudoliotia cf. pressa*. A-C: *concha*, 1,7 mm de diámetro, MNHN, Sur de Madagascar, Cabo Santa Maria, ATIMO VATAE: Stn. BS16, 15 m; D: *protoconcha*; E-F: *escultura y detalle*.

tia cf. pressa from Stn. BS16) (Fig. 45) differs from *Pseudoliotia pressa* (holotype) in having fewer lamellae in the

subsutural channel, fewer nodules on the peripheral carina and fewer axial folds inside the umbilicus; by having

the nodules of the basal and periumbilical carinae thicker and rounded, and by the thick and winding axial ribs forming

quadrangular cells in the interspaces between carinae, most evident in the periphery.

Pseudoliotia plusnodosa n. sp. (Figures 9E, 46A-F)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34109) and one paratype (MNHN IM-2000-34110) in MNHN. **Material examined:** (10 s): Society Islands, TARASOC: 2 s, Tahiti, Stn. DW3498, 347-460 m (Type material); 1 s, Tahiti, Stn. DW3436, 430 m; 3 s, Tahiti, Stn. DW3487, 400-440 m; 4 s, Tahiti, Stn. DW3491, 440-500 m.

Type locality: Tahiti, Society Islands, 347-460 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3498].

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the Latin words *plus* "more" and *nodosus, a, um* "nodulose" alluding to that there is one more spiral nodulose cord.

Description: Shell very small (<2.5 mm), solid, formed by 4 ¼ whorls separated by a non canaliculate suture, turbinate-depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring about 450 µm, with a little more than 2 ¼ totally smooth whorls; it ends with a clear change of sculpture. The teleoconch has about 1 ¾ whorls; ornamented by nodulose carinae and cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. Spiral cords are crossed by thick axial ribs forming pointed nodules at the intersections, most obvious adapically. In apertural view, in the last whorl, 7 carinae can be observed, of which 1 is subsutural, 4 peripheral, 1 is basal and 1 periumbilical; in the last quarter of the last whorl, 7 additional spiral cords are intercalated between the carinae and reach the edge of the outer lip. Both basal and periumbilical carinae are initially nodulose, the nodules disappearing previously to the last quarter whorl. The spaces between the carinae are concave. Axial ribs occupy the spaces between the carinae in the adapical part, being almost not perceptible on the basal part. Radially aligned microtubercles can be seen on the whole surface of the teleoconch.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a thick carina, which is nodulose at the beginning and becomes practically smooth in its final part. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears fine axial striae and a spiral cordlet close to the bounding carina. Aperture oval, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callus; columella curved, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, forming a small internal angle close to the parietal area, unaffected by the spiral cords, but expanded laterally at the termination of the peripheral carina, forming there an internal angle.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.35 mm in diameter and 1.09 mm in height (H/D: 0.46).

Habitat: Dredged between 430-440 m depth, in the upper bathyal stage.

Distribution: Only known from Tahiti, Society Islands, its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia plusnodosa* n. sp. is characterized by its completely smooth protoconch; by having a greater number of spiral carinae than their congeneric species and by the sharpened nodules which are formed at the intersection points of the axial ribs with the carinae.

Pseudoliotia distincta n. sp. (Figure 9F, 47A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34111).

Material examined: (1 s): Society Islands, TARASOC: 2 s, Tahiti, Stn. DW3498, 347-460 m (type material).

Type locality: Tahiti, Society Islands, 347-460 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3498].

Etymology: The specific name derived from the Latin word *distinctus, a, um*, which means "different, variable", alluding to the different microsculpture of irregular lines of tubercles.

Figure 46. *Pseudoliotia plusnodosa* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.35 mm, MNHN, Tahiti, Society Islands, 347-460 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3498]; D: protoconch of the holotype; E-F: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 46. Pseudoliotia plusnodosa* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 2,35 mm, MNHN, Tahiti, *Islas de la Sociedad*, 347-460 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3498]; D: *protoconcha del holotipo*; E-F: *microescultura y detalle*.

Description: Shell very small (<2.1 mm), solid, formed by 4 ¼ whorls separated by a non canaliculate suture, turbinate-depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring 560 μm, with more than 2 ½ totally smooth whorls; it ends with a clear change of

Figure 47. *Pseudoliotia distincta* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.1 mm, Tahiti, Society Islands, NO Alis campagne TARASOC, Stn. DW3498, 347-460 m (MNHN). D: protoconch; E-F: microsculpture and detail. *Figura 47. Pseudoliotia distincta* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 2,1 mm, Tahití, Islas de la Sociedad, NO Alis campaña TARASOC, Stn. DW3498, 347-460 m (MNHN). D: *protoconcha*; E-F: *microescultura y detalle*.

sculpture. The teleoconch has $1 \frac{3}{4}$ whorls, ornamented by nodulose carinae and cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. The spiral cords are crossed by axial ribs, forming small sharp nodules

at the intersections; there are as many nodules as axial ribs. In apertural view, in the last whorl, 5 carinae can be seen, of which 1 is subsutural, 2 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical. On the last $\frac{1}{2}$

whorl, an additional spiral cord, also nodulose, is intercalated between the suture and the subsutural carina, and on the last 1/4 whorl, 4 more spiral cords are intercalated between the carinae and reach the edge of the outer lip. Both basal and periumbilical carinae are initially nodulose, with the nodules disappearing previously to the last quarter whorl. The space between carinae is concave. Axial ribs occupy the spaces between carinae in the adapical part; they are not perceptible, but are still evident at the intersections on the rest of the shell; on the peripheral carina, it is possible to count 55-60 nodules and ribs on the last whorl. Radially aligned microtubercles are distributed randomly on the surface of the teleoconch.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a carina, which is nodulose at the beginning and becomes practically smooth in its final part. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears fine axial riblets. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a callus; columella curved,

thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, forming a small internal angle with the parietal area, outer lip unaffected by the spiral cords or by the peripheral carina.

Dimensions: The holotype is 1.88 mm in diameter and 1.02 mm in height (H/D: 0.55).

Habitat: Upper bathyal species dredged at 347-460 m deep.

Distribution: Only known from its type locality.

Remarks: The species is characterized by small and numerous nodules, 55-60 on the peripheral carina in the last whorl. It may be distinguished from the following species:

Pseudoliotia pressa (Figs. 44 and 45) has a very dense microsculpture of spirally aligned tubercles.

Pseudoliotia plusnodosa n. sp. (Fig. 46) has an obsolete axial sculpture and, on the base, some cords have scarcely marked nodules.

Pseudoliotia seposita n. sp. (Fig. 48) has fewer nodules on the last whorl and the axial ribs are very separate.

Pseudoliotia seposita n. sp. (Figures 10A, 48A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34112).

Material examined: (1 s): Society Islands, TARASOC: 1 s, Tahiti, Stn. DW3484, 300-650 m.

Type locality: Tahiti, Society Islands, 300-650 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3484].

Etymology: The specific name is the past participle of the Latin verb *seponere* which means "to separate" alluding to the axial cords of the last whorl more separate than in other species.

Description: Shell very small (<2.5 mm), solid, formed by a little more than 4 whorls separated by a non canaliculate suture, turbinate-depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring 610 μ m in diameter, with more than 2 1/2 totally smooth whorls; it ends with a clear change of sculpture. The teleoconch has 1 3/4 whorls; ornamented by nodulose carinae and cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. The spiral cords are crossed by axial ribs forming sharp nodules at the intersections. In apertural view, in the last whorl, 5 carinae can be observe: from which 1 is subsutural, 2 peripheral,

1 basal and 1 periumbilical. In the last 3/4 whorl, a spiral cord is intercalated between the suture and the subsutural carina, and in the last 1/4 whorl, 4 more spiral cords are intercalated between the carinae and reach the edge of the outer lip. The spaces between the carinae are concave. Axial ribs occupy the spaces between carinae on the adapical part, but they are hardly perceptible on the basal part. The axial ribs are more conspicuous on the last whorl between the cord and the subsutural carina, where they form quadrangular spaces characteristic of the species. Radially aligned and randomly distributed microtubercles are seen on the whole surface of the teleoconch.

Figure 48. *Pseudoliotia seposita* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.16 mm, Tahiti, Society Islands, 300-650 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3484] (MNHN); D-E: protoconch of the holotype and detail; F: microsculpture.

Figura 48. *Pseudoliotia seposita* n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 2,16 mm, Tahití, Islas de la Sociedad, 300-650 m [TARASOC: Stn. DW3484] (MNHN); D-E: *protoconcha del holotipo y detalle*; F: *microescultura*.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a carina. Both basal and periumbilical carinae are ini-

tially nodulose, the nodules disappearing prior to the last quarter whorl. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and

bears fine axial striae, and a spiral cordlet close to the periumbilical carina. Aperture oval, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a callus; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, form a small internal angle next to the parietal area, unaffected by the spiral cords, but drawn out by the termination of the peripheral carina, forming there an internal angle.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.16 mm in diameter and 1.14 mm in height (H/D: 0.53).

Habitat: Upper bathyal species dredged at 300-650 m deep.

Distribution: Only known from type locality.

Remarks: The present species has a wider protoconch than others of the group, the nodules on the last whorl are fewer, and the axial ribs are well marked but separate.

Pseudoliotia tribulationis has more numerous axial ribs, a subsutural line of deep cavities and the microsculpture of tubercles is very dense and aligned spirally.

Pseudoliotia pressa n. sp. has very numerous axial riblets and dense spiral lines of tubercles.

Pseudoliotia plusnodosa n. sp. has one more cord, and the nodules in the crossing of ribs and cords are pointed.

Pseudoliotia distincta n. sp. has more axial ribs very close but scarcely marked in some areas.

Pseudoliotia inanis n. sp. (Figures 10B, 49A-G, 50A-I)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34113) (Fig. 49A) and 34 paratypes (MNHN IM-2000-34114) in MNHN.

Material examined: (2 spms, 358 s): New Caledonia, MUSORSTOM 10: 35 s, Côte Est, Stn. DW654, 21°17'S-165°57'E, 237-298 m (type material); 1 spm, 10 s, Côte Est, Stn. DE700, 20°57'S-165°35'E, 160-222 m; 1 spm, 2 s, Côte Est, Stn. DE705, 21°02'S-165°38'E, 350-400 m; 1 s, Côte Est, Stn. DW706, 21°42.0'S-166°34.0'E, 247-252 m. Fiji, MUSORSTOM 10: 1 s, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1329, 17°19.3'S-177°47.4'E, 102-106 m; 79 s, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1334, 16°51.4'S-178°13.9'E, 251-257 m; 16 s, Bligh Water, Stn. CP1323, 17°16.1'S-177°46.7'E, 143-173 m; 80 s, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1333, 16°50.4'S-178°12.5'E, 200-215 m; 7 s, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1329, 17°19.3'S-177°47.4'E, 102-106 m; 26 s, South of Viti Levu, Stn. DW 1359, 17°49.7'S-178°47.8'E, 183-188 m; 15 s, South of Viti Levu, Stn. CP1363, 18°12.4'S-178°33.0'E, 144-150 m; 43 s, South of Viti Levu, Stn. CP1366, 18°12.4'S-178°33.1'E, 149-168 m; 16 s, South of Viti Levu, Stn. CP1369, 18°11.1'S-178°23.4'E, 392-433 m; 13 s, South of Viti Levu, Stn. DW1384, 18°18.5'S-178°05.8'E, 260-305 m. Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8: 10 s, Stn. DW1065, 16°16'S-167°21'E, 360-419 m. **Type locality:** New Caledonia, East Coast, 21°17'S-165°57'E, 237-298 m [MUSORSTOM 10, DW654].

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin word *inanis* which means "empty, unoccupied" making reference to the scarce sculpture of this species.

Description: Shell very small (< 2.5 mm), solid, formed by 4-4 ¼ whorls separated by a non canaliculate suture, turbinate-depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring between 550-600 µm, with more than 2 ½ whorls totally covered by microtubercles, more densely concentrated subsuturally; it ends with a change of sculpture prior to the teleoconch. The teleoconch has 1 ½ - 1 ¾ whorls, ornamented by nodulose carinae and cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. The spiral carinae are crossed

by axial ribs forming small, more or less sharp nodules at the intersections; there are as many nodules as axial ribs. In apertural view, on the last whorl, 5 carinae can be observed, of which 1 is subsutural, 2 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical. In the last ½ whorl, a spiral cord, also nodulose, is intercalated between the suture and the subsutural carina; in the last 1/4 of whorl 4 more spiral cords are intercalated between the carinae. Both basal and periumbilical carinae are initially nodulose, the nodules disappearing previously to the last half whorl. The space

Figure 49. *Pseudoliotia inanis* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.05 mm, New Caledonia, 237-298 m (MNHN); D: shell, 2.19 mm, New Caledonia; E: protoconch of the holotype; F-G; microsculpture and detail.

Figura 49. Pseudoliotia inanis n. sp. A-C: *holotipo*, 2,05 mm, *Nueva Caledonia*, 237-298 m (MNHN); D: *concha*, 2,19 mm, *Nueva Caledonia*; E: *protoconcha* del *holotipo*; F-G; *microscultura y detalle*.

between the carinae is concave. Axial ribs occupy the spaces between the carinae; they are most evident near the carinae and at the intersections and are barely perceptible in the middle part of the interspaces between the cords; on the peripheral carina, in the last whorl, can be counted 45-50 nodules and ribs. Radially aligned and randomly distributed microtubercles are seen on the whole surface of the teleoconch.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel shaped, delimited by a carina which is nodulose at the beginning and becomes practically smooth afterwards. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears fine axial ribs. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a callus; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, forming a small internal angle with the parietal area, the inner edge also deflected by the termination of the peripheral carinae.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.05 mm in diameter and 1.02 mm in height (H/D: 0.49). Having many shells we measure a lot of them and the medium dimensions were: 1.98 mm in diameter and 1.02 mm in height (H/D: 0.51).

Habitat: Dredged at 106-392 m deep.

Distribution: Known from New Caledonia, Fiji and Vanuatu.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia inanis* n. sp. is characterized by having its protoconch completely covered by microtubercles, by the nodulose cords which angle the shell like carinae, and by the axial ribs more evident near the carinae and at the intersections.

The samples from New Caledonia have a shell colour which is different from those of Fiji and Vanuatu. While the latter are vitreous, almost transparent, without additional colouring, the shells from New Caledonia are vitreous and almost transparent but creamy with one or two yellowish-brown dorsal cords.

Philtata Group

The species which make up *Philtata* group are characterized by having all the teleoconch covered by spiral cords crisscrossed by axial ribs and pointed

tubercles at the points of intersection, forming a cancellate sculpture.

The group is formed only by:

Pseudoliotia philtata (Hedley, 1900).

Pseudoliotia philtata (Hedley, 1900) n. comb. (Figures 10C, 50J-L)

Liotia philtata Hedley, 1900: 502, pl. 26, figs. 1-3. [Type locality: off Cape York, Queensland, Australia].

Type material: Holotype in Australian Museum Sydney, Malacology Collection, registration number (C. 8101). Locality: off Cape York, Queensland. Examined by photograph.

Material examined: Only the holotype by photography.

Description, based on the holotype: Shell small (≤ 5.0 mm), solid, formed by 5.1 whorls separated by an impressed suture and a subsutural channel, depressed-turbiniform, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2.1 whorls and it is apparently smooth. The teleoconch has 3 whorls, ornamented by nodulose spiral cords and axial ribs. The space between the cords is concave. The spiral

cords are crossed by axial ribs forming a reticule of quadrangular spaces with sharp nodules at the intersections. The spaces which form the reticule are totally covered by fine axial striae. In apertural view, on the last whorl, 10 spiral cords can be observed, distributed between the suture and the umbilicus; the 7 cords between the suture and the base are wider and their nodules are more prominent, and the 3 basal cords

Figure 50. *Pseudoliotia inanis* n. sp. A-B: holotype, 2.05 mm, New Caledonia (MNHN); C-D: shells, 2.09, 2.0 mm, New Caledonia, West coast, Stn. DW654 (MNHN); E-F: shells, 2.05, 1.98 mm, Fiji, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1334 (MNHN); G: shell, 1.96 mm, Fiji, Bligh Water, Stn. CP1323 (MNHN); H-I: shells, 1.83, 1.91 mm, Vanuatu, Stn. DW1065 (MNHN). J-L: *Pseudoliotia philtata* (Hedley, 1900). J: original figuration. K-L: *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900, holotype, 5.0 mm, AMS –C8101. *Figura 50. Pseudoliotia inanis* n. sp. A-B: *holotipo*, 2,05 mm, Nueva Caledonia (MNHN); C-D: *conchas*, 2,09, 2,0 mm, Nueva Caledonia, costa Oeste, Stn. DW654 (MNHN); E-F: *conchas*, 2,05, 1,98 mm, Fidji, Bligh Water, Stn. DW1334 (MNHN); G: *concha*, 1,96 mm, Fidji, Bligh Water, Stn. CP1323 (MNHN); H-I: *conchas*, 1,83, 1,91 mm, Vanuatu, Stn. DW1065 (MNHN). J-L: *Pseudoliotia philtata* (Hedley, 1900). J: *representación original*. K-L: *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900, *holotipo*, 5,0 mm, AMS –C8101.

are finer and with much smaller nodules. The suture and the first cord are separated by a channel, crossed by lamellar axial ribs, and delimited by a fine spiral cordlet.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a fine nodulose cord. The umbilical wall is slightly convex and bears 23-25 axial ribs; close to the periumbilical cord, there is another spiral cord, nodulose in its early part and less so in its final part. Aperture rounded, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a fine callous layer; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip exter-

nally indented by the termination of the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype size 5.00 mm in diameter and 3.00 mm in height (H/D: 0.60).

Habitat: Off Cape York, Queensland; one specimen, dredged by Mr. J. Brazier.

Distribution: Australia: off Cape York, Queensland (HEDLEY, 1900).

Remarks: HEDLEY (1900) wrote that *Liotia philtata* is related to *L. calliglypta* Melvill, but is of less height, wider and has a more developed spiral sculpture. The slight development of the thickened lip agrees with the latter and with *Cyclostrema cingulifera* A. Adams.

Linguifera Group

The “*Linguifera* Group” is characterized by having the spire more or less depressed, the protoconch protruding above the remainder of whorls; an ornamentation formed by thick nodules spirally aligned both on the base and adapically, by the presence of axial ribs only between basal cords and by a thick cord inside the umbilicus, which forms a projection where abutting on the beginning of the columella.

The group is formed by the following species:

Pseudoliotia linguifera (Thiele, 1925)

Pseudoliotia rudispiralis n. sp.

Pseudoliotia minor n. sp.

Pseudoliotia coronata n. sp.

Pseudoliotia nodosa n. sp.

Pseudoliotia nodenim n. sp.

Pseudoliotia philippinensis n. sp.

Pseudoliotia bellatula (Feng, 1996)

Pseudoliotia linguifera (Thiele, 1925) n. comb. (Figures 10D, 51A-F)

Vitrinella linguifera Thiele, 1925: 71, pl. XV, figs. 31-32.

Pseudoliotia linguifera (Thiele, 1925): OBIS Indo-Pacific database.

Type material: Indonesia: lectotype (Fig. 51A), here designated. ZMB/Moll – 108491 and 27 paralectotypes (21 s, 6 j), Indonesia, Padang; 1 paralectotype ZMB/Moll – 108493, Indonesia, Sunda Sea, 0°30'S-107°W; 4 paralectotypes, ZMB/Moll - 108492 Nias South Channel, 3°40'N-106°40'W.

Material examined: (33 s): The type material.

Type locality: Indonesia, Padang.

Description, based on the lectotype (ZMB/Moll – 108491): Shell small (<3.0 mm), solid, formed by 4 ½ whorls, orbicular, turbinate, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring about 520 µm in diameter, with about 2 ½ whorls and two distinct phases; the first totally smooth and the second with few fine tubercles, more concentrated near the suture, fin-

ishing with a sinuous labial edge. The teleoconch has a little more than 1 ¾ whorls, ornamented with nodulose spiral cords, axial ribs and conspicuous growth lines. The nodules are formed in the intersection of the axial ribs with the spiral cords. In the first whorl they are rounded, in the last one the nodules become sharply pointed. On the last whorl, 12 spiral cords can be seen, distributed between the suture and the inner part of the umbilicus; the

Figure 51. *Pseudoliotia linguifera* (Thiele, 1925). A: lectotype, 2.47 mm (ZMB/moll – 108491) Padang, Indonesia; B-C: paralectotypes, 2.8 and 2.9 mm (ZMB); D: protoconch; E-F: sculpture and detail. *Figura 51. Pseudoliotia linguifera* (Thiele, 1925). A: lectotipo, 2,47 mm (ZMB/moll – 108491) Padang, Indonesia; B-C: paralectotipos, 2,8 y 2,9 mm (ZMB); D: protoconcha; E-F: escultura y detalle.

cords from 1st to 5th have pointed nodules; the cords from 6th to 10th are smooth and only near the external lip present some small nodules. The 11th-12th cords are totally nodulose, with small, not very prominent nodules; the subsutural cord presents 37 pointed nodules. Adapically, there are no axial ribs in the spaces between the cords, and only marked growth lines can be seen. Abapically, between the cords 9th-10th, only fine

axial ribs can be observed near the edge of the outer lip; between the 10th-12th cords, the axial ribs are wider and connect the nodules forming rectangular spaces. In the rectangular reticulate between the spaces in the basal cords, no microtubercles have been observed. The spaces between the cords are concave.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, with nodulose spiral cords also inside; no particular cord is delimiting the umbilicus;

the cord located deeper inside is not nodulose, it becomes very thick and, when meeting the inner lip, forms a projection at the beginning of the columella. Aperture circular, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a thick callus; columella angled, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip indented by the termination of the cords which are prolonged to reach the inner edge.

Dimensions: the lectotype size is 2.47 mm in diameter and 1.71 mm in height (H/D: 0.58); the other largest shells (paralectotypes) have a size in maximum diameter of 2.80 and 2.90 mm.

Habitat: Unknown.

Pseudoliotia rudispiralis n. sp. (Figures 10E, 52A-D, 53A-F)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34115) and 3 paratypes (MNHN IM-2000-34116) in MNHN.

Material examined: (6 s): Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 4 s, Stn. DW1767, 8°19'S-160°40'E, 98-200 m. Papua New Guinea, PAPUA NIUGINI: 2 s, Alexishafen, Stn. PS14, 05°05.3'S-145°48.0'E, 8-13 m.

Type locality: Solomon Islands, 8°19'S-160°40'E, 98-200 m [SALOMON 1: Stn. DW1767].

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin words *rudis* which means "rough, unpolished", and *spira*, alluding to the cords of the shell.

Description: Shell small (<3.0 mm), solid, formed by up to 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, orbicular, turbinate, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, is totally smooth, measuring between 560-580 μ m in diameter, having over 2 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls and two distinct phases. The teleoconch has 2-2 $\frac{1}{4}$ whorls, and is ornamented with nodulose spiral cords, axial ribs and microtubercles. The nodules are sharp pointed and are formed at the intersections of the axial ribs with the spiral cords. On the last whorl 10-12 spiral nodulose cords distributed between the suture and the umbilicus can be seen; the subsutural cord presents between 28-31 pointed nodules. At the beginning of the teleoconch, the 2-3 first nodules of the subsutural and peripheral cords are connected by a wide axial rib; on the rest of the shell the axial ribs disappear in the spaces between the cords and are limited to the intersection of the cords. On the basal part, the axial ribs occupy the spaces

Distribution: Indonesia: Riau: Padang, Pulau and Sumatera Utara: Nias, Pulau.

Remarks: THIELE (1925) described and figured *V. linguifera*, pointing out the thick nodulose cord inside the umbilicus and which abuts on the beginning of the columella.

Pseudoliotia linguifera differs from the remaining species of the group, by its most depressed spire, the presence of marked growth lines adapically, the basal cords completely smooth without axial ribs in the interspaces, the shape and the large size of the cord in the inner part of the umbilicus and which marks the beginning of the columella.

between the cords, forming smaller nodules at the intersections. The spaces between the cords are concave.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, with nodulose spiral cords also inside; no particular cord delimits the umbilicus; the cord located deeper inside thickens where meeting the inner lip, and forms a projection at the beginning of the columella. Aperture circular, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a very thick callus; columella angled, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, unaffected by the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype size is 2.67 mm in diameter and 1.72 mm in height (H/D: 0.64). The paratype size 2.52 mm in diameter and 1.15 mm in height (H/D: 0.60).

Habitat: Infralittoral and circalittoral species dredged from 13 m to 98 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Solomon and Papua New Guinea.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp. is characterized by having both basal

Figure 52. *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.67 mm, MNHN, Solomon Is. Stn. DW1767, 98-200 m; B-C: paratype, 2.52 mm, MNHN, same locality; D: protoconch.

Figura 52. *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,67 mm, MNHN, Islas Salomón, Stn. DW1767, 98-200 m; B-C: paratipo, 2,52 mm, MNHN, la misma localidad; D: protoconcha.

cords and those inside the umbilicus nodulose, and marked axial ribs in the interspaces between them; adapically,

the axial ribs are limited to the intersection points with the cords, but without crossing completely the interspaces.

Pseudoliotia minor n. sp. (Figures 11A, 54A-G, 55A-E)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34117) and 8 paratypes (MNHN IM-2000-34118) in MNHN.

Material examined: (22 s): Philippines, PANGLAO 2004: 9 s, Bohol Island, Ubajan, Stn. S25, 9°45.1'N-123°51.0'E, 21 m, mud (type material); 3 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. T19, 9°42.2'N - 123°50.8'E, 10-26 m, mud; 4 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. D10, 9°42.4'N-123°50.6'E, 15-22 m, mud. MUSORSTOM 3: 6 s, N Panay Island, Stn. DR140, 11°42.6'N-122°34.5'E, 93-99 m.

Type locality: Philippines, Bohol Island, Ubajan, 9°45.1'N-123°51.0'E, 21 m, mud [PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S25].

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin word *minor*, alluding to the smaller size of some nodules in some of the spiral cords.

Figure 53. *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp. A: shell, 3.0 mm (MNHN) Papua New Guinea, Stn. PS14, 8-13 m; B-C: paratype, 3.26 mm MNHN, same locality; D: protoconch of the shell in figure A; E-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 53. *Pseudoliotia rudispiralis* n. sp. A: concha, 3,0 mm (MNHN) Papua Nueva Guinea, Stn. PS14, 8-13 m; B-C: paratipo, 3,26 mm MNHN, la misma localidad; D: protoconcha del ejemplar de la figura A; E-F: microescultura y detalle.

Description: Shell small (<3.5 mm), solid, formed by 4 ¼ whorls, orbicular, turbinate, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measures 590 µm in diameter; it has 2 ½ whorls and two

Figure 54. *Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 3.35 mm, Philippines, Bohol Island, Ubajan, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S25; D-E: apex and protoconch; F-G: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 54. *Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 3,35 mm, Filipinas, Isla de Bohol, Ubajan, PANGLAO 2004: Stn. S25; D-E: ápice y protoconcha; F-G: detalle de la microescultura.

distinct phases, the first one is totally smooth and the second with fine tubercles randomly distributed although

more concentrated near the suture. The teleoconch has about two whorls, ornamented with nodulose spiral cords and

Figure 55. *Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp. A-C: shells, 2.32, 2.16, 1.92 mm, Philippines, Bohol Island, Cortes, Campagne PANGLAO 2004, Stn. T19, 10-26 m, mud; D: protoconch; E: detail of the microsculpture. *Figura 55. Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp. A-C: conchas, 2,32, 2,16, 1,92 mm, Philippines, Isla de Bohol, Cortes, Campaña PANGLAO 2004, Stn. T19, 10-26 m, fango; D: protoconcha; E: detalle de la microescultura.

axial ribs. The nodules are sharp and are formed at the intersection of the axial ribs with the spiral cords. On the last whorl, 10 spiral cords can be seen, distributed between the suture and inside the umbilicus; the first five cords have thick pointed nodules, the following two (6th and 7th) are smooth and the remaining three (8th -10th) have thick rounded nodules at the

intersections with the thick axial ribs which occupy the interspaces between the cords; the subsutural cord presents 28-30 sharp nodules. Adapically, there are no axial ribs in the spaces between the cords, the axial sculpture being limited to the intersections with the cords. On the basal part, the axial ribs occupy the interspaces between the cords forming smaller nodules at the

Figure 56. *Pseudoliotia coronata* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.62 mm, Vanuatu, Fond Bay, BOA 1: Stn. DW 2441, 15°09'S-166°55'E, 72-147 m; D-E: apex and protoconch.

Figura 56. *Pseudoliotia coronata* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 2,62 mm, Vanuatu, Bahía Fond, BOA 1: Stn. DW 2441, 15°09'S-166°55'E, 72-147 m; D-E: ápice y protoconcha.

intersections. The nodules of the spiral cords are covered by minute, closely set lines of spiral tubercles (Fig. 54G). The spaces between strings are concave.

Umbilicus wide and deep, with nodulose spiral cords also inside; no particular cord delimits the umbilicus; the cord located deeper inside thickens where meeting the inner lip, and forms

a projection at the beginning of the columella. Aperture circular, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a very thick callus; columella angled, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, unaffected by the spiral cords.

Dimensions: The holotype is 3.35 mm in diameter and 2.15 mm in height (H/D: 0.64).

Habitat: Infralittoral species living at 10-26 m in mud bottoms. In Panay Island it has been dredged at 93-99 m.

Distribution: Only known from Bohol Island, Philippines.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia minor* n. sp. is characterized by having fine tubercles on the second phase of the protoconch; it has fewer spiral cords on the last whorl and the adapical cords have wide and sharp pointed nodules, with the axial ribs not continued in the interspaces, but limited to the intersections with the spiral cords. It is also characterized by having two basal cords almost smooth, except in the proximity of the aperture where they

have some small nodules; the remaining basal cords are all nodulose, with thick axial ribs in the interspaces. Another distinctive character is the microsculpture formed by fine, spirally aligned lines of closely set tubercles, located on the nodulose spiral cords.

The specimens with a less developed spire (≤ 2.5 mm) have the first two adapical cords with thick nodules and the other cords, both peripheral and basal, totally smooth, without axial ribs in the interspaces; only few shells had, on the last quarter of whorl, small nodules on basal and umbilical cords, and fine axial ribs in the interspaces.

Pseudoliotia coronata n. sp. (Figures 11B, 56A-E)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34119) and one paratype (MNHN IM-2000-34120) in MNHN.

Material examined: (2 s): Vanuatu, BOA 1: 2 s, Fond Bay, Stn. DW2441, 15°09'S-166°55'E, 72-147 m.

Type locality: Vanuatu, Fond Bay, 15°09'S-166°55'E, 72-147 m [BOA 1: DW2441].

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin word *corona*, "a crown", alluding to the aspect of the shell with elevated pointed nodules in the adapical cords.

Description: Shell small (<3.0 mm), solid, formed by 4 ½ whorls, orbicular, turbinate, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is protruding from the rest of the shell, measuring 560 μm in diameter with a little less of 2 ½ whorls; it is developed in two distinct phases, the first totally smooth and the second with very fine tubercles. The teleoconch has 2 1/8 whorls, ornamented with nodulose spiral cords and axial ribs. The nodules are sharply pointed and are formed in the intersection of the axial ribs with the spiral cords. On the last whorl, 10 spiral cords can be seen distributed between the suture and the inner part of the umbilicus; the three first cords have wide and pointed nodules; the following three (4th-6th) are initially smooth and later change to be nodulose; the following four (7th-10th) have smaller nodules at the intersections of the axial ribs with which are in the interspaces between the ribs; the subsutural cord presents 22 pointed nodules and the first peripheral cord, 24 nodules. Adapically, the interspaces between cords are very concave and

contain fine, oblique axial riblets. On the basal side, the axial riblets also occupy the space between the cords, forming smaller nodules at the intersections.

Umbilicus wide and deep, with nodulose spiral cords also inside; no particular cord delimits the umbilicus; the cord located deeper inside thickens where meeting the inner lip, and forms a projection at the beginning of the columella. Aperture circular, very prosocline; parietal area covered by a very thick callus; columella angled, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, margin unmodified by the spiral cords.

The spaces between the cords are very concave.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 2.62 mm in diameter, and 1.62 mm in height (H/D: 0.62).

Habitat: Circalittoral-upper bathyal species dredged at 72-147 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Vanuatu, the type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia coronata* n. sp. is characterized by the low number of nodules in the subsutural and peripheral

Figure 57. *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 2.88 mm, Fiji, NO Alis BORDAU 1, Stn. DW1435, 170-183 m; D: protoconch; E-F: sculpture and detail.

Figura 57. *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 2,88 mm, Fidji, NO Alis BORDAU 1, Stn. DW1435, 170-183 m; D: protoconcha; E-F: escultura y detalle.

ords; adapically, by the prominence and pointed shape of these, which give the appearance of a double crown; by the insertion, where approaching the outer

lip, of two cordlets between the cords forming the crown, and by the presence of thin and oblique axial ribs in the adapical interspaces between the cords.

Pseudoliotia nodosa n. sp. (Figure 11C, 57A-F, 58A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34121).

Material examined: (37 s): Fiji, BORDAU 1: 1 s, Ride de Lau, Vanua Balavu, Stn. DW1435, 17°11'S-178°45'W, 170-183 m (holotype). Vanuatu, SANTO 2006: 1 s, NE Aoré Island, Aimbue Bay, Stn. EP04, 15°33.0'S-15°33.4'S - 167°11.7-12.8'E, 89-109 m. MUSORSTOM 8: 1 s, Stn. DW1105, 15°03'S-167°07'E, 154-179 m. Philippines, PANGLAO 2005: 12 s, Bohol/Sulu seas sill, Dipolog Bay, Stn. DW2370, 8°33.7'N-123°08.6'E, 92-96 m, black mud. PANGLAO 2004: 22 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. T18, 9°41.8'N-123°49.9'E, 80-100 m, muddy bottom with sponges.

Type locality: Fiji, Ride de Lau, Vanua Balavu, 17°11'S-178°45'W, 170-183 m [BORDAU 1: Stn. DW1435].

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin adjective *nodosus*, alluding to the nodose cords.

Description: Shell small (<3.0 mm), solid, formed by about 4 ¼ whorls, turbinate, depressed, widely and deeply umbilicate.

The protoconch is in the same plane as the first whorl of teleoconch, measuring about 480 µm, with 1 ¾ to 2 whorls; it is developed in two distinct phases, the first one totally smooth and the second with fine tubercles uniformly distributed. The teleoconch has about 2 ½ whorls, ornamented with spiral cords bearing thick nodules, fine growth lines and micro-granules distributed randomly in the first half whorl of the teleoconch. In apertural view, 7 nodulose cords can be seen: 1 subsutural, 3 peripheral, 2 basal and 1 periumbilical. The space between the cords is concave. Adapically, in the spaces between the cords there are no axial ribs, but only fine growth lines; the axial ribs may be observed only between the basal cords. These basal cords are initially nodulose and later smooth; between them and after becoming smooth, there are equidistant axial ribs. The periumbilical cord is formed by a row of 10-14 thick rounded nodules; in the interspace between the inner basal cord and the periumbilical row of nodules, there are also axial riblets, two of which are abutting on the base of each nodule.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a thick and nodulose spiral cord; one nodulose cord located inside is definitely thickened when it reaches the inner lip and marks

a projection of the columella; one still more inner cord circumscribes the inner part of the umbilicus. The umbilical wall is slightly concave and bears only fine growth lines. Aperture circular; parietal area covered by a very thick callus; columella angled, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, unaffected by the spiral cords, forming an internal angle with the parietal edge.

Dimensions: The holotype size is 2.88 mm in diameter and 1.52 mm in height (H/D: 0.53).

Habitat: Circalittoral-upper bathyal species dredged between 96 and 170 m in black mud, fine mud sand and muddy bottom with sponges.

Distribution: Fiji, Vanuatu and Bohol Island in Philippines.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp. is characterized by having the microtubercles extended only on the ¾ of the first whorl of the teleoconch, by the quadrangular reticule formed by the axial ribs connecting the nodules of the first two cords, by a combination of elliptical and sharp nodules adapically; additional diagnostic characters are the basal cords nodulose at the beginning and then becoming smooth, the axial ribs which occupy spaces between basal cords throughout the last whorl, and the presence of two nodulose cordlets inside the umbilicus which abut on the thickening and the reflection of the columella and the parietal area.

Pseudoliotia nodenim n. sp. (Figure 11D, 59A-F, 60A-E)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (MNHN IM-2000-34122).

Material examined: (2 s): Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Stn. DW1762, 8°40'S - 160°04'E, 396-411 m (holotype). Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8: 1 s, Stn. DW1072, 15°40'S - 167°20'E, 622-625 m.

Figure 58. *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp. A-C: shell, 2.85 mm, Vanuatu, NE Aoré Is., Aimbue Bay, Stn. EP04, 89-109 m; D-E: apex and protoconch; F: detail of the sculpture.
Figura 58. *Pseudoliotia nodosa* n. sp. A-C: concha, 2,85 mm, Vanuatu, NE Aoré Is., Babía Aimbue, Stn. EP04, 89-109 m; D-E: ápice y protoconcha; F: detalle de la escultura.

Type locality: Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1: 1 s, Stn. DW1762, 8°40'S - 160°04'E, 396-411 m.

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the two Latin words: *nodus* "knot" or "node", and the adverb *enim* "evidently" making reference to the sculpture of the shell.

Figure 59. *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 1.72 mm, Solomon Islands, SALOMON 1, Stn. DW1762, 396-411 m; D: protoconch; E-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 59. *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 1,72 mm, Islas Salomón, SALOMON 1, Stn. DW1762, 396-411 m; D: protoconcha; E-F: microescultura y detalle.

Description: Shell very small (<2.00 mm), solid, formed by 3 ½ whorls, turritate, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is almost in the same plane as the first whorl of teleoconch,

measuring about 540 μm, with 2 ¼ whorls; it is developed in two distinct phases, the first one totally smooth and the second with a finely frosted surface. The teleoconch has 1 ¼ whorls and is

Figure 60. *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp. A-C: shell, 1.19 mm, Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8, Stn. DW1072, 622-625 m; D-E: apex and protoconch.

Figura 60. *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp. A-C: concha, 1,19 mm, Vanuatu, MUSORSTOM 8, Stn. DW1072, 622-625 m; D-E: ápice y protoconcha.

completely covered by spiral cords bearing thick nodules; adapically the nodules are large and elliptical and, on the basal part, they are thick and round. Fine growth lines and uniformly distributed microtubercles can be seen all over the surface. In apertural view, 7 nodulose cords: 1 subsutural, 3 peripheral, 2

basal and 1 periumbilical can be seen. The space between the cords is concave. Adapically, in the first $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl, the nodules of the two first cords are connected by thick axial ribs, forming a quadrangular reticule; subsequently the axial ribs disappear and only fine growth lines are observed. The basal

cords are completely nodulose; the inner cord has thick rounded nodules and the outer one, thinner and sharper ones; in the last 1/4 whorl, the nodules of both cords are weaker. The periumbilical cord is formed by 13 thick rounded nodules; between the basal internal cord and the periumbilical one, there are no axial ribs.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a thick and nodulose spiral cord. The umbilical wall is slightly concave and bears only fine growth lines and a fine spiral cordlet. Aperture nearly circular; parietal area covered by a thick callus; columella curved, thick and reflected towards the umbilicus, forming an angle with the parietal area; outer lip thick, forming an

internal angle with the parietal area, externally scalloped by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: The holotype size is 1.72 mm in diameter and 0.90 mm in height (H/D: 0.52).

Habitat: Dredged at 411-622 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Solomon Islands, its type locality, and from Vanuatu.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia nodenim* n. sp. is characterized by having elliptical, sharp nodules on the cords, by the rectangular reticule formed in the first 1/2 whorl by the axial ribs connecting the nodules of the first two cords, by the fully nodulose basal cords, and by lacking axial ribs in the interspaces of the basal cords.

Pseudoliotia philippinensis n. sp. (Figure 11E, 61A-G)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-34123) and 6 paratypes (MNHN IM-2000-34124) in MNHN.

Material examined: (21 s): Philippines, Panglao 2004: 7 s, Bohol Island, Maribojoc Bay, Stn. T11, 78-95 m, sponges and muddy sand (type material); 14 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. G1, 9°41.9'N-123°49.5'E, 100 m, fine muddy sand.

Type locality: Bohol Island, Maribohoc Bay, Stn. T11, 78-95 m, sponges and muddy sand.

Etymology: The specific name is derived from the name of the archipelago where the species was collected.

Description: Shell very small (<2.50 mm), solid, formed by 3 1/4 whorls, turbinate, depressed, widely umbilicate.

The protoconch is almost in the same plane as the first whorl of teleoconch, measuring about 450 μ m, with 2.1 whorls; it is developed in two distinct phases, the first totally smooth and the second with fine tubercles uniformly distributed. The teleoconch has a little more than 1 whorl and is completely covered by spiral cords of thick nodules; adapically, the nodules are large and elliptical and, on the basal part, they are thick and round. Fine growth lines and spirally aligned microtubercles can be seen all over the surface. In apertural view, 7 nodulose cords can be seen: 1 subsutural, 3 peripheral, 2 basal and 1 periumbilical. The space between the cords is concave. Adapically, in the first 1/2 whorl, the nodules of the two first cords are connected by thick axial ribs,

forming a quadrangular reticule; subsequently the axial ribs disappear and there are only fine growth lines; fine axial ribs can be seen on the base between the basal cords.

The basal cords are totally nodulose. The innermost one has wide rounded nodules; on the outermost one they are a little finer and more sharply pointed; in the last 1/4 of whorl, the nodules of both cords are attenuated, and fine axial equidistant riblets can be observed between them. The periumbilical cord is formed by the alignment of 13 wide rounded nodules. In the interspace between the inner basal cord and the periumbilical row of nodules, in the last 1/4 of whorl, there are also axial riblets, two or three of which are abutting on the base of each nodule.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a thick and nodulose spiral cord. The umbilical wall is

Figure 61. *Pseudoliotia philippinensis* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.55 mm (MNHN), Philippines, Bohol Island, Maribohoc Bay, Stn. T11, 78-95 m; B-C: paratypes, 2.2, 2.5 mm, same locality, MNHN; D: protoconch of the holotype; E: detail of the aperture; F-G: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 61. Pseudoliotia philippinensis n. sp. A: *holotipo*, 1,55 mm (MNHN), Filipinas, Isla de Bohol, Bahía de Maribohoc, Stn. T11, 78-95 m; B-C: *paratipos*, 2,2, 2,5 mm, la misma localidad, MNHN; D: *protoconcha* del holotipo; E: *detalle de la abertura*; F-G: *microescultura y detalle*.

slightly concave and bears fine growth lines and, deep inside, a spiral cord which thickens where meeting the inner lip and forms a distinct projection on the columella. Aperture circular; parietal area covered by a very thick callus; columella angled, very thick and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thick, forming an internal angles with the parietal area, externally indented by the termination of the cords.

Dimensions: The holotype is 1.55 mm in diameter and 1.0 mm in height (H/D: 0.50). Some paratypes reach up to 2.5 mm.

Habitat: Circalittoral, dredged at 78-95 m in sponges and muddy sand bottom.

Pseudoliotia bellatula (Feng, 1996) n. comb. (Figure 11F, 62A-F, 63A-F, 64A-D)

Circlotoma bellatula Feng, 1996. *Studies on Marine Fauna and Flora and Biogeography of the Nansha Islands and Neighbouring Waters II*, 85–205 [Type locality: Hainan Nansha de Half Moon Shoal, Nansha Islands] Pleistocene, Recent, China.

Pseudoliotia bellatula (Feng, 1996).

Type material: Holotype in Nanjing Institute of Geology and Palaeontology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (122397).

Material examined: (34 s): Philippines, PANGLAO 2004: 17 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. T26, 123-135 m, mud; 12 s, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. D10, 15-22 m, mud. Papua New Guinea: PAPUA NIUGINI: 5 s, W Sek Island, Stn. PD27, 30-35 m.

Description, based on the material examined: Shell minute (< 1.5 mm), formed by 3 ¾ whorls, orbicular, very depressed, carinate and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch has 2 ¾ whorls, measures about 600 µm and has 2 different phases; the first one is completely smooth and the second has fine tubercles randomly distributed; in very fresh shell fine spiral lines can be observed.

The teleoconch has more than 1 whorl and its periphery is carinate. It is ornamented with nodulose carinae, ribs and axial folds. Seven carinae are distributed between the suture and the umbilicus: 1 is subsutural, 3 peripheral, 1 basal and 1 periumbilical. The nodules of the subsutural and peripheral carinae are elongated and pointed, and those from the basal and periumbilical carinae are rounded, becoming somewhat more pointed where they approach the edge of

Distribution: Only known from Bohol Island, its type locality.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia philippinensis* n. sp. is characterized by the quadrangular reticule formed by the subsutural and peripheral cords with the axial ribs on the first ½ whorl of the teleoconch, by the wide elliptical nodules on the first two cords, by having fully nodulose basal cords, and by having fine axial grooves and one spiral band inside the umbilicus.

It can be distinguished from *P. nodenim* n. sp. because this species lacks the axial sculpture on the base, has more nodulose basal cords and has a wider protoconch.

the outer lip; there are 35 nodules on the peripheral carina and 19 on the periumbilical one. Generally, the axial ribs do not cross the spaces between the cords, but limited to the area of intersection with the carinae; only at the beginning of the teleoconch, there are several axial ribs, very thin, which connect the nodules of the subsutural and peripheral carinae, but these subsequently disappear.

Umbilicus wide and deep, funnel-shaped, delimited by a nodulose spiral cord. The umbilical wall is concave and bears wide axial folds which continue the nodules towards the inner part of the umbilicus. Aperture with octagonal form due to the spiral carinae which angle it internally; the parietal area is covered by a thin callous layer; the columella is arched and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip thin, externally indented by the termination of the carinae.

Figure 62. *Pseudoliotia bellatula* (Feng, 1996). A-C: shell, 1.5 mm, Philippines, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. T26, 123-135 m; D: protoconch; E-F: sculpture and microsculpture.

Figura 62. *Pseudoliotia bellatula* (Feng, 1996). A-C: concha, 1,5 mm, Filipinas, Isla de Bohol, Cortes, Stn. T26, 123-135 m; D: protoconcha; E-F: escultura y microescultura.

Dimensions: The shells photographed measure between 1.34 and 1.41 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Infralittoral to circalittoral, dredged or trawled on muddy bottoms at 22-123 m depth.

Distribution: Nansha Islands, China; Bohol Island, Cortes, Philippines and Sek Island, Papua New Guinea.

Remarks: *Pseudoliotia bellatula* is characterized by the large size of the protoconch and by having it ornamented on its

Figure 63. *Pseudoliotia bellatula* (Feng, 1996). A-C: shell, 1.4 mm. Philippines, Bohol Island, Cortes, Stn. D10, 15-22 m; D: protoconch; E-F: detail of the protoconch.

Figura 63. *Pseudoliotia bellatula* (Feng, 1996). A-C: concha, 1,4 mm, Filipinas, Isla de Bohol, Cortes, Stn. D10, 15-22 m; D: protoconcha; E-F: detalle de la protoconcha.

second phase with 7 lines of spirally aligned tubercles; also by the pointed shape and small size of the nodules and the octagonal shape of its aperture.

Its general shape resembles a *Circulinae*, however its systematic placement in

Pseudoliotia is mainly based on the development and ornamentation of the protoconch, on the existence of axial ribs and on the form and development of the nodules; proposing its new location on the genus *Pseudoliotia* and leaving the genus *Circlotoma*.

Figure 64. *Pseudoliotia bellatula* (Feng, 1996). A-C: shell, 1.45 mm, Papua New Guinea, W Sek Island, Stn. PD27, 30-35 m; D: protoconch.

Figura 64. *Pseudoliotia bellatula* (Feng, 1996). A-C: concha, 1,45 mm, Papua Nueva Guinea, W Isla de Sek, Stn. PD27, 30-35 m; D: protoconcha.

FOSSIL SPECIES

Pseudoliotia motobuensis McNeil, 1960 (Figure 65A-B)

"*Cyclostrema*" *micans*. NOMURA & ZIMBO, 1936: 264, pl. 11, fig. 35.

Pseudoliotia motobuensis McNeil, 1960: 35, pl. 10, figs. 26-28 [Type locality: Nakosi sand, Untenko, Okinawa].

Type material: Holotype (USNM 562888). Examined by photography.

Description, in McNEIL (1960): "Shell medium small, whorls round, spire low. Protoconch, not projecting, consisting of about one full smooth whorl. Aperture round with the faint suggestion of an indentation at the position of the anal sinus; edge of entire

aperture rounded. Umbilicus open. Sculpture consisting of prominent spiral ridges, about 7 in number of which the 2 along the periphery and the 1 above are the most prominent, crossed by small raised ridges along the growth lines, the 2 series of ridges

Figure 65. *Pseudoliotia motobuensis* MacNeil, 1960. Holotype, 8.2 mm [USNM MO 562888]. C-D. *Cyclostrema eburnea* Nevill & Nevill, 1875, India, original figuration.

Figura 65. *Pseudoliotia motobuensis* MacNeil, 1960. Holotipo, 8,2 mm [USNM MO 562888]. C-D: *Cyclostrema eburnea* Nevill & Nevill, 1875, India, representación original.

giving the shell a strongly cancellate appearance”.

Holotype (USNM 562888) measures: height 5 mm, diameter 8.2 mm.

Distribution: Pliocene, Nakoshi sand, Okinawa.

Localities: Nakoshi sand, Untenko (figured type), Gabusoga (figured by NOMURA & ZIMBO, 1936).

Remarks: MACNEIL (1960) wrote: “The specimens reported by Nomura and Zinbo from Gabusoga, Okinawa, are from the same fossil zone. The Recent *Cyclostrema pulchella* Dunker, from Japan, is closely related to this species, but it is smaller and does not have the spiral ridges as strongly developed.

“*Delphinula reeveana*” as figured in DICKERSON (1922: 2, fig. 17) from the Miocene or Pliocene of the Philippines may be closely related, but it appears to have a more deflected parietal callus.

Unidentified specimens of a species, probably *P. micans*, closely related to the one here described were taken by the Albatross expedition from Tawi Tawi, and by Byrant and Palmer from off Java”.

Actually, the species having more affinity with *P. motobuensis* is *P. reeviana*, with which it shares most of morphological traits. We have not been able to examine the protoconch and or the ornamentation of microtubercles of the teleoconch, therefore we cannot confirm if it is the same species or not.

SPECIES EXCLUDED

A doubt was *Cyclostrema eburnea* Nevill & Nevill, 1875 (4.75 mm, (NHMUK 195.12.1.36) from India, which original figuration was included in the Figure

65C-D, and finally we decided to exclude it from the present study due that the type material was very eroded that the shell could not be examined.

CONCLUSIONS AND COMMENTS

Pseudoliotia is a genus of small vitrinellids characterized by having a shell with a more or less depressed spire, nodulose spiral carinae, axial ribs connecting the nodules and a very oblique aperture. The species vary in form and in size, from 1 to 10 mm.

Their external anatomy is very similar to that of the genus *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865 confirming the monophyletic origin of both genera, as explained by CRISCIONE & PONDER (2013). The animals of *P. oscostata* n. sp. and *P. faceta* n. sp. present (Fig. 2):

- long distally bilobed snout
- long cephalic tentacles with motile cilia and stiff compound cilia on the distal ends
- a pair of pallial tentacles
- anterior end of the foot expanded into small lateral projections
- metapodial tentacle absent
- posterior end of the foot bilobed

The absence of a metapodial tentacle in both species confirmed the statement by PONDER & DE KEYZER (1998) regarding the possibility of presence/absence of this organ in *Pseudoliotia* species.

The posteriorly notched foot lacking a metapodial tentacle and the pair of pallial tentacles are characters shared by *Pseudoliotia* and *Circulus* (PONDER, 1994).

Number of species

Pseudoliotia is a genus of predominantly Indo-Pacific distribution. From the 24 previously known species, only one, *P. hattenbergeri* Rolán & Rubio, 2002, is from the West African Coast. The lack of knowledge regarding this group is probably due to the small size of most of their species and to the fact that the area has so far been scarcely sampled in a little known Pacific Ocean.

Although this study is developed in the area with a higher density of species of the genus, the samplings have not been very extensive, and therefore no new material was collected for some species. For example, *Pseudoliotia bellatula* has its type locality in China; *P. linguifera* in Indonesia; *P. philtata*, *P. acidalia*, *P. tropica*, *P. radians*, *P. axialis*, *P. gowllandi*, *P. speciosa*, *P. micans* in Australia; *P. granulosa*, *P. pulchella* in Japan; *P. henjamensis* in the Persian Gulf and the Red Sea; *P. reeviana* in Singapore; *P. godeti* and *P. pulchella* in Viet Nam;

However, the collaboration of numerous museums has allowed to remedy these shortcomings of samplings and to get photographs of the type material of species which had not been collected. We do not mention *P. eburnea* for the little information we have on this species.

Type material photographed in museums

The type material from the previously known species for comparative purposes have been photographed from several museums:

Cyclostrema micans A. Adams, 1850; *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864; *Liotia speciosa* Angas, 1871; *Liotia gowllandi* Brazier, 1874; *Microtheca acidalia* Melvill & Standen, 1899; *Cyclostrema cristata* Sowerby, 1900 and *Cyclostrema henjamense* Melvill & Standen, 1903 in NHMUK.

Cyclostrema godeti Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907; *Cyclostrema bushi* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 and *Liotia angasi* Crosse, 1864 in MNHN.

Pseudoliotia axialis Laseron, 1958; *Discreliotia radians* Laseron, 1958; *Pseudoliotia tropica* Laseron, 1958; *Liotia tribulatio-*

nis Hedley, 1909; *Liotia philtata* Hedley, 1900 and *Pseudoliotia liliputia* Laseron, 1958 in AMS.

Cyclostrema anaglyptum A. Adams, 1863 in AMV.

Liotia asteriscus Gould, 1859 in USNM.

Cyclostrema pulchellum Dunker, 1860 in SMF.

Vitrinella linguifera Thiele, 1925 in ZMB.

Vitrinella caelata Garrett, 1873 in ANSP.

Pseudoliotia granulosa Kuroda & Habe, 1971 in NSMT.

Amount of collected material

Altogether, the amount of studied material is relatively low, probably because the places where these species lived were hardly accessible with methods of sampling (living in some depth, under rocks), by which the greater part of the collection was made from shell-bearing sediments.

The previously known species stand out by their abundance:

P. tribulationis, 94 specimens

P. bellatula, 34

P. linguifera, 33

P. reeviana, 15

The remainder ones have a short number of 1 or 2 types in museums.

From the species here described as new, only in one case is there a large amount of material, and in a few more cases there is a moderate number of specimens:

P. inanis with 354 specimens

P. nodosa and *P. dispersa*, 37

P. gabrielruedai, 36

P. minor, 22

P. philippinensis, 21

P. faceta, 16

P. plurifunus and *P. teresae*, 13

P. plusnodosa, 10

P. fijiensis, 9

P. rudispiralis, 6

The remainder ones are only represented with 1-2 specimens.

Distribution of species by countries

Examining the species found in any country we have that Vanuatu is that in which more species were collected. This is the total species found in each one:

Vanuatu: 10 species: *P. dispersa*, *P. vicina*, *P. oscostata*, *P. gabrielruedai*, *P. plurifunus*, *P. tribulationis*, *P. inanis*, *P. coronata*, *P. nodosa*, *P. nodenim*,

Australia: 10: *P. micans*, *P. speciosa*, *P. gowllandi*, *P. calliglypta*, *P. axialis*, *P. radians*, *P. tropica*, *P. acidalia*, *P. tribulationis*, *P. philtata*,

Philippines: 9: *P. dispersa*, *P. cristata*, *P. indicta*, *P. faceta*, *P. tribulationis*, *P. minor*, *P. nodosa*, *P. philippinensis*, *P. bellatula*,

Papua New Guinea: 9: *P. gowllandi*, *P. dispersa*, *P. oscostata*, *P. indicta*, *P. intermixta*, *P. sementis*, *P. tribulationis*, *P. rudispiralis*, *P. bellatula*,

Fiji: 6: *P. caelata*, *P. gabrielruedai*, *P. plurifunus*, *P. fijiensis*, *P. inanis*, *P. nodosa*,

Solomon: 5: *P. vicina*, *P. gabrielruedai*, *P. profundus*, *P. rudispiralis*, *P. nodenim*,

Japan: 5: *P. pulchella*, *P. asteriscus*, *P. reeviana*, *P. anaglypta*, *P. granulosa*,

New Caledonia: 3: *P. gabrielruedai*, *P. plurifunus*, *P. inanis*,

Tahiti: 3: *P. plusnodosa*, *P. distincta*, *P. seposita*,

Red Sea: 3: *P. micans*, *P. henjamense*, *P. tribulationis*,

Vietnam: 2: *P. pulchella*, *P. godeti*,

Indonesia: 2: *P. reeviana*, *P. linguifera*,

China: 2: *P. asteriscus*, *P. bellatula*,

Hong Kong: 1: *P. asteriscus*,

Singapore: 1: *P. reeviana*,

Madagascar: 1: *P. pressa*,

Korea: 1: *P. pulchella*,

Reunion 1: *P. teresae*,

Persian Gulf: 1: *P. henjamense*,

Taiwan: 1: *P. salva*.

Distribution areas of the species

The distribution area of the studied species of the genus *Pseudoliotia* is variable in its extension. Even having present that in some species the samples were scarce, we found many differences and the following information can give an idea:

Only three species were found in 4 countries:

-*P. tribulationis* in Vanuatu, Philippines, Papua New Guinea and Red Sea;

-*P. reeviana* in Indonesia, Singapore, Philippines and Japan;

-*P. gabrielruedai* in New Caledonia, Vanuatu, Solomon and Fiji.

Five species were found in 3 countries:
-*P. asteriscus* in Hong-Kong, China and Japan;

-*P. dispersa* in Philippines, Vanuatu and Papua New Guinea;

-*P. plurifunus* and *P. inanis* in Vanuatu, New Caledonia and Fiji;

-*P. nodosa* in Philippines, Fiji and Vanuatu.

In only two countries were found the following 9 species:

-*P. micans* in Australia and the Red Sea;

-*P. gowllandi* in Australia and Papua New Guinea;

-*P. vicina* and *P. nodenim* in Vanuatu and Solomon.

-*P. oscostata* in Vanuatu and Papua New Guinea;

-*P. henjamensis* in Persian Gulf and the Red Sea;

-*P. pulchella* in Japan and Korea;

-*P. indicta* and *P. bellatula* in Philippines and Papua New Guinea;

-*P. rudispiralis* in Solomon and Papua New Guinea.

And the following 38 species were found only in one country:

-*P. speciosa*, *P. calliglypta*, *P. axialis*, *P. radians*, *P. tropica*, *P. acidalia*, *P. philtata* in Australia;

-*P. cristata*, *P. faceta*, *P. minor*, *P. philippinensis* in Philippines;

-*P. anaglypta*, *P. granulosa* in Japan;

-*P. plusnodosa*, *P. distincta*, *P. seposita* in Tahiti;

-*P. caelata*, *P. fijiensis* in Fiji;

-*P. pulchella*, *P. godeti* in Viet Nam;

-*P. intermixta*, *P. sementis* in Papua New Guinea;

-*P. teresae* in Reunion;

-*P. profundus* in Solomon;

-*P. pressa* in Madagascar;

-*P. linguifera* in Indonesia;

-*P. coronata* in Vanuatu.

Depth of the collecting

Pseudoliotia species have a littoral to bathyal distribution, with a bathymetric range between 0-1100 m. From some species with little material we have not enough information. This is the range from those species previously known:

-Intertidal for *P. micans*, *P. asteriscus*, *P. pulchella*, *P. speciosa*;

-Between intertidal to 100 m for *P. granulosa*;

-Between 12 and 100 m for *P. tribulationis*;

-15 m for *P. henjamensis*;

-below 20 m for *P. radians*, *P. reeviana*, *P. acidalia*, *P. bellatula*.

From the rest of the known species (11 taxa) the depth of the collecting was unknown or the information is not clear.

The new species described in the present work can be divided in three lots in relation of the depth of collecting:

-Intertidal to 10 m for *P. indicta*, *P. sementis*, *P. faceta*, *P. oscostata*;

-Between 10 and 100 m for *P. dispersa*, *P. intermixta*, *P. pressa*, *P. rudispiralis*, *P. minor*, *P. philippinensis*; in the case of *P. gabrielruedai* in Fiji was collected between 14-60 m, while other samples were collected between 98-184 m.

-Between 100 and 600 m for *P. teresae*, *P. salva*, *P. plurifunus*, *P. fijiensis*, *P. plusnodosa*, *P. distincta*, *P. seposita*, *P. inanis*, *P. coronata*, *P. nodosa*, *P. nodenim*.

Out of these groups we must mention the following ones:

-Deeper than 1000 m for *P. profundus*; also, *P. vicina* was collected in a sample below 1000 m, but in another one the depth was only of 7 m.

Habitat

We must have in consideration that most of the samples collected were formed by empty shells. Only in five species live material was obtained:

-*P. pulchella* 11 spms;

-*P. dispersa*, 1 spm;

-*P. reeviana*, 17 spms;

-*P. faceta*, 16 spms;

-*P. inanis*, 2 spms.

So, most of the species have been studied from empty shells and so the information on the habitat was obtained from the literature, it is wanting, or it is not reliable.

From the literature, we have information, for example, on *P. speciosa* and *P. micans*, and also from *P. pulchella* (Dunker, 1860) which was collected from the undersides of buried stones in embayments (SASAKI, 2008).

From the previously known species, the examined material from the museums, the information on the habitat is wanting in some cases, or is not completely informative. In 12 species there is no information: *P. caelata*, *P. calliglypta*, *P. bushae*, *P. godeti*, *P. axialis*, *P. radians*, *P. tropica*, *P. reeviana*, *P. anaglypta*, *P. cristata*, *P. philtata*, *P. linguifera*.

In others the information is short but provides some clues:

-*P. micans*, *P. speciosa*: on seagrasses and on hard objects (like wood, stones) in estuaries (PONDER & DE KEIZER, 1998) or under rocks;

-*P. asteriscus*, *P. acidalia*: sandy bottom;

-*P. pulchella*: tide pools and rocks;

-*P. gowlandi*: under stones;

-*P. henjamensis*: coarse sand;

-*P. granulosa*: sandy gravel;

-*P. tribulationis*: mud and sand; in caves or holes of the rocks;

-*P. bellatula*: muddy bottoms.

In the newly described species we also lack information for 15 of them: *P. indicta*, *P. teresae*, *P. intermixta*, *P. salva*, *P. sementis*, *P. plurifunus*, *P. fijiensis*, *P. profundus*, *P. plusnodosa*, *P. distincta*, *P. seposita*, *P. inanis*, *P. rudispiralis*, *P. coronata* and *P. nodenim*. This has an explanation because most of them are species with a very small number of specimens collected.

The species for which we have some information are:

-*P. dispersa*, *P. gabrielruedai*, *P. faceta*: muddy and sand bottoms;

-*P. vicina*: sandy bottom;

-*P. oscostata*: small embayment with muddy mangrove and nearby coral;

-*P. pressa*: sandy concretions;

-*P. minor*: muddy bottoms;

-*P. nodosa*: black mud, fine mud and sandy and mud;

-*P. philippinensis*: mud and sand bottoms with sponges;

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